

The design phenomenon

How design ability is present across
professional fields

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Master Thesis

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To my dear uncle
Peter and my loved aunt
Mariana, even if we can't
touch you now, you will
always be with us...

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1 INTRODUCTION

Dear reader, this will be the only part in this document that will be written as first person. It contains my perception and impulses; I believe it will help you to better understand the context which leads to this thesis. I present myself not as a researcher, but rather as a designer formed in a faculty of pure art. Yes, I could be called an artist given my formation and academic foundations. During my bachelor studies, I was educated with a strong anti-design spirit of the 80's, next to painters, sculptors, and engravers. Until a few years following my graduation, my school tried to preserve the essence of the Bauhaus through the insight of Bruno Munari, a founding collaborator in the original curriculum of my academic program. The reason why I mention this detail will take importance while examining a mandatory question to start this research: What is design?

I ask myself this question from time to time. It started when I decided to study industrial design, and even today more than 15 years later, I do it in my spare time. Contrastingly, this curiosity never comes to me when I am at work. When I am in a project, I proceed with a clear understanding of what I know and don't. I solve the ambiguities and there is no space for thoughts of ontological reflection. It is worth noticing that a designer asking about design is more an ontological issue than praxiological. This is not a particular case; no labor addresses the meaning of its profession because it has an ostensive definition in their actions. So, this question comes to me as a retrospective, in conclusion and relation of what I have been doing.

The answer has is of intrinsic importance to my labor, my role, even how I live my life. It sounds like a serious matter, and the reason is that for me my discipline is a way of life and not something that I do for life. So, the meaning of design is a cornerstone in the construction of all my conceptions of my profession, a word that, by the way, has its root meaning in profess. Moreover, it is thanks to this elusive answer that we acquire a perspective of the design field where we stand our professional practice. If you know where you are, you can go wherever you want. It's the same for this research, a necessary starting line is establishing a definition of design. After that we will move forward to

the framework of this thesis, and its main issue: Describe how design ability is shared among different professions in special with non-design related disciplines.

Then we go back to ask, what is design? It is a tricky question as design is a polysemous word used in many contexts. So, at the end of my bachelor's, I arrived at what I believed was a certain truth: design is a verb and a subject. That, I would say, was my most valuable learning of that time and drove most of my thought process. Design could be a product of a work but also could be referred to the process of the work itself, something that later I will recognize as an activity. Years later in my postgraduate degree of Industrial Design I ran into the phrase from whom I consider my second mentor, John Heskett: "Design is to design a design to produce a design" Heskett and I, if a comparison is allowed, regard the question of "what is design" differently and, though his proposal is much deeper and more complex, our core suspicions align. Worth mentioning is that he was an economist, and I am a designer, and my perspective turns pessimistic as the time passes, because I conclude that this polysemy has insidious deep problems for the profession.

Invariably, having a diverse set of definitions leads to misconceptions and misunderstandings. It's like if a sailor has only variable reference points, imagine if Columbus tried to arrive at what he believed was India without a compass or the north star to orient him. I had been out to sea. Where everything is blue and there is nothing else but water and clouds, if it weren't for the fix references, you can't trace a course, your efforts could be in vain and at the end you would die... it's a horrible destiny if you don't have something to guide you. For the departments inside a design faculty that don't have a clear definition of design is the same. Moreover, this lack of clarity and common understanding affects the comprehension of design ability, that it is also translated to the professional field. As a result, workplace disputes and debates across disciplines and backgrounds, with misconstrued ideas about design emerge.

So, dealing with this ambiguity that surrounds design is a necessary condition that should be solved. Doing it can substantially improve how designers integrate different teams of disciplines and backgrounds. While enhancing their own practice and exploring deeper the different dimensions of design. So,

I again return to the spark question, what is design? The definition that I will present will be an ostensive meaning. Established as a primitive conception of the empirical experience, is a proposal useful although it is limited but has been the base of my research and practice, so this introduction is the best place to present it.

Lexical, operative and stipulative meanings of design will be thoughtfully revised in the chapter that defines the study variable. However, all of them are born from what will be presented in this introduction. Someone could argue, why must an ostensive definition be clarified? Why would a designer need it? It's simple, as Antoine de Saint-Exupéry would say: sometimes "the essential is invisible to the eyes" (1984). As being conflicted by the amount of knowledge to explore, without an academic or scientific ground to support our opinions, even with the experience of our learning and practice. We forgot to look around us, and give as done, what science and humanities share to our discipline. We ignore that an epistemology in design needs to establish its study object on the base of the ostensive, what we perceive and recognize. From there we can talk about establishing a "science of the artificial."

I propose the following definition not as a formulation but as an ostensive realization: Design is a natural phenomenon. One that shapes our world unintentionally but driven by a strong causality. Even the most planned project will have unexpected results, they will also be part of the final shape of our products. These unforeseen events are where the nature of design resides, a fruit of determinism without a willing. Thus, fundamentally there is design in the inorganic, you can see it from a stalactite to a mountain, in the atoms and the galaxy. So, does not need a conscious or intention to be produced, I understand that could be controversial, but is an instance to recognize design over the living beings.

Recognizing the proposal definition does not mean that we should neglect the wide variety of popular uses established over time. It had been and will be multiple attempts to grasp the comprehension of design. However, we, as designers, need a clear reference to start our trip in the wide sea of our practice and research. That is what our discipline lacks right know and answering this question should be one of our main concerns.

This has more relevance today than ever as we are in the dawn of a new era, where the artificial intelligence questions us about the ownership of the design practice as well as many other activities. We should not be afraid, machines could design, as a step from this natural phenomenon. Even if they are not conscious, design happens from a process that once in movement, searches its equilibrium. And that struggle is where the design manifests.

This phenomenon is a process where change, be it virtual or physical, is both the catalyst and the main feature of transformation. As a process, design has characteristics, the chief amongst them being organization. There is no design without organization, even the chaos has design within and that is the reason why deep down there is order inside. Consider how it is possible to find evidence of this struggle for order from even the atoms that compose our world. One can find a natural mineral as a pyrite ore that grows as a perfect cube, bismuth shaping a hopper crystal, or baryte a desert rose.

Furthermore, design is a phenomenon that is also present in animals. We can take bees and their hexagonal honeycombs, or spiderwebs as an evident example. Intelligence is not a main factor, as has been demonstrated with experiments on the slime mold *Physarum polycephalum*. However, it is thanks through its transmigration to the living world, design acquires many plugins, some of them are easy to identify and so highlighted that could be mistaken with the phenomenon itself, like creativity and aesthetic. Many times, associated as an equivalence or even treated as synonyms.

Naturally, the design phenomenon manifests itself in human activity; humans, consciously, appropriate it to a point where it has become a discipline in its own right. To master the discipline, humans had to acquire and perfect specific skills and knowledge. This know-how is addressed by various research as design ability since the start of the previous century and the belief of its presence in all the population is the focus on this thesis.

Every one of us has their own opinions about design, we should stand for it, share them, confront them, and arrive at a common understanding. Design needs a clear statement, a common belief that assembles us in one voice and helps us to go further. Of course, opinions on the matter are several and debates are inevitable. I maintain, however, that rallying behind one voice will advance

the discipline. We have the responsibility to understand this better than the rest, because we are professional designers, so we profess our lives to Design.

A disclaimer is warranted. The term design is used profusely in this paper. Likely, those who respect the proper use of the term and find that it is prostituted nowadays would prefer restraint and find this paper off-putting. I would have included myself in this group. But in authoring this paper and choosing the right moments to use the term, I have found it more rewarding to embrace the real meaning of “talking about design”—coincidentally, the title of my first reading on professional design—and I hope readers do too. This work is a place that I consider ideal to pronounce design like it is, as I understand, as I learned, as I want to communicate it.

2 CONTEXT

From Simon Hartman in the 60’s to Erik Stolterman in this last decade, the statement that the existence of design practice precedes the formal programs of design is being shared and well known by multiple authors (Raizman, Margolin, Heskett among others). This study takes this affirmation as its starting point considering that like in many other professions design has its roots in traditional activities that evolved with time and expertise. Therefore, the evidence of its presence and the results of design are diverse and cannot be classified in a specific typology. Frankly, many authors are audacious and propose that all the elements that compose human reality are products of design. Indeed, it is common to find expressions like “Everything in human society that does not come directly from nature is designed by man” (Montana, 2004).

The interpretation of design as a common activity has attracted non-design professionals to be conscious of their practice and a trend has risen between disparate disciplines where complementary programs and courses are offered to professionals and students not related with design faculties. Clearly, multiple professions recognize design as part of their practice or include it in

their programs, as an activity that amplifies their possibilities and improve their results without being designers. Paraphrasing Andre Ricard in “Hablando de diseño” (1987): “Everybody can design but not everybody is a designer,” The validation of these observations implies recognition that the design practice is present in every human being. Certainly not in the same way that a professional of the design field, but at least a basic design ability should be an innate human trait.

As a result, new ramifications of design are now popularized and establish specializations focusing on experience, interaction, or collaboration among other aspects common in the traditional formation of designers. This is a tendency that starts at the beginning of the XXIth century thanks to the branding of “design thinking.” A term coined by the founders of IDEO, the company that became its main promoter using foundations from the notion of the Human centered design proposed by Donald Norman in the 90s. However, is worth noticing that is a denomination that appeared in the 60s, used by a small academical community focused on the science of design, very differently to what the common meaning implies today (an approach, method or even a set of tools), which aims to obtain new ventures in universities and companies through its popularization.

Whereas the intentions for this change were commercial or academical, its undeniable they reopen or ease the dialog between design and other specialties and, as result, broaden the field of designer practices in places where no one considered their participation before. The inclusion of design in interdisciplinary teams has become more frequent and popular in workplaces. As an example of this, companies promote and include designers and design practices in their structures in a deeper and more strategic way, establishing them in areas related to research, development, or innovation among others.

So, this is the origin of the context of today, where there are a wide variety of manifestations of design practice and a desire to include them in other disciplines. However, this kind of recognition is still ambiguous due to the big difference in perspective of design from non-designer professionals. Although design implies creation and a process, both aspects have a variety and disparate ways to be manifested which results in that “The concept of design seems opaque and strongly frayed at the edges” (Dieter Rams in IF design foundation,

2021). As a result, there are a certain group of difficulties in the integration of designers in working environments (examined in detail on the next section). Conditions that demand with the mentioned popularization of design, migrate from a way to integrate a small sector of professional practices to a wide variety of disciplines.

3 PROBLEM STATEMENT

As it was revised in the context, nowadays design practices are incrementally being involved in projects associated to multiple disciplines. Designers are not isolated anymore or confined to working only with their pairs. However, “the role of designers in cooperation with other departments, disciplines, sectors, hierarchies, languages and cultures is ill-defined” (IF design Foundation, 2021). This situation speaks directly to the problem at hand in this paper: **the unclear distinction of design practice from non-designers**. This lack of clarity implies strains in communication and procedures. Here, the principal effects of the problem are considered: The difficulty to understand design roles in non-design teams, the unexpected results on design teams working with non-designer’s team members, and drawbacks to implement designs ways in transdisciplinary activities.

This is not a new issue, even in the previous century designers have dealt with this problem and the challenges it implies as part of their day-to-day life. Designers that are used to working with interdisciplinary teams typically composed of marketers, managers, engineers, and other design specialists confront these situations in an empiric and craftsmanship way, based in their experience. A tactic that although effective, highly depends on the time and types of experiences of the professional, hence presenting inconsistent and unscalable solutions. Moreover, it is not a popular or common discussion in social spaces of designers like forums or conferences. This is probably caused by the supposition that as everybody designs, all of us are designers and each one experiences it in a similar way. Although this could be true for design specialties, it is not the case for non-design professionals. It should be

remembered that “design is variably a value-add, an everyday event, a working method, a byproduct, a literacy, and a complete abstraction. And frequently designers are nowhere to be found” (Burdick, 2009).

Thus, **the unclear distinction of the practice of design from non-designers** is not an explicit problem, and even when noticed is usually not regarded as a problem because design is recognized as a “mainstream” activity. A mother can regard design (as a verb) in his child craftsmanship or an engineer in his process to make an electric schematic. However, although everybody has the ability to design, “in the absence of widespread agreement about its significance and value, much confusion surrounds design practice” (Heskett, 2002). Thus, when we place designers in multi discipline environments, the different perceptions unveil the insidious implications of the unclear distinctions. This has been researched in some degree and dimension for different specialist bringing ideas like “the design ladder” from the Danish Design Council (DDC) or courses like “Design thinking” of David Kelley and his group.

This is a problem whose implications can be observed from different angles on design and other disciplines. One of the most common situations for fresh design graduates is the difficulty of explaining their roles and their functions when starting in companies or interdisciplinary groups without previous designers. On the contrary, experienced designers managed by non-designers, found themselves pigeonholed in certain tasks or functions losing opportunities to capitalize their experience or knowledge in aspects that are not evidently related to design causing conflict or frustration in the relation with the team and workload. This has changed, as designers arrive at managing positions where they open borders and achieve a certain integration. Although even there, they must adapt and deal with unexpected results on labors from different understanding of their non designers personal in charge.

The catalyst for these situations is the ambiguous recognition of design practice that collides with the different perspectives of design from non-design disciplines. Whereas the usual scenario of this problem is projects or areas. Each professional brings its own understanding and strategy to transform their resources into proposals that meet what is required. We can state that design practice can be done by everyone, so it is also present in all the disciplines.

Even though, there is a difference in the way that is manifested between professions, and this is the cause of the unclear distinction of their practice by non-designers, which negatively affects the interactions between designers and other professions.

4 SCOPE

Through the preliminary research done at the start of this study, it has been identified that the main cause of the unclear distinction of design practice from non-designers is a lack of understanding regarding what consists of design activity. Even in the design community there is not a consensus of what design is (as a verb, or how some modern authors called designing). Although a wide variety of proposals have been made, among them the most common approximation to understand design practices comes from methodology studies, another less but still popular from design ability, and one more unusual from some researchers based in the idea of design intentionality.

Considering design practice as methods is a valid way to explore the phenomenon. The specialization of industrial design has been the most enthusiastic and fruitful participant of its development since the 60's with the first conference on design methods in London (Cross, 2006). Since then, a wide variety of proposals and research has been made, some of them gather in the work of Dubberly (2005). As a result, it has been found that this way of manifestation is particular to any type of conditions. Even considering one specific field of design, each designer presents his own method which does not necessarily follow a patron of basic components.

So, it is not an ideal approach to use in order to understand the similarities with other disciplines. Moreover, these studies based on design methods are placed in the world of professional design or really close disciplines like architecture or engineering. Looking to understand particularities of the design practice in its best realization. That is why has matched well with the current vision that the design thinking branding has established, and it could be said that the vision

of the design practice from the methodology is to share professional design capacities to the other professions. As Tim Brown mention “in practice, design thinking is a set of tools that can grow old with us” (2015).

Further, we have an interpretation of design practice that comes from philosophy but is also supported in psychology, the idea of a design intentionality associated with any kind of activity or certain types of situations. This proposal was totally new for the author: “regarding the designer’s intentions and activities have not received adequate consideration by design researchers” (Burnette, 2009). A proposal that can be summarized as the awareness of performing the action of design. This is a controversial topic, as one could say that recognizing the activity transforms it and no longer is what was recognized previously.

However, it must be noted that an activity can be segregated between their minor components task, actions, and operations. What the design intentionality implies is not a specific activity, instead a type of relations and components necessary for the presence of design(ing). This goes hand in hand that design can manifest in a variety of ways in each individual but is when they have the realization of this structure is present that we can call them designers. As can be imagine this understanding of the design practice is also focused on professional designers, but it also presents cases of non-designers to highlight their differences. So, it is not the best approach to seek the common aspect in the design performed by different disciplines.

Finally, the third way mentioned to recognize design practice is through its ability. A conception that takes place in the environment of professional practice and labor roles, which is directly related to professional competencies. Thus, abilities have been well established through education and psychology studies as the use of skills through knowledge. Returning to the idea that everyone can design, we can infer that there is a common design ability. Although skills and knowledge used could differ depending on the individual with significant differences, that is suspected as the origin of the problem statement. This is a relevant aspect because at the same time could be the basis for a possible solution as comprehending the design practice shared by multiple disciplines comes from a common ability required to perform it.

These three approaches ([Fig.1](#)) are not the only ones, but they are the most frequent approximations to understand the presence of design practice. All of them are considered valid, and the preliminary literature review has found a wide spectrum of data well supported by multiple authors that are addressing the context in different ways. However, to make the research manageable to the resources of the author it is necessary select which has the high potential to explain the problem statement. This way the study will be narrow, and the framework based on a specific theory.

Starting with the first of the list, true is that everyone could have their own method through manifesting the practice of design, but the variability and individuality of this aspect makes it substantially difficult to identify the essential aspects of a shared procedure that allows the manifestation of design. This implies that the sample required to establish a consistency would be large and the data examined will be grounded to the type of product that the activity aims to produce, which in the end could be associated to other kinds of ability or disciplines. “The limitations of the theoretical frameworks that design Methodology offers for empirical research are explored in the paper by Dorst and Dijkhuis” (Dorst, 1995).

The second case has similar challenges with the intentionality, as a study of mental states the complexity of the study is beyond the expertise of the author. Moreover, it is based on fundamentals that are still in debate on their fields of origin. Probably for that reason it is the youngest developed of the three, with studies that start in the last decade of the century. Considered as an essential part of the practice of design by many authors, it is more focused as an element to define the category of a designer. As the present study is supported by the idea that design can be practiced by non-designers, it will be an argument that will not be used at its fullest and even could be contradictory.

It is the last option which presents the best alternative, considering abilities as something that is shared by all human beings, the practice of design should have strongly be based on one. Moreover, the specialization of abilities through training is a common phenomenon in professional disciplines and does not mean that a common and elemental ability is not shared anymore. The reason that its use is not perceived by professionals not related to design could be due an unconscious action that usually corresponds to cognitive processes.

Then, if we go back to the context, and independently, if this process is done by a designer or other kinds of professional, it would be reasonably narrow the subjects for the study people graduated from a tertiary education. Even if the proposal could have the potential to study other laborers or individuals in other stages of educational development. This is a way to achieve a delimitation of the study, considering the resources of the researcher.

Moreover, considering the professional graduates as the population of the study helps to share a similar perspective of formation even if they are from different disciplines. Tertiary education shares similar principles and at least a basic curriculum structure that the author has experience analyzing as a professional in curriculum development. This will be different if we study people of technical labors as its expertise could come for empirical experience or not formal programs. Meanwhile, in the case of students in other phases of formation, will not be part of the situations mentioned in the context and the problem statement.

Fig 1. The map shows the relation between the different elements considered to delimit the study from the understanding of design practice and the population selected.

5 RESEARCH QUESTION

The construction of the research question starts from analyzing the problem: **the unclear distinction of design practice from non-designers**. This situation is relevant for designers and their colleagues in collaborative environments. From the preliminary research of the author and his own experience, it is considered that is an inconvenience that is distinctly noticed by professional designers (people who had received specific training in design), which working environment is usually surrounded by a population that has received tertiary education in other disciplines. Although is not the only group that interacts with the designers is the most frequent that presents the condition.

That is why the study will focus on this population, and using this delimitation, the immediate inquiry that arises in the study seeks to understand the common element between the different disciplines that allow them to practice design. This is addressed as the design ability, and the exploration of their presence and particularities in other professionals can be answered through a research question that imply is it is potentially shared but also its evidence can be heterogenous between them. In that way, the research question is formulated as:

- *How is design ability present across design and non-design professionals?*

This research question, can be disassembled for a deep analysis as a research instrument with the follow components:

- Main inquiry: **How..... is present across**
- Variable: **design ability**
- Sample: **Design and non-designer professionals**

5.1 Sub-research questions

To help answer the main research question, three sub research questions have been selected as complements. They help structure the problem while guiding the process to develop the research. Altogether, this consolidates the answer and constraints the complexity of the variable.

The following are the list of the sub-research questions:

1. What definition of design ability could be used to bridge a common understanding between professionals?
2. How design ability can be present in design and non-design professionals?
3. Why is design ability understood differently by design and non-design professionals?

The first question serves to open the study as exploratory research; it will use the wide studies on ability made in the education and psychology fields while filtering with the design studies to make a contrast valid from different disciplines. This information will be used after extracting the sample to answer the second question, and structure the result establishing the presence of the common design ability. This will be based on the identification of the differences and similarities between the two groups. The third one uses the previous data and contrasted with each group of samples independently to explain why exist the different understanding that creates the “unclear distinction of the design practice from non-designers.”

6 SIGNIFICANCE

The importance of this document can be examined at various levels, from the more general as a contribution to the discipline of design to the most particular field as design education. Between them it can be found contributions to the

theme where the studied is placed, the capacity of perform design, passing through the relation among designers and no-designers and concentrating it in solutions to the problem that arises in their collaborative work.

As said in the introduction of this thesis, this work arises from the inquiry of what design is. It presents a study of the design phenomenon through the comprehension of the design ability, a well established topic that is still in development. Moreover, there has been an increasing interest in this kind of research. Just in the first third of the 2023, the quantity of papers related to “design ability” has been the third part of the last decade of the previous century. A proof that the design community has noted the validity to understand design in this way. As Dorst mentions, a “better insight into the cognitive behavior of designers is widely seen as a prerequisite for developing effective and efficient design support tools.” (1995)

Ignoring or underestimating the study of design ability has been an insidious cause for the stated problem and their effects on team groups. The naturality of how designers participate in the design practice many times makes them think that is something obvious and evident for other professionals. Even the thought that all concerning design ability has been researched does not sound strange, taking it for granted. However, as we see in the previous paragraph is not a case closed, on the contrary their real study just has started. That is why the research question of this study starts looking for an explication of its manifestation, and the sub research questions help to frame the research in a very particular way. This consists in a distinct perspective among the current research, as the study proposes the analysis of units of analysis not related to the typical type of the design ability studies and a framework refined based in the backgrounds and experience of the author in the educational field.

Thus, answering the research question will help to explain the subtle, but significant variations in design ability presented in professions not related to traditional design roles. It is important to study this condition in other disciplines because while doing this, our comprehension of the bases of the designer’s ability can be examined and allow us to improve them, as Siegel and Stolterman mention from their studies with other professions: “Dealing with non-designer students reveals deep insights about the nature of the design

process and makes it possible to better formulate what constitutes a designerly approach” (2008).

Besides, in a more practical way, the conclusions will help to address the problem of the unclear distinction of design practice with other disciplines and establish a common understanding affecting multiple situations in collaborative work, such as:

- Clarify the identity and importance of design roles.
- Capitalize on teamwork with non-designers.
- Promote a reflexive dialogue between multiple disciplines.

Finally, other researchers could use this document as a starting point for in-depth research on a particular group of sampling instead of the breadth over non-designer’s professionals that this study is concerned with. Their results as well as the present could be used as a base for restructuring or construction of programs that which to nurture an explicit design formation, this is already a current practice, where most of the studies on design ability are conducted by design educators aiming to improve the learning process in various disciplines.

7 OBJETIVE

Considering the previous sections, the purpose of this study aims to understand design ability. Although it takes the validity of use non-designers as main sample, to improve the comprehension of the design practice and the collaboration with other disciplines. What is considered by the author the main causes that create the gaps in collaborative teams. Thus, the objective of the study will be to identify the presence of a potential design ability shared by different disciplines practices and explain the similarities and differences between designers and non-designer professionals.

7.1 Sub-objectives

Through the process of building the answer to the research question, it will be required to achieve certain goals, that are defined as sub-objectives. They will help to support the argument and orient the process of the study. So, the following three sub-objectives has been selected and will be completed trough the research progress:

1. Identify a model of design ability ideal to establish a common understanding between professional designers and non-design professionals.
2. Describe how design ability is present in non-design professionals and professional designers.
3. Compare the understanding of design ability between design and non-design professionals using the model.

The first sub-objective is establishing a construct of the variable design ability that will be used to develop the instruments of research and analyze the results of the samplings. The main population to conduct the study will be the non-design professionals. It is expected that they present a practice of design ability, but it will not be clear unless a solid framework is applied in the sampling. In this manner, the second sub-objective will be achieved identifying similarities and differences. It is worth noting that as a study based in an activity, it is necessary to validate the theoretical model that will be used. For that reason, a reference of the design ability develops at its fullest will be contrasted. This base measure will be obtained from professional designers with work experience. Through the identification of their characteristics and comparing with the non-design professionals using the model, the third sub-objective will be accomplished which consist in determine why and how the design ability is differently understood from the populations studied.

8 RESEARCH TYPE

To define the type of research that will be realized, first it is required to align the objectives with the academic background where the study is conducted; and it is a delicate matter because depending on how design is understood, disparate classifications will be used. The first consideration is “design as a discipline,” as this research is conducted in a university program. It should be highlighted that is just a reaffirmation of their status as a group of professional formations. It needs clarification that this has no direct interpretation with Cross consideration of design relation with science.

As a second stage it is necessary to recognize the conditions of the program where this thesis will be conducted. Consequently, it is described as part of a Design department and the degree obtained will be a master’s in arts. Considering both aspects, the proposal of Christopher Frayling for research in art and design from the Royal college of art is taken as a preliminary perspective to identify the field where this research can be placed, being considered as “research into design.” This does not mean that cannot be classified by other means, but due to the condition of the program, is the most pertinent way to do it.

Then, with the classification and the place of this thesis, stated as research into design in the design discipline. The last consideration is defining the type of research, to simplify this, it will be used the recommendation of Sampieri, Bernal, and Mejia. Being the first one of the most important references of research method in Latin America for university programs in humanities or sciences. Meanwhile the other two have a similar status for the author’s country. It must be considered that a thesis is a work to be shared and collaborated on, for that reason a common classification between disciplines should be used. At the same time this helps to find the opportunity for addressing research from other fields and the implementation of existing processes or the necessity to establish new ones.

Most of the studies related to design ability are a mix of quantitative and qualitative methods, The reason for that is that the acquisition of the raw data is made through assessment instruments, but the conclusions of the results are

based on inferences and assumptions that are sustained through statistics. This is a usual way for research in humanities, and from the author experience is a standard in the education community that study abilities. However, to being able to support the results through statistics, the sample should be significant and homogeny. Both aspects are not considered as requirements for the research as is looking for amplitude and will take less than a semester to complete all the process of the study. The time of the sampling and availability of the units of analysis will not allow us to compile enough data that could be used with confidence in statistical analysis. This doesn't mean that statistics won't be used as an excellent tool to detect relations in the sample, but the results and conclusions will not rely on its finding to propose a ratio on populations, instead will be a proposal and approximation rationales from a point of view.

Another important aspect to be considered is that the research question looks to understand the variable, yearning to be studied as it is present naturally. For that reason, the sampling will not be obtained through an experiment that alters the way in which the design ability is used by the units of analysis or altering the composition that is proposed to define it. The answer obtained would be a validation of the conditions implied in the framework and a description of how is present. The objective of the sampling will be recollecting this data through interviews and observation, not direct intervention.

On the other hand, the recollection of this data will be done in a determined stage of the study and only on one occasion. Although different types of data or instruments can be applied sequentially, there will not be a register of a progress or change in the result that has been obtained. It is considered that design ability does not change significantly in a short amount of time unless is nurtured through some type of training. That is why the study considers professional non designers that do not have received some kind of capacitation in design as the main sample.

This group of the population will not be enough to understand a common state of design ability. Design practice done by non-designer should have basic roots with designers, to recognize this aspect, the use of a second group compound by professional designers will be used as a refence to be contrasted in similar conditions to the first one. As a result, is expected to show similarities and

differences between designers and non-designers that helps to describe how design ability is present across professional fields. So, the main classification to this study is descriptive comparative.

Although the vast majority of comparative studies are conducted to analyze relation between variables, it is not the case for this document, a condition called non-causal. The studies made over non-design population are limited and not conclusive, to the point that is an area that could be considered for exploratory research. Even though, there is a solid development in the study of design ability for professional, technical and student designers. Taking that as a base for the framework can be transposed to non-designers and used to confirm the descriptive study but not enough to develop a correlational study.

Then, after evaluating all the earlier aspects of this document and evaluate the better conditions for the study based on the resources available for the author and the variable design ability. The research type proposed is considered as a **qualitative non-experimental transversal descriptive comparative non-causal study**. To summarize each subclass and the reason for is consideration, a dissection will follow:

- **Qualitative:**
The study won't use statistics because the sample will be too small to make significant inferences.
- **Non-experimental:**
The variable will not be modified by the author or any experiment.
- **Transversal:**
The study will be focused on one specific time.
- **Descriptive comparative:**
The main objective is to understand the variable contrasting it in two different populations.
- **Non-causal:**
There is not a study of causa-effect associated to the variable.

8.1 Method

Considering the type of research and the objectives, the method for this research starts with literature research about the practice of design. This brought the elements to narrow the study and guide for the literature selection. After a review of this, the design ability is taking as the start for the framework research. The delimitation is based on the use of a construct with a solid structure to implement a theoretical model in the process of sampling. As a result, the instrument background will be selected and adapted to be used after a preliminary testing.

They will be used in a population chosen considering the requirements of the previous stages and the results acquired will be threshed. This information will be used to trace the bases in their design ability and identify which ones are shared with non-design disciplines. The data will be examined through a formal method selected from past successful studies and compile to elaborate a descriptive analysis that would help to identify the results and verify the hypothesis. The crystallization of this understanding will be expressed in the conclusion section. On the other hand, about the specific steps of the research method, are the following list:

- | | | | |
|------|-------------------------|------|---------------------------|
| 1. | Literature research | 3.4. | Instrument testing |
| 1.1. | Literature selection | 4. | Sample recollection |
| 1.2. | Literature review | 4.1. | Sample selection |
| 2. | Framework development | 4.2. | Instrument application |
| 2.1. | Framework research | 4.3. | Result threshing |
| 2.2. | Framework delimitation | 5. | Data analysis |
| 2.3. | Framework structuration | 5.1. | Data segmentation |
| 2.4. | Framework operation | 5.2. | Data examination |
| 3. | Instrument planning | 5.3. | Data compilation |
| 3.1. | Instrument research | 6. | Description of results |
| 3.2. | Instrument selection | 6.1. | Identification of results |
| 3.3. | Instrument elaboration | 6.2. | Hypothesis evaluation |

8.2 Timeline

The theme of this study has been chosen with some other alternatives since the author application to the program and the research project has started since the second semester in the mentoring 2 subject, complementing the literature review during design theory 2. Additionally, before the official start of this thesis, planned in the third semester, all January and the first month of February has been used in the literature research.

The progress of the study has been shared with the two assessors in a formal meeting at the end of each stage, this was useful and indispensable to refine and optimize the route of the research. That way from the official countdown of 16 weeks, a Gantt ([table 1](#)) was made to summarize the spans of time for the main stages of the research. To navigate in it, a guide of colors inside each stage will help to notice the time when the different sub-objectives start to being achieved through the research process:

	1 st Objective
	2 nd Objective
	3 rd Objective
	4 th Objective (general answer)

Table 1 Gantt chart Thesis schedule

TIMELINE																	
Month	February			March				April				May				June	
Week	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
Literature research																	
Literature selection																	

8.3 Consistency matrix

Table 2. Consistency matrix

PROBLEM	QUESTION	OBJECTIVE	HYPOTHESIS	VARIABLE	METHOD	POPULATION	OUTCOME
GENERAL PROBLEM	GENERAL QUESTION	GENERAL OBJECTIVE	GENERAL HYPOTHESIS	Design ability	Qualitative	Professional non-design professionals and professional designers	Outcome 1: Comparative description of design ability between design and non-design professionals. Their types, properties, differences, and components.
The unclear distinction of the design practice from non-design professionals.	How design ability is present across design and non-design professionals?	Describe the design ability shared with non-design professionals.	Design ability cross over professional disciplines as the use of projection skills through contextual knowledge.	The structure of the variable will be defined by a recognized model. Although the objective is not an assessment, an instrument is required to identify its presence.	The study won't use statistics because the sample will be too small to make significant inferences.	Context: Work teams assembled with professionals from multiple disciplines / majors.	Outcome 2: A description of design ability based in the presence of their indicators and testing of the model selected.
SUB-PROBLEM	SUB-QUESTIONS	SUB-OBJECTIVES	SUB-HYPOTHESIS	The first sub-objective will help to identify the specific model to use.	Non-experimental: The variable will not be modified by the author.	Type of sample: Extreme cases	Outcome 3: Recommendations to achieve a common understanding of the design practice between professionals from disparate disciplines.
Difficulty to understand design roles in non-design teams.	What definition of design ability could be used to bridge a common understanding between professionals?	Identify a construct of design ability ideal to establish a common understanding	This sub question will choose a model proposal of design ability existent and if necessary, will improve it.	To understand how the ability is shared between professions, the differences and similarities have to be described.	Transversal: The study will be focused on one specific time.	Sample1: Non-design graduated professionals from disciplines not traditionally associated with design.	Outcome 4: Instruments for the study of design ability developed for this research.
Unexpected results on design teams working with non-design professional members.	How design ability can be present in design and non-design professionals?	Describe how design ability is present in non-design professionals and professional designers.	There is common skills and knowledges used for all professionals in disparate complexity.		Descriptive: The main objective is to understand the variable.	Sample2: International design professionals with high experience.	
Teams find drawbacks in implementing designs ways in transdisciplinary activities.	Why is design ability understood differently by design and non-design professionals?	Compare the understanding of design ability between professional designers and non-design professionals using the model.	Non-design professionals use design ability unconsciously which limited the understanding of their use.		Comparative: Two different populations will be contrasted. Non-causal: There is not a relation of causa-effect between the study variables.		

During Mentoring 2, the author used his consistency/research matrix as the main tool (Table 2). Although it is a method from the human sciences, he has experience with its use through previous master's degree in education, from which this template is based. Due to experience with its usefulness in structuring research, he considers it an indispensable tool to crystalize the research plan. Moreover, this matrix has been constantly evaluated and modified since then. The current form was finalized after reviewing the framework and theoretical foundations; and it is useful to orient the process of sampling and hypothesis evaluation as a reference.

9 FRAMEWORK

The awareness of design ability in academical studies has been traced by the author at the first mid of the last century. A search in google scholar showed the first register of the term in an academical document from 1926 by the psychologist Virginia Taylor. This document was part of educational studies aiming to assess the design ability of certain children groups using the Kohs Block Design Test. These kinds of instruments were constantly used in the following studies, even on which were conducted in design faculties until the 70's. By that time, the perception that was associated to the design ability, was a component related to the function of certain types of intelligence and cognitive process, in particular to spatial-visual intelligence, what is part nowadays as the theory of multiple intelligences of Gardner proposed in 1983.

It was also from that time the studies in design ability have been growing steadily, and well-known representatives have appeared. Among them, the most associated with the term is by far Nigel Cross. His bibliography related to design ability has been one of the largest, starting at the end of the 80's producing papers and books. It's not unusual to find him frequently quoted in other design research that use his documents as base of their frameworks. It was also the entry point of this study using his book "Designerly ways of knowing." Although most of the work of Cross is based on other authors (especially Simon and Schön), his approximation to the design ability seems

to be one of the first to assemble all of what was developed from other disciplines outside design until that point. He made this to present a solid argument to declare that the design ability in professional designers is significantly different and more developed than in other humans and professions and promote the transference of this quality.

Thanks to this work there is not significant debate about the condition of design ability, but at the same time this creates the illusion that it is a matter totally understood. At least for the community that are not related with the field. However, what has been done at the end of the century has been the aperture to the doors. The key has been recognized that design ability is present in all human beings and a potential common element in professional performances that is highly developed in designers. For that reason, a good amount of the studies has migrated from focused on experts related to the design practice, to other professionals. The author found with surprise that the majority of studies of the last decade have come from other disciplines (although, close to design) as engineering and architecture.

9.1 Design: definitions

Defining design is a delicate subject for designers, as it was stated in the introduction of the document, “inherent difficulties... acknowledged to be a ‘slippery concept’ to define” (Nomen, 2014). Designers involved constantly in their practice seldom question themselves about their activities. This was also mentioned by Schön in his book “The Reflexive Practitioner” from 1983. On the other hand, in the academic literature, there is a wide variety of definitions assigned for the term. There is no one that has taken relevance over the rest, not only because each specialization of design has its own understanding that responds to their necessities and situations, but it is a definition that is in constant transformation with the change of roles and progress of the profession. So, “design has no commonly agreed definition and the word is given different meanings in different contexts” (Puigarnau, 2009).

Nevertheless, to structure the framework is necessary to establish a formal description that will be used in the study, this will be the stipulative meaning. Besides that, and as consideration of the possible use of the study for further research, it will be mentioned the ostensive, lexical, and operative definition as reference. These interpretations (with the exception of the ostensive that is made by the author) have been taken from the literature review considering their alignment between them and to the author personal approach expressed in the ostensive definition. It is important to include them although could appear that is not relevant (as design is not a variable of study in this document), because is necessary to consider that design is the main part for the construct of the design ability. Thus, the definitions are as follow:

- **Ostensive:** It was described at the introduction of this document a here presented condensed, Design is a natural phenomenon of transformation that seeks balance through a transformation where change is the catalyst and main feature to achieve organization/integration driven by a strong causality.
- **Lexical:** From the natural ambivalence of verb and noun, it will be considered a definition closest to the study and for that reason related to the action. Then design can be understood as “The art or process of deciding how something will look, work, etc.” (Oxford, 2023)
- **Operative:** For practical uses, a traditional definition from the industrial design field will be considered: “design arises in response to a certain ‘problematic situation’: when there is a desire, need or idea to construct a change in a certain environment, but the precise means and ends of this construction are not given.” (Zamenopoulos, 2009)
- **Stipulative:** The definition that will be used for the analysis conducted in the present document, is related to the idea that everybody designs, and it is present in multiple contexts. So, “design means being able to handle the everyday practicalities, and to deal successfully (or at least adequately) with difficult technical and social contexts” (Löwgren and Stolterman, 2004)

9.2 Ability: definition

The term ability has been extensively studied for multiple fields. Historically, it has been of big concern in education and psychology. Distancing from the “design situation” mentioned in the previous section, there are a solid group of definitions that are used depending on the specific theory or historical wave from where the studies are placed. Moreover, there are similar components in many of them that allow us to use a common definition between disciplines including design. From this condition, the main aspect to reflect is that skill is not the same as ability, although even in some dictionaries could be treated as synonymous, as it is in the day to day. It is not the case for the overall community that are focused on their study, where the relation of ability and skill is close but not the same and usually considers the latter as part of the former. From the same route, it can be also affirmed that “highly specialized innate abilities can be called talents” (Simonton,1999). Starting from these considerations, the follows interpretations are selected:

- **Ostensive:** the author considers this type of definition of ability as the capacity to perform certain actions with a bare minimum acceptable result and being recognized by others for that feat.
- **Lexical:** It is interesting the definition that classifies the term as a unit of value describing ability as “a level of skill or intelligence”. (Oxford, 2023)
- **Operative:** From the usual field of research “Ability is defined as the cognitive capacity to perform some mental or behavioral task. The better the performance of that task, the higher is the presumed level of ability.” (Simonton, 2003)
- **Stipulative:** this definition will be based in the wave of competencies, which the author is familiar with from his previous studies in curriculum development. It uses a typical construct, inspired in the KSA theory in education, that present competencies as “the willingness and ability to solve tasks and problems in a target-

orientated, correct, methodical and independent manner using knowledge and skills, and to assess the outcome” (Hensen and Hippach-Schneider, 2016). From that asseveration, it is considered that the definition of ability is the use of skills through a specific knowledge.

9.3 State of the art

The complexity of the design practice is easily recognized, at least apparently. However, is not easily understood as there is a wide variety of components that intervene in its manifestation. It is similar to when someone hears a song and almost instantly can recognize the melody, the sum of all the parts and hum it. But unless it is someone related to music hardly will recognize the different elements, like rhythm, harmony, chords, instruments, and other elements; that are used, and how they are used to produce the song. In the same way, a wide variety of elements are associated to the design practice, and none of them is presented isolated, including the design ability. Sadly, a study that considers all of them in equal terms will require an amount of resources that are not available for the author.

Fortunately, among all the aspects that compose the design practice, there are three majors’ components: ability, method, and intention. Each one, by itself, conduces to a comprehension of the design practice from a particular approach. This research is focused on one of them, the design ability. However, is important to recognize the existence of other elements and at least present a shallow approximation of the more related factors besides the other two major mentioned. The chart ([Table.3](#)) will be made to list and describe these components that also includes a type of person classification that has been made informally in relation to the practice of design, and used in the previous chapters, to facilitate the correlation with the other elements.

Table 3. Stipulative chart

Design terminology	Stipulative definitions
Professional designer	A person graduated from a formal design program that is part of a tertiary education. Their practice implies a plain use of design competencies.
Designer	A person with a recognized role by others which focuses on design activities. It uses the design ability maybe with design intentionality.
Non designers	A person that does not recognize his activity as a design practice. But could use design ability implicit or explicit as part of their day-to-day activities.
Design method	A group of steps that could be implicit while are followed by a designer to create a design proposal.
Design intentionality	A mental state that promotes the use of design ability on designers. It consists in a desire and a belief of a viability to change the reality as result of its intervention thanks to a medium.
Design situation	A context in a constant pressure where there is a need for a change in external reality of an individual, their problem could or not be defined but the necessity is tangible as their effects or causes.
Design problem	Extracted from design situation deconstructed in a waterfall of events. It consists in a point that works as a catalyst of causes into effects, that is selected and defined by a designer even unconsciously.
Design practice	It is the use of the design ability in a context defined as design situation, and for that reason can be performed for any individual. Also, being a basic unit, it can be embedded in any kind of activity.
Design Task	The presence of the design practice in a specific task of an activity that could be performed by any non-designer. The design ability is present in most of their actions or operations.
Design activity	A group of tasks where most of them use the design ability in an iterative process thanks to the design intentionality for a long term, usually structured by a design method.
Design ability	Based on the definitions revised in the previous sections, it is defined as the use of specific skills through knowledge to materialize a proposal to solve a design situation. It is part of all human and its use could be implicit.
Design willingness	It's the sum of values and motivations based in the design intentionality and nurtured by the culture of professionals that is part of a didactic transposition in an educational program.
Design competency	Depending on the region, different structures to define competency are well established. Based in documentation like CEFOP from Europe, it considered for this study the combination of design ability and design willingness.
Design proposal	The materialization of a final idea, product of the use of design ability, that although it may lack design intentionality (here could

	enter the concept of derived intentionality), it has a goal to achieve a certain change in the reality.
Design process	A categorization of any design activity based on the design willingness over reality. By defect all design methods are circumscribed in a type of design process.
Design intelligence	It is postulated as a particular way of reasoning that groups the design ability with other abilities, skills, and knowledge from different sources, to produce judgements applied in a design process.

The terms that are described in the chart could be well known for professional designers and even most of them can be identified by designers without formal education, but their meaning is usually implicit and there is not a clear agreement in their use. Even in the academical world, after the literature review, it was found significant distances between authors in the use of the terminology presented. So, the chart was presented to clarify the term used and also a diagram where the implications of the different terms can be shown (Fig.2). Both of them are considered tools to place the study in context. As an analogy, should be reflected that although all of us can recognize a dog and explain what it is; professionals that study living beings could share a standardized description for it. Professional designers as well, should look up cohesion in these definitions that are base to define the design practice.

Fig 2. Diagram of terminology used in the present study. Cesar Yachi, (2023)

From that perspective, the framework used to understand that design ability described as a condition that manifests its presence in specific circumstances. That although should be common in the day to day of the humans would be more specific for professionals. Which are the main population of the study as the research problem is placed in a collaborative environment. On the other hand, it can share some elements like skills or knowledge with other types of abilities, but the way in which they are related and interact between them should be particular and oriented to design. Finally, the objective and intentions that lead to the application of the ability must be clear but does not mean that are exclusive to design practice, multiples abilities are required in different activities including design. A characteristic that reaffirms the idea that design ability is present in the labor of all kinds of professionals.

10 THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS

Based in the framework the answer to the research question is delimited. Even though, some theoretical bases are required for an explicit understanding of the variable of study. This will shape an operative definition that allows its analysis and develop a hypothesis. As can be observed in the timeline section, the framework delimitation, structure, and implementation were done simultaneously with the literature review related to the design practice. The reason for this was the vast number of sources related to the topic, not only from the design discipline but for other disciplines, especially for architecture and engineering. It was considered necessary to explore the variety of perspectives presented to have a clear idea of how the problem has been addressed, the methods of research applied and the pros and cons of their results. Eventually, all the data studied helped to define the structures of this document.

So, while the scoop of the study orients the research to the area of design ability, it is worth noticing that a big section of this type of research derives in the analysis of design competencies. It was the same intention at the start of the present document because there was a high consideration to address the

problem and the research question from that point. However, while going for this path and due to the extension of that area, by the time planned for the framework development, the research had two main axes. The first one was the existence of a common design competency and the second one was about how design practice is present in other disciplines outside design. These two points, although correlational, are too wide by themselves, which implied that after being evaluated, one had to be discarded.

Concerning the first one, it would be necessary to start defining the design competencies, because there is not a consensus about them, although significant work has been done, especially in Asia. So, this would be a project that, based on the research revised and the experience of one of the assessors, could take all the time available in the schedule, and doing it is a valid research work by itself that presents a variety of examples in other disciplines on the educational field. On the other hand, it does not address the problem directly, nor the effects that were mentioned in the context. Focus on the design competencies will have a high relevance for educational purposes, but in the practice of graduated designers will not be as significant apparent. So, the idea of understanding the design ability through their crystallization as competencies, although valid and significant for a population, was discharged for the second alternative.

Thus, the second axis was chosen to keep building the structure of the theoretical bases. This is focused on how design practice is present in other disciplines, in particular professionals with a tertiary education. Nonetheless, the exhaustive literature reviewed related to the competencies have been valuable as it is considered as a reference to the structure of the design ability. It was essential to validate the idea that an ability could be shared by multiple disciplines. For example, a part or a complete ability from economy could also be part of administration. This was a step to answer how the design ability could be present in other professions but at the same time present its own challenges as that makes it difficult for design to claim ownership over a specific ability and would depend highly on the combination of cognitive aspects, behavior, and goal orientation to place it on a determinate discipline.

This description that touches topics usually related to psychology could make the impression that design ability is an equivalent of intelligence. An aspect

that Cross claims plainly in his paper “The nature and nurture of design ability” from 1990. However, his main intention when he affirms “design ability as a form of intelligence in its own” is that many of the abilities, skills and knowledge that Garner assigned to other intelligences should be grouped in one independently. He states a solid statement using the bases of the theory of multiple intelligences to affirms the existence of this type of intelligence and his demand is totally comprehensible as the components in litigation of the other intelligences are more developed in professional designers. He proposes an intelligence made by the parts of other intelligences and the evidence of its existence. Sadly, at the end of his argument he recognizes the limited research on certain areas to support the argument and concludes the case as “not proven”. For that reason, kept using the term design ability.

Today, after 33 years of the publication of that dissertation (Although his book “*Designerly ways of knowing*” from 2006, have the paper pasted with minimum adjustments to be used in a book) the labors of researchers have been intensive and nowadays the reality of the design intelligence could be proven. We can reexamine briefly the three main aspects that were considered insufficient developed from the perspective of Cross: A core operation, developmental history, and support from experimental psychological tasks. The first one required the development of AI enough to develop proposals (without concerning the quality) through the insertions of prompts, which we already achieved. The second one asked for evidence of a progressive change in the individuals that perform activities related to design. This has been vastly covered by studies in the field of design education. Finally, abilities that can be applied in multiple types of contexts, not only in design. This has been an objective of the studies on design thinking previous the “unintentional” appropriation of the term by “IDEO” and his successful incursion on multiple fields not related to the traditional fields of design as well as his popularity of its courses among professionals from different disciplines.

So, this is another affirmation that could be extracted from the research; there is clear enough proof to affirm the existence of design intelligence. However, this is not synonymous with design ability. After the introduction of the theory of multiple intelligences in the 80’s, where the differences between ability and intelligence were blur, today not only physiology, education and other disciplines related to neurosciences, had established a clearer division (although

not standardized). From the research conducted by the author in this thesis as well for his previous one and his studies on a master in education he presents an operative definition of design intelligence and the other types, as a sum of multiple domains that allows the creation of judgements that trigger specific behaviors on specific context, therefore intelligence and ability should not be treated as synonyms.

Returning to the definition, the domains refer directly to the Bloom taxonomy, a popular and traditional theory in education which consists of a learning objectives classification in three main categories: cognitive, psychomotor, and affective. It is of particular interest that these learning objectives are usually interpreted as a classification of abilities when used in instructional design and psychological process. It is important to highlight that the three categories are not the same as the most popular subclassification of the cognitive category, part of the taxonomy and usually implemented in educational training. For the present document the relevant aspect is the main categories as the design ability should be classified in one of them. To determine where is placed a short analysis will be conducted in each type.

Starting with the affective domain, which was the least developed by Bloom and his colleagues, we can relate it with factors where emotions and motivations play the main role. These components are the essential part of the studies focused on design intentionality (that explore the desires and beliefs that participate in the design practice) but also when mature they transform on willingness. If the notion of design ability is at least partially studied with this background, will be inevitably immersed in the field of competences. As was mentioned, although valid, design competency is a field wider than the research scope and not immediately related to the problem selected. Design ability cannot be studied properly when transformed on a superior stage as a competence because it presents its own challenges of study. So, it can be concluded that design ability is not part of this domain.

The second group can be considered the psychomotor domain, their main feature is the conscious use of some part of the body to a certain degree of efficacy to achieve a goal. This category apparently has the highest possibility of embracing design ability because historically it has been related to actions that present a high skill over physical tools. Drawing is the most common

between them and it requires at least complex hand control. Based on this crucial observation, there has been a wide group of studies that base their analysis on the statement that design ability is evident in professionals that use certain tools. Amongst them, there is not unusual imply sketching as essential part of design, “The use of sketches is clearly an important part of the natural processes of designing” (Cross, 2006)

However, thanks to the ramification of the discipline and the changes in the professional roles, today we can affirm that instruments are not homogeneous between the different cases of the design practice, including the use of a pen on a stage of their process. For instance, we could consider that an industrial designer poses design ability while we observe him doing a tridimensional modeling, we cannot be sure where the ability is specifically present or at what part of the procedure correspond its use, but we can be sure that in some point the design ability is manifested. The same case happens in a graphic designer that makes some posters on a computer or a textile designer that makes some fabric proposals with acrylic paint. So, if we keep exploring professional designers’ activities, we will find out that even in the same specializations from the same program, the type of tools that are used vastly differs and the lack of skill with a tool, does not imply the absence of the design ability. It is proposed that there is a design ability, common for anyone that with time evolves and conducts the development of other abilities (which starts as skills) on certain tools, that reflect the expertise of the designers. Consequently, when we talk about design ability, should not be defined based on the use of an instrument and although it highly supported by members of this category (like other abilities and skills), must not be considered as part of the psychomotor domain.

This last affirmation could seem not relevant or obvious at first glance but hides one of the main realizations of the author, because as a conclusion we could declare for example, that design ability does not imply drawing. This would mean that try to understand a common design ability as its most basic composition with actions that implies sketching could conduct to spurious results or misconceptions. This affirmation will be controversial as almost all the studies oriented to understand design ability are based or/and highly supported by the implications of the actions associated with the drawing skill. But nowadays, the author considers that is clear for any professional designer with some years of active practice that design did not imply an activity where

one had to draw forcibly. The reason to mention these observations is to clarify as reductive reasoning, the motives to consider the design ability, in its most pure and basic form (shared by multiple professionals), is classified in the cognitive category. This does not mean that could not be reinforced by elements that are part of the other two categories. Moreover, when developed, its borders of competence are diffuse and makes attractive, to sustain that is part of the three. Further research is needed but there are some clues that could help to achieve this clarification, as some professional designer besides an expertise over certain tools (to study the psychomotor domain), also develops (for example in the affective domain) a capacity of empathy with their clients or users. Determining if this is part of a specific design competency or a superior ability in design would be a great contribution to the field of this study.

Returning to the matters of this thesis, the design ability shared by the people is considered inside the cognitive classification from the Bloom theory, implies as main characteristic that all the stream of this ability can take place on the mind. Obviously, having the support of external inputs/outputs can exponentially increase the effectiveness of this ability and transform it. Conversely, being fundamentally psychological implies a group of requirements that vary depending on the theoretical approximation in the field of cognitive science, even in the educative discipline (remember that the taxonomy is highly used by this type of professionals). Between them, the most basic considerations associated with domains mention a sequence of events oriented by a type of intention that shapes a process, a type of cognitive process (Anderson and Krathwohl, 2001). This does not denote a fixed or explicit method but recognizes its condition as a congruent connection of different components that were defined in the background as skills and knowledge.

A short pause of the analysis of the main route “design ability as a cognitive process” will be taken here and resumed in the next section. From here on there is a mayor bifurcation that is worth understanding, because it will help to frame the operability of the variable. It can be affirmed that thanks to recognize design ability as a cognitive process, the idea of design intentionality takes more substance indirectly. The reason is that usually there is an “intention” which triggers the activity, it has been regarded as the point to define a state of mind while designing. Based on that, some studies opened the possibility of design intentionality. This approach was described previously in the scope of

the study as another way to understand the design practice, usually taken by philosophers and psychologist. There is an increasing number of studies about it, but as a topic with few decades of research, there are many challenges to clarify in this area. The main of them considered by the author is related of the evidence of unconscious design, to be more precise the design that is made in the day to day of common individuals that are not called designers but are involved in a practice of design.

As an example, when someone chooses their clothes for a date, there is indubitably the presence of a certain design ability. Still, most people would not realize that unless is mentioned, so theoretically it cannot be present a proper intention of design, as the awareness of what one is doing, it is a mandatory condition of any intentionality. Moreover, if it is considered that an ability must be associated with its specific intentionality, as some proposals mention, then in the case of activities that consider the use of multiple abilities, will have to present a cluster of intentions each one autonomous as working with each ability, even in simultaneous use. This seems hardly possible and less practical than the natural process of the mind that had been observed. Some authors solve this situation presenting the idea that cognitive process can function whit a sort of a derived intentionality (Searle, 1983) which also applies for the case of design (Zamenopoulos, 2009).

The review of the work from multiple authors, showed it a common patron in the proposal for the intentionality where the design ability is manifested. This considers situations where a cognitive process is based in an intentional state that seeks to transform a reality to comply conditions of desire. The critical difference between one design intention and another kind would be that the former is part of a designer consciousness and will be present in reflexive circumstances, always in evaluation and transformation being part of constant iterations. This will not conflict with the theory of unconscious cognition abilities, as a derived intentionality can work pretty much as “background” intentionality with low to no apparent impact in the manifestation of the ability. Hence, that would be the postulation used in this study to complement or refine the cognitive process and will not be further explored on the intentionality field as is wide as design ability and the current approximation is enough to proceed with the research. It will be considered that design practice manifests with a

general intentionality, which helps us to identify the different situations where there is a high potential use of the design ability.

10.1 Design ability

Returning to the analysis of the main part, design ability as a cognitive process is not a novel proposal, moreover it could be considered as a usual paradigm. Some examples of it are presented in studies that describe design ability with terms like; decision making, creative predisposition, problem solving, strategic orientation, abductive reasoning, natural judgement, mental capacity, human condition, artificial phenomenon, or even a composition sense. However, few of these cases explore the consequences of being categorized as a type of cognitive process. This kind of classification is typically overseen in most definitions that fit on it, but this was not the case in this study. The previous section focused on their implications and presented a context that could be treat as a value condition to be associated that allows to construct a more detailed description of the design ability: A cognitive process that uses skills through knowledge to materialize a **design proposal** required **to change a reality** in a **design situation**.

This definition uses multiple expressions that were briefly revised in the “state of the art” subchapter, but their relationship with the current theoretical bases will be supported and expanded. In the first place, the term design proposal is used considering that any use of the design ability will create something, physical or virtual, as result of the effort and the application of a skill. This product is the conclusion to bring the idea to reality and it is an essential condition to complete the use of the design ability. It must be highlighted that this does not refer to a method of design, or even the activity of design. When a product is mentioned, it indicates the minimum materialization of an idea to the external world. It could be the oral description of a building (as the material is the sounds that travel in space) or could be written the list of guesses for a wedding (where the product will be a piece of paper with the names in it).

Even if the best designer in the world starts his practice of design, if he does not express this idea in the external world, he cannot finish it. This is the main difference between design and imagine, although is not about the necessity of the existence of something, its communication, or evaluate its viability. The reason is simpler, it must be considered that whatever is designed is based in the external world even if is something fantastical like a dragon, a poem, or a new ice cream flavor. Eventually, the design had to be used in a certain way, because it was designed for some reason, and at that time, would be necessary to be placed in reality. That means using the elements of the reality to constitute a representation of the idea. When the designer lands their design, the change of the materials of his inner world to the outer world would cause a minor or mayor strain that will produce at least some minimum changes that will be adjusted by his design ability. Only after this migration has been done the cognitive process will be finished.

The second one, is the expression that synthesizes the approximation to the intentionality in the previous section, “to change a reality” is the natural condition that ignites the design practice. This means that the design ability is driven to produce a transformation, but not positive or negative as this will be subjective to perspectives from the different stakeholders related to what is designed. Instead, it denotes that an effect can be expected in the designer surroundings thanks to his actions. This could be on other people or the environment being infimal or significant, and not about the representation of the idea (as draft or a final commercial product), instead, is related to the result of the design proposal. That is the reason why on frontward the latter will can be called a “medium” because is the way to achieve the desired change. So, associated to the previous paragraph the design ability is a “**way to materialize a medium**”.

Finally, it is mentioned a “design situation” as the type of context where the ability is performed, the conditions associated for the manifestation of design practice. Multiple authors have reviewed the topic and it was very common by the end of the last century to associate design ability with the existence of problems and its way to create solutions. As Libby Osgood and Clifton Johnston describe it “as an ability to define the problem, evaluate alternatives, and communicate the design” (2014). This was particularly relevant in the field of the design thinking since its beginning in the 60’s, to the point that was

common to consider that where there is a problem there was a potential to design.

Furthermore, there have been two main approximations that born for this perspective. One group consider that designers specialize in define problems to engage its workspace in a manageable situation, and others consider that designers deal with “wicked” problems that are untamed and in a big part (if not all) of their design process must deal with a “situational ambiguity”. Both affirmations are valid as in part of the background research the author looked for clarification and got in contact with many designers from different specialties to ask about their personal experiences regarding problem identification, the result was that most of the sample aligns with the second group but there is also a significand sector that aligns with the first one. Supplementary research had to be done if one of the two groups wants to be discarded, as the size of the sample was not statistically significant, and the work that supports both cases is limited by qualitative studies of very few subjects.

For that reason, the presence of defined problems is not a requirement to manifest the design practice and cannot be considered mandatory. However, the existence of an unexplicit problem is still required, although recognized it could be a complex task that could complicate the practical use of the concept of “design situation” in the operative definition of the design ability. So, it is easier to consider, to validate the context with their existence, the use of one main symptom of problems: the necessity. It means that a condition for design ability should include detecting a necessity on the reality, a change required but also wished and can be developed in a more synergic way using the interpretation of “**desire a change in a situation**”.

After checking these components, the attention can return to the cognitive process, that from the background section implies the use and sequence of disparate skills through a body of knowledge. Some studies are specifically related to the knowledge used in design; the validity of the proposals will depend on the type of skis implied. Thus, when the research arrived at this point, a compilation of all the skill registered in the multiple practices of design was conducted, fortunately a short time started, a patron appeared. Three main groups where the skills used in design practice were observed. The first one

related to the use of tools to make “representation of the ideas”. A second group related to the way they perceive the “need for a change” of their realities. And finally, a third group that is based in the processing of information to project an answer to their problems as a “design proposal”.

As can be noticed, these three groups are directly associated with the paragraphs at the start of the section, although their identification were a coincidence result of the “organic” synergy of the research. Moreover, when the author noticed this, he searched hoping there was some study related to at least one of the classifications. He was gladly surprised that the classification found was a common conclusion arrived for many other authors that had been studied with different terminologies since many decades ago. Furthermore, the classification was part of a model of cognitive process that has been used while in constant evolution to understand the design practices and in some cases more specifically the design ability. Between the denominations used to call the variety of proposals to model the theory, the author chose to refer to his own version as a “**creative reasoning**”. This term is a mix of the different terminology used historically to call this type of **cognitive process** and model in constant evolution that best suits the conclusions that has been developed for the present study.

So, integrating all the previous aspects of revised in this section, a construct of design ability can be built to work as a study variable. It will avoid the use of the term design multiple times to not generate confusions: “**Design ability as a creative reasoning way to materialize a medium to achieve a desired change in a situation**”. The following subchapters will focus on explaining in detail the main component of this statement, the creative reasoning, and the model of cognitive process developed from it. After that the next chapter will concentrate on exploring the main elements of the research construct to proceed to operate the variable.

10.2 Creative reasoning antecedents

The creative reasoning presented in this thesis is a theoretical model of cognitive process that uses a sequence of disparate skills through a body of knowledge, based in the background and the construct developed for design ability. The reason to call it creative reasoning, started in one of the literature selections that the author finds more related to the research question of this thesis, called “Scientific discovery and creative reasoning” from Herbert Simon and Peter Cheng, a document which is also used two years later in the book “The creative cognition approach” (Finke et al, 1995).

In that research the use of diagrams is presented as a potential design ability to complement the other abilities necessary to solve mathematical theorems inferred from the physical field. Simon is the precursor of the ideas that design is present in other activities as the base of a problem-solving activity and for that reason not related to what traditionally is consider design, to the point that propose be studied as a field by itself calling it “the science of the artificial”, his most important book related to that published in 1969.

On the other hand, as a coincidence the term is also used to present a description that is close, bridging distances, to the construct that has been developed; “Design is the process by which we devise courses of action aimed at changing existing situations into preferred ones through the creation of artifacts – objects created by humans through creative reasoning.” (Simon in Graham M. Winch et al, 2023). It has to be considered that Simon was not any close to the circle of design, so the polysemic use of the word is strong in him. So, at least it can infer that what he means as design was design practice, and from the study of his work can be understood as basis for the primal idea of design ability.

In that way, what is called in this study as “creative reasoning”. It is an approach that has been developed by multiple researchers to understand the way in which design practice is performed in the mind. It dates from the theory of visual thinking associated with Robert McKim. Although previously studied by other authors (as Rudolf Arnheim), was McKim book “*Experiences in visual thinking*” from 1972, that was used as the source for most of the latter

studies. In his work the idea of visual thinking was proposed as a complex phenomenon that transcends the limits of the cognition directly related to the visual perception. Presented in all human beings, it has different levels of development, and manifest in multiple situations.

“Visual thinking is constantly used by everybody. It directs figures on a chess board and designs global politics on the geographical map. Two dexterous moving men steering a piano along a winding staircase think visually in an intricate sequence of lifting, shifting, and turning... An inventive housewife transforms an uninviting living room into a room for living by judiciously placing lamps and rearranging couches and chairs.” (Arnheim, 1965)

In plain sight, visual thinking can be considered as part of design, an ability that is used in its practice. But it was the theory of McKim for its structure and the way how works that make him the reference of the theme. He proposes a model of a partial cognitive process (Fig.3) composed of three actions: seeing, imagining, and drawing. Each one of them is presented in an area of a Venn diagram, where each intersection represents a variety of interactions. The flow of the process can present any direction, it could take place multiple times and it is not mandatory that the three actions take place in some iterations. This model in his time was particularly useful to understand the practice of architects, artists, and designers; but it was also considered that any person can perform it as part of a natural ability.

Fig 3. Visual thinking model (McKim, 1972)

Another important aspect of the model is that it is not framed in a complete activity, like the studies of the design field from the same time on design thinking, that try to understand the design practice focusing on the methods used by the experts. The visual thinking, on the other hand, was thought to be considered as the minimal expression of actions or operations that imply building ideas in the mind to solve problems. McKim base his approach counting that this construction will be visual, comparable to when someone dreams or what we can make physically with a pen. So, “imagining” takes an essential part of the process. However, imagination has to be fed by the experiences of the outer world, and that is where “seeing” springs into action, not only with the environment but also with the manifestation of what is imaged embodied in drawings.

As can be inferred the relation of design thinking and visual thinking in their beginning was at best distant, although both fields had their formal research in the 60’s. It is clear is that they were never considered synonymous and their interest, researchers and disciplines involved were not the same. Roughly, visual thinking was focus on a cognitive process, design thinking was concentrated in methodology, and while design thinking keeps his term until being appropriated for commercial uses, losing scientific support and credibility to the point to be called “a useful myth” (Norman, 2010), the visual thinking approach keep evolving and transforming securing a solid field of research, which this study is part today.

From this development, others refined their own models. One of the first significant contributions considered was made by Ward, Smith, and Finke in 1992 (Fig.4). Their proposal is usually referred to as a creative cognition model due the reframe of the field in psychology and presented with the name of “Geneplore” as a mix of the two main words that describe their understanding of the visual thinking: **generate** and **explore** ideas. This approximation is considered important because places the phenomenon that McKim presented, as an analysis of a cognitive process. This is possible because the model disassembles the action to “drawing”, to the “think” while drawing, in a way very similar to what Schön called the reflection **in** practice. So, the action of “drawing” is regarded as skill that is engaged to the cognitive process of idea

creation but not an essential part of it as could be replaced by other types of means.

It is worth noting that although the flow of the process is still multidirectional, the components are separated, which clarifies the type of interactions that can be manifested. It changed the type of components involved, from the original actions to categories of elements. “Imagining” is replaced by “generation of pre-inventive structures” and consider that imagination is not the only factor that intervenes in the elaboration of an idea (what is called pre-inventive). Their mature until are ready to be used in the “pre-inventive exploration and interpretation” what was previously called “drawing”. This was examined in the previous paragraph, concluding that the refinement of the idea could be achieved in different kinds of ways, where the psychomotor domain has a secondary role. Finally, the third element, “seeing” is alike to the new denomination “product constraints” as it is composed by the inputs of the context. However, it does not consider that could be fed back by the other elements, as the original component. It works in a way similar to making a painting where the reference is not altered by our actions or perceptions.

Fig 4. Creative cognition model, “Geneplore” (Ward, Smith, and Finke, 1992)

The Geneplore model aimed to understand the creative process that produces ideas, not as delusions but as rational proposals. That is the reason why they

use the term “pre-inventive” on the different components, they consider that is necessary to begin from the generation of that kind of structures and after is explored and interpreted, it could return to a new cycle but now as a “concept”. Meanwhile, the conditions that are presented in the context are constantly narrowing the viability of the development operating as “constraints”. This is an analogy of what is manifested in the design practice, and an improvement over the perception of the previous model that was strongly attached to the visual. It allows us to analyze activities made by non-designers with high potential of present design ability.

With the popularization of the creative cognition model and their use in diverse research, especially in psychology, it could be considered how the studies in the field close of the last century. The perspective that the creation process is not pigeonhole in the visual aspects was a giant leap for the future understanding of design abilities, this change of paradigm was so important for the author that decided to use part of it to name his model proposal, the **creative** reasoning. However, it does not mean that the topic was resolved, and the work done. The research gained a new impulse and even became significantly more active, thanks to the entry of the design community in the field with new proposals and clear goals, adjusted specifically for the study of design ability. One of the first approximations in the new millennium was presented by John Gero and Udo Kannengiesser in 2004.

Their proposal was not based directly on the interpretation of the previous models, but they arrive at similar conclusions thanks to the analysis of the design protocol analysis applied to architects presented by Schön in “The reflective practitioner”. Through a thorough analysis of the design practice presented there, they create a framework that was crystallized in a proposal of two models of what they call situated designing (Fig.5). The model for general cases particularly caught the attention not only for its similarity with the previously models revised but for the way they arrived at their proposal. In the case of the author, he has to do a very exhaustive research of design ontology and educational theory about ability. Instead, Gero and Kannengiesser arrived at a similar conclusion “through” empirical observation.

Their model presents the traditional three areas that also work as categories taking distance as the previous model, also consider the relations between these

areas as the visual thinking model with specific denominations as: interpretation, focusing and action. It also considers that the flow could happen from any direction, but all the elements are mandatory in the iterations. These main elements are called worlds and include a variety of components similar to the creative cognition model. The first one is called “external world” and their equivalents are the “product constraint” and the “seeing” sets. The second one is the “expected world” and are equals with the “generation of pre-inventive structures” and the “imagining” sets. Finally, the last one is the “interpreted word” which equivalents are the “drawing” and “pre-inventive exploration and interpretation”.

Fig 5. General situated design model, (Gero and Kannengiesser, 2004)

Besides this work, John Gero participated actively with a wide group of researchers that are highly related to the concept of visual reasoning, a “process consisting of figural perception and non-figural conceptualization” (Hsien-Hui Tang, 2001). A wide variety of studies in design ability in the last decade, part from this approach and propose their own structures, they conduct extensive and valued research with different types of populations. Although most of them do not create a diagram that could serve as a model reference for their proposals. One exception is Yong Se Kim and Jung Ae Park who presented their visual reasoning model in 2007 ([Fig.6 right](#)). His work was strongly based on McKim model, but they also narrow the original approximation as “an

underlying cognitive process in design... a design reasoning model” (Kim and Park 2009)

Other differences with the original proposal are the division of the groups as the creative cognition, the integration of sub-actions specifics for each set, the integration of a complex net of relations with a free direction flow associated to the sub actions, and a frame of the cognitive process in a scheme and a ring of knowledge. This modification makes the model very detailed to analyze and easier to apply in quantitative studies. Nevertheless, as the “situated designing model”, it lacks the progress of the background developed after the original model. That is the reason why they are fixed with the original actions of the visual thinking model. It was not the case with other recent studies without a diagram as the proposal of Hsien-hui Tang or Yvonne Outterside.

In the case of Tang, his structure is more complete than the rest, as include the idea of types of knowledge that connect the sets, which keep fixed by the visual representation, changing “sketching” instead of “drawing”. Although it recognizes that “seeing” is not the only input possible and call to that area “perception”, and “imagining” is recognized as a very limited denomination and is replaced as “functional reference”. On the contrary, Outterside consider the sets as fixed actions and keeps the imagining denomination, makes the similar change in “seeing” but as verb, calling it “perceiving”, and change “drawing” by “modelling” considering that make graphics is not the only way to represent the ideas. This is totally associated that his work taking place with children, and she could observe their behavior with other means like clay. These approximations have affinities with what has been built in the previous sections, and although the lack of models in the last two, their proposals are useful to refine the cognitive process model used for the present study, that is the reason to use part of its name in the construct. “The creative **reasoning** model” will be revised and contrasted with the previous ones in the next section.

Fig 6. Equivalence with colors of cognitive models that support the creative reasoning including the visual reasoning model from Yong Se Kim and Jung Ae Park.

10.3 Creative reasoning model

After understanding the origin of the term “creative reasoning”, it is easier to relate it as a proposal of a cognitive process used in the manifestation of the design activity, multiple studies have verified the presence of the reasoning models in designers. Moreover, McKim principles, that are the base of the present proposal, state that it is manifested in non-designers and Outterside validated in children, but not in a proper design task. Thus, although there is a possibility that it is not exclusive to the design practice, it is clear that should be considered as the cornerstone for design ability. The reason for this affirmation is their essential function to generate design proposals, that has been studied for years in the practice of professional designers.

The reason why the author requires to present his own proposal although the wide number of studies and recognized models from other authors is because the objective and conditions that the present study poses, are significantly different than their predecessors. The majority of explorations conducted in the field of design ability raise and aim to educational purposes. The study of the variable is oriented to establish ways to assess its development and through it, trace a route to improve their programs, courses, or procedures. For that reason, most of them are quantitative studies, which conclusion are narrow to specific academical contexts.

That is also why their main analysis units are designers (not necessarily professionals) or students that receive some kind of education in design. Analyzing design ability from designers and above all from professional designers is like trying to isolate and element from a compound abundant in the element and with a very strong bond. Instead, doing it from non-designers is like a compound that is scarce in the element but with a weak bond. The type of instrument required for each case will be different and is the same for this study that is focused on a population that has not been studied.

There are a few exceptions, but they come from other disciplines, and they manage a different agenda: like Outterside and his work with children or Simon with his study with scientists. Neither of them has “design ability” as their main interest or see the presence of the cognitive process as a plain design manifestation without going deeper than what is necessary to support its relationship with what is their own variables of study. This is totally comprehensible and not a demerit, but that is the reason why a more pertinent tool is required to be used in the present study. However, it will use similar bases than the other authors and will be called the “creative reasoning model” (Fig.7).

The model is composed of categories, of which the main components are skills, divided into three kinds as; perceive, project, and represent. They are categories because disciplines and specializations use different means to achieve what implies the name of each group. Nevertheless, some qualities, talents, skills, and others, are shared by professionals and what makes evidence of their difference in the process is how they understand, develop, or experience them. So, the model proposes the link between these groups of elements based on a specific type of knowledge that is acquired by the previous one. Thus, the idea that ability as a composition of skills and knowledge based on the educational theories of e competency mentioned in the framework is paved on the frame of the creative reasoning model.

In that sense, was also found a classification of three types of design knowledge that works synergically with what has been researched. It was developed by Kolaric, Beck and Stolterman (2020) and called “hierarchical levels of design knowledge”. Each type will be revised with the area of the model that is mainly responsible for their construction. It has to be mentioned

that although is referred to as design knowledge, it is not that is exclusive or born from design. Knowledge for the present study is a way to understand data through a process of assimilation. What Stolterman et al. propose is classify the way how knowledge is integrated through the design practice. That is the reason why even without planning, it fits perfectly in all the cognitive models that have been revised in all this chapter.

Fig 7. The creative reasoning model, Cesar Yachi (2023)
The colors used are equivalent to the previous models.

The first one is the group that aim to “Perceive”, it is the start of the model flow, as “one cannot dream what has not seen”, if you saw a face, maybe you can imagine a new face in your dreams but for example if you never saw or hear about a bicycle and their components it will not be possible to image one immediately, as the randomness to integrate and associate all the elements will be very small. What is known through perception, turns to be the base where all the creativity and ideas start to take shape and that is called in the hierarchy as contextual knowledge.

That is why perception is the initial spark for the process, but is not established as the visual boundary, there is enough evidence that one can identify the necessity of change in a reality from others, when a designer hears a client but does not see the cases on firsthand. Sure, eventually the iteration of the ability

model will return to “perceive” and the visual dimensions will take more relevance. For example, after hearing a client and starting to do a sketch, in that moment, it will require other skills from this group some of them common to any person like the “vergence” or the “spatial vision” while other more specific to a profession like the way in which a prototype is observed or where to focus the attention on a composition. This skill will produce thoughts that are classified as context knowledge as are related to the reality perceived.

The second group “Project” contains all the skills (and other components) that help to create and nurture an idea from its seed. That means, is the category where the thoughts about a proposal are developed and grow, an idea does not born concluded, on the contrary initially is diffuse and ambiguous. Here is where imagination and creativity take the stage filling the blanks. Its components work very similar to what McKim as well as other authors called the “eye of the mind” what in accordance builds what we call a “mental image”. Consider for example that before thinking in a proposal, when the designer listens to his clients, he creates the scenario in his head.

However, it also has a very rational side as the inductive and deductive reasoning is part of what produces these ideas and is called by Stolterman et al. as development knowledge because is still in construction and about what is constructed. As an incubator for a human this category is not adequate to retain an idea indefinitely, it must be free and live in the world to mature as a proposal. That does not mean that will not return to this category to be refined, is important to consider this category as the “airport”. Where the ideas depart to the exterior (passing through the other two categories) and will also land, trying to match what is it his depiction in the reality with what is in the mind. When the idea matches reality then a proposal has been made.

That brings the case of the final third group, which aims is to “Represent”, and it is composed by anything that helps to contemplate an idea that can be considered complete at least temporally. It is the way in which a reference of the idea is obtained, and usually how is manifested in the reality. As has been stated, is in the second group that the idea born and takes form, it is evaluated, modified, contrasted and many other conditions could take place; and when there is a final decision, and all the consideration has been settled, it is necessary to consolidate everything in a unity and where the components of

this category take place. This is excellent expressed in Spanish as “pasar en limpio” which approximations of the idiom in English could be as; make a “fair copy” of the thoughts. This has an intimate relation with the name of the group “represent” as “present again”.

This means that the third category thinks again of the idea not as an exploration but as an affirmation, it does not modify it, it is used as a guide to proceed to replicate it. This procedure was frequently studied from the case of drawing because usually, the representation implies their materialization in the reality, but not in a particular level of detail or quality, it could be a draft in a napkin or an oral description. “Many design theorists not only considered design expertise resides in designers’ visual representations... the “language of designing” is consisted of the tightly connected verbal and non-verbal elements.” (Jiang and Yen., 2009). So, as has been mentioned before, drawing or any kind of physical representation is not essential of this group, instead it is the “reasoning” used to achieved them. That is the reason to call it “representation” and not “materialization” the latter involves a mandatory work in the reality while the term chosen is their potential.

The transference of ideas outside the mind helps to recognize the implications and the viability of the proposal. Taking it to the reality is like giving it life taking its own identity and establishing a dialog that was well studied by Schön as the “reflexive conversation” (1983). It is for work with these ideas that also two different kinds of knowledge are acquired, the most important one is a latent knowledge that is placed in the representation, waiting to being perceived. So, it is transmitted to the first category where is interpreted and returned to the projection as a knowledge that will be compared and evaluated the original idea that was used to build the representation. In that way new modification will be made to the “mental image” and new procedures will take place from the “represent” category.

It is the last case, that corresponds to what is present in the model proposed with the more comprehensible term “contrasted knowledge” because this will always be used to contrast the reality. It must be noticed that although it could seem that after obtaining this knowledge the idea is finished, this is not the case. As is just the end of a cycle that could last permanently in a constant iteration. One could think about it in the develop of one sketch that is in

constant modification from the first mark to the last point, until arrive to the final shape, the creative reasoning model is existing in constant iteration while one draft is made and not finished. Each time that a new line is done, there is a new cycle of perception, projection, and representation.

About the second type of knowledge acquired thought “representing” category, is not related to the “idea” itself, instead about what is used to materialize the proposal. From the materials to the technics and the methods or the way to design. The hierarchy from Stolterman et al. takes more relevance to this type (although it also consider the previous one, but as in minor impact) and that is why is called “high knowledge” in the hierarchy, composed basically of thoughts that is acquired while doing the representation and the conclusions that could be obtained from the multiple practices of design (like principles, theories, even styles), as of specific skills that one acquires through experience after making the materialization like a draft or a mockup.

10.4 Model placed in context

The diagram proposed to represent the model of creative reasoning is located in a context where the design practice takes place, when that condition is fulfilled the design ability is identified and analyzed. It must be considered that the design ability is not the only element that intervenes in the design practice, and it is not a process that corresponds to the whole activity. This is an essential concept necessary to proceed with the idea that design ability is present in the professional practice of non-designers. If the design ability would be required in the total intervention of the performers. In principle it will be easily recognized that they are designing, and a clear understanding of the practice will not be a problem as it has been verified. And as second place but overall, if the design ability were all the activity (as iterations or one cycle), even considering the theory of sub-conscious process, it would restrain (or even block) the resources necessary for other cognitive processes necessary for any complex labor that are also need it in design professional practice.

Based on that, it is necessary to postulate that one cycle in the present model is enough to manifest the design ability. Moreover, the model is the minimum unit of a design practice, composed by their operations. Meanwhile the iteration of the cycle is equivalent as actions. For that reason, there is a high possibility that the activities of non-designers possess some kind of design task inside them. This classification of activity/task/action/operation (Fig.8) is wrongly credited to Donald Norman because it takes popularity by him, like the case of IDEO and the design thinking. In this case the theory is usually called “Hierarchical Task Analysis” or “activity centered design” in the UX field. Actually, it comes from the contributions to “the activity theory” made by Victor Gonzales (2006) and Bedney/Harris (2008). Which bases, “the first generation”, were established almost a century ago by Vygotsky and Leontiev. Nowadays the “third generation”, was developed by Yrjö Engeström. He boosted its adoption in the education, management, and engineering disciplines and at the end of the millennium with the user experience field in the last decade.

Fig 8. Examples of diagrams based on Bedney, Harris and Gonzales approach of the activity theory:

Right. – Decomposition without hierarchy from Albert Snow, 2015

Left. - Relation with autonomous tools in hierarchy. Used by Cesar Yachi in 2012 for his thesis in 2014. (Anonymous, N.D.)

Based in this hierarchy, the design activity could be disassembled into tasks which some of them have actions or operations that rely on the use of the design ability. To present that condition, the context where the action takes place has to be in a way that was deeply explored at the start of this chapter and called a “design situation”. To refresh the meaning, essentially consist in the necessity to transform certain aspect of the reality and when that condition is existent, then some of the actions or operations are immersed in what can be called a “design task”. In that way the design ability perches on the levels of the activity hierarchy, and a complete round of the creative reasoning model happens in an operation, this correspond to certain action where multiples cycles could be manifested by the repetition of the same operation or the inclusion of other types.

So, it can be inferred that the design ability is not the only type of ability that is present during the accomplishment of a design task and different types of cognitive process can occur. It is proposed that the continuous use of the design ability for a long period of time (as it requires attention) is fueled by the design intentionality. Theoretically that is what differentiates a designer from a non-designer and what can be considered a proper design activity. Moreover, it could be the basis of the inexplicit design methods, followed by designers without any type of education. It would be a natural evolution of the ability with a constant "dialectical relationship" that forces the rise of creativity. However, the validation of this statement overtakes the scope of the present study, and it is mentioned just as a loose idea for futures research.

Returning to the placing of the model, the design task is the “court” where the study will start his “excavation” to identify actions or operation with traces of the ability. This is an aspect that differentiates the study from others, as most of them consider a whole design activity or/and descend to the level of task at the most. On the one hand because until the new millennium most of the studies could be classified as explorative research. And on the other hand, the current studies, although more descriptive-correlational, are interested in improving all the activity in education through the understanding of the ability in the different stages. There are some studies that are focus on the sublevels besides tasks, but they are not frequent and all of them are focus on specific categories of the model as Outterside with the child or Park and Kim. The former was of particular interest because in her work “The emergence of design ability: the

early years” (2019) uses specific instrument in different operations each one corresponding to a specific category of her model. Park and Kim use a similar approach in his work “visual reasoning model as an analysis tool for different task related to design abilities” (2009) where they call what could be actions as “design task”.

It is important to identify the type of level in the hierarchy to have a clear analysis of the behavior and cognitive elements that are manifested during the study field. This is an affirmation based on the experience of the designer in multiple ergonomic studies for product development, the author has verified how these concepts help to refine the analysis with methods like REBA, RULA, minute per minute, and others. Moreover, after determining through the literature review that the best way to examine the results of the instruments, will be through the “design protocol analysis” based in the protocol analysis in psychology and education, that are historically linked to the activity theory by Vygotsky.

10.5 Differences with other models

The principal difference between the new model and the other revised antecedents is that even considering the structure of the three categories used in the previous models, it does without any fixation with the visual dimension. Hence, the terms are similar to the used for Tang ([Fig.9](#)) but discarding “Sketches” to use “Represent” and changing “Functional reference” for the more comprehensible “Project” finally the last one keeps similar as “Perceive”. It also conserves the idea of knowledge as the links between the categories but use the proposal of the “Design hierarchy knowledge” by Kolaric, Beck and Stolterman. However, a modification of the name “High Knowledge” was made, replaced as “contrasted knowledge” to make it more comprehensible and associated with the current model.

Another particularity was the direction of the process flow, the previous models (except for the creative cognition model) presented bidirectional routes, without any specific start. The proposal travels clockwise and starts

from the “Perceived” category. The reason for this condition is that the design practice starts not as an involuntary action, on the contrary is a reaction to a condition “perceived” in need of a change. The outer world provides the “reason” for design that is perceived in multiple ways. This data is transformed in knowledge that create the idea that is “projected” in the mind and as developed knowledge serves to be “represented” in a physical world which carry a contrasted knowledge of when travel to the “perception” again, and so goes on until the goal is completed.

However, this flow does not go inversely, someone can “perceive” and then “represent” without making a mental image. Even when someone tries to make a figurative draft, some kind of skill related to the short memory will operate as base intermediary from the visual skill used to capture the image to help the skill that is used to manipulate a tool that constructs the image. This kind of example has been thoroughly studied since the initiatives of McKim and Finke. In a more obvious way is not possible to feed the projection of ideas with their representation if a skill related to perception is not used. Maybe for non-designers is not obvious but a designer has a particular way to perceive their representations (even if is a draft or a blueprint each designer will “see” it in a different mode), and this is more evident between designers from different specialties. So, the flow has a specific direction and the participation of the three categories is mandatory.

Fig 9. The visual reasoning models from Tang (2002), Outterside (2019) with the addition of Stolterman et al. “design knowledge Hierarchy” (2020), and Park and Kim (2007).

11 HYPOTHESIS

The hypothesis of this study raises as an answer to the research question of how design ability is present across design and non-design professionals. The statement is based on the model built in the framework and the theoretical foundations developed in the previous chapters. It is considered that everyone possesses the design ability, however, is clear that is not developed equally and not presented in the same kind of tasks. Also, it has been verified that the principles of the creative reasoning model are present in everyone, but there is high probability that each category of the model has its own way of being implementing depending on the practitioner and specially their professions.

The author proposes that the categories of “Perceive” and “Represent” are developed very differently in a professional designer than in a non-designer (notice that he only mentions different not better or worse). The reason to support this affirmation will be the big contrast in the educational curriculum in science or humanities with arts or design. Here is worth clarifying that a curriculum is not understood as the set of subjects and topics that will be attended by a student. Instead, it is seen from the educational sciences as an organic system that is composed of agents and components in constant interaction (Yachi, 2018). If the effects of small changes of educational methods can be notorious in soft skills (part of the categories mentioned), how much should be in a totally different educational perspectives over an ability that one of program tries to promote explicitly.

So, from this perspective, a theoretical examination of each of the components (categories and knowledge) of the model will be made. Starting with the order of the categories which condition are easier to validate due to empiric evidence. So, the first one to consider is “Represent” because is evident that the way in which professional designers materialize their ideas would be (at least most of the time) different than non-designers, even in a similar task. Imagine that one person uses his stack skill with square rocks and other with circulars, the results will be completely different and the experiences too. This will inevitably produce a contrasted knowledge difference but is not limited to the use of

different tools, even between designers using the same instrument can be noticed significant variations in his modes.

As the first, the “Perceive” group, it is an area of study in growing and there is significant evidence that proves that the perception of a professional designer a non-designer is significantly different. The most empirical example could be related to the way that designers from different specialties examine a work outside their expertise. For example, in a piece of art, industrial and graphic designer will focus their attention on different sectors. However, as it takes the raw data from a shared context, the type of knowledge that is acquired would not be completely different even between disciplines, so is proposed that is partially common across the professions.

Finally, for the third category “projection” the author considers that is the exception and there is a share condition, and a high similarity between the skills used by a professional designer and non-designers. Although the way in which ideas are born and are nurtured apparently should be the biggest difference between designer and non-designers. The author consider that is not the case and propose that the reason that could cause this misconception is due the partial different input that is received as contextual knowledge and for a faster and more intensive iteration of the creative reasoning model. This naturally produces a totally different developed knowledge and creates the impression that the components of projection are different. So, considering all the paragraphs above, the synthesis of the hypothesis will be:

“The design ability is common between professional designers and non-design professionals as projection skills and partial contextual knowledge used to materialize a medium that achieves a desired change in a situation.”

The answer proposed is represented in the graphic below ([Fig.10](#)), it shows how each group of professionals possesses its own type of design ability, as each one completes his own model of their creative reasoning model in their non-intersected area. However, as was explained the “Project” category is common to both groups and the category “Perceive” is partially shared with the type of knowledge that is produced there. These elements that are shared in the design ability by the different populations could serve to achieve a common understanding of the design practice ([Fig.11](#)).

Fig 10. Diagram of hypothesis about how design ability is present across professionals' fields.

Fig 11. Sector in red where the bases of a common understanding of design practice can be built.

11.1 Sub-Hypothesis

To validate this hypothesis and translate that procedure in an argument to support it, the sub questions should be answered. This result in a group of sub-hypotheses corresponding to each number:

1. As an exploratory study, the first sub question proposes to use a definition of design ability. This has been done to a certain extent. The construct developed for this study is based on a solid theory as the visual thinking but also the KSA o ability or the activity theory. Although there are improvements made by the author, all of them have support from another research and authors. So, the model presented only needs to be revalidated indirectly with the other sub-hypothesis.
2. As the second sub-hypothesis it is proposed that the projection skills used by professional designers and non-design professionals are similar (there is no fixed list, it would depend on the task) the only major difference would be the way how they are used and the kind of results they get as a developed knowledge. Most perceptual and projection skills are expected to be the same, and to some extend contextual knowledge. On the other hand, there is a high probability that professional designers would use the cycles of the creative reasoning model more intensively and perhaps for this reason complete a cycle faster.
3. The third sub-hypothesis explains the semantic barrier between the two populations considering the differences in the model, the most important of which is the "represent" group, since it assumes that both groups have very different specializations in tools, the only exception will be the ability used for an internal reality "representation". However, it is expected that people will not rely on it as much due to their limitations and prefer to use physical means, which is likely to be seen as an ostensive understanding of design practice and its ability

by non-designers. Finally, designers are expected to clearly recognize the model as a result of their constant practice.

12 VARIABLE OPERATION

The construct developed for the present study is “Design ability as a creative reasoning way to materialize a medium to achieve a desired change in a situation”. The previous chapters have analyzed the different components that make up this statement; on this basis, an operational definition has been established to guide the creation and use of the research instruments. It is important to remember that even with the support of the theories revised in the previous chapters, “any classification divides the reality in an artificial way to study it in deepest and detail” (Lacruz, 2006).

In this way, the studied variable, design ability, is divided into two main dimensions: creative reasoning and specific task. The former is composed of groups of skills (which are the main element corresponding to the categories of the model) and types of knowledge. Meanwhile, the specific task is examined in terms of three main characteristics that indicate the potential use of the creative ability: the materialized medium, the desired change, and the original situation. Each of these indicators is divided into a group of elements that facilitate its understanding.

Using this structure, the following “variable operational chart” will be diagramed ([Table.4](#)). This is a traditional element used in humanities research where the items are the pillars to construct the instruments aiming for a specific data. It summarizes the framework and theoretical foundations used to conduct the study and at the same time helps to orient the results examinations.

Table 4. Variable operational chart

Variable	Variable definition	Dimension	Dimension definition	Indicator	Indicator definition	Item		
Design ability	A creative reasoning applied in a specific task.	Creative reasoning	A cognitive process that uses a sequence of disparate skills through a body of knowledge.	Skills	The adept manual, verbal or mental manipulation of things*	Perception Projection Representation		
				Knowledge	An organized body of information usually of a factual or procedural nature*	Contextual Development Contrasted		
				Materialized medium	A physical result of a task (intervention of an agent over the reality)	Work Product Tool		
				Desired change	The ideal state of the reality aspired as result of the task.	Objective Necessity Subject		
		Original situation	The state of the situation prior to the start of the task.	Environment Problem Stakeholders				
		Specific task	An activity to materialize a medium to achieve a desired change in a situation.					

To complete the chart and based on the author's experience in using this tool in educational research, it was considered to add operational definitions for the items of each dimension (table 5 & 6). They are reviewed in detail in the following subchapters.

12.1 Creative reasoning

Since it is a model of a cognitive process, its components are located exclusively in the subject's mind. It is important to remember that it is not a model for the study of skills (most of them can be considered as a psychomotor area). Instead, it is assumed that thought, formed with the help of the skills, is the structure of the design ability. These thoughts evolve in judgments, decisions, conclusions, and others until they are externalized from their original category in their final form as a kind of knowledge. For this reason, in the end, each type of knowledge in the model can be considered as part of the category that generates it and shares its operational definition. Nevertheless, an operational definition chart (Table. 5) that differentiates the categories as the knowledge is also considered paragraph below to provide a more detailed analysis.

Returning to the category, the skills used in each of them vary according to the task and represent different factors that construct their ideas. It is noted that the skills are shared by different abilities, but it is the combination with the types of knowledge in a specific situation (the task) that determines to which type of ability belongs. Even drawing, which is always associated with design, could be associated with an artistic or an engineering skill. It will depend on a large part of the knowledge that is used, such as an artist will consider his knowledge of the expressiveness of the lines and the change of grading or tone. On the other hand, the person who makes a blueprint will pay attention to the clarity, cleanliness, and homogeneity of his drafts.

Thus, it is not adequate to make a list of fixed skills that correspond to design. Although some studies present them, they are limited to their context and objectives. Just consider that a list of industrial designers, while complete, is not the same as a graphic designer or the many other specializations of design that exist and will exist. It will be better to consider that regardless of the type of skill used in the practice of design, it includes a cognitive aspect, reflections that arise from them and have the structure of creative reasoning model as part of the design ability involved. Therefore, a list of skills is not as valuable as an operational description of the thoughts used in all of them. The following table is divided into the thoughts that are associated with each category and correspond to the structure of design practice.

Table 5. Categories operational chart

CATEGORY	OPERATIONAL DEFINITION
Perception	Thoughts based on the interpretation or descriptions of what it is perceived concerning the task.
Projection	Thoughts that build the idea of a proposal result of the ideal task concluded. Usually related to the future and about something that doesn't exist yet.
Representation	Thoughts that mirror the behavior in the reality made it when externalize the proposal. Usually related to the immediate present.

On the other hand, design knowledge is acquired not only in education but also in practice. This means that this knowledge is accessible to everyone in daily

life and that it is a matter of experience to gain a valid understanding of one's activities. Nowadays, this is an epistemological fact shared in the field of curriculum development, where a disciplinary knowledge can be considered as the way data is understood through an approach acquired by the historical evolution of a professional role. In the case of this study, this practical knowledge was classified using the hierarchy theory revised.

The most important aspect of this classification is its relationship to the three categories of skills. This is because it also implies that the knowledge acquired in practice is shared by all disciplines. There is no exclusive practical knowledge, as each professional can approach the same challenges with a different approach. In addition, the creative reasoning model proposes that one always uses the three types of hierarchy. To identify each manifestation, and additional table of operational definitions ([Table.6](#)) is used.

Table 6. Knowledge operational chart

KNOWLEDGE	OPERATIONAL DEFINITION
Contextual	Facts that come from the senses perched in the situation that it is tried to change.
Development	The mental image, list of requirements or any clear reference of the idea that wants to be represented.
Contrasted	Data inferred through the materialization of the development knowledge. It will always be contrasted with what was expected and, in that way, refined.

12.2 Specific task

The specific tasks described in this study and used as the basis for the fieldwork have the potential use of the design ability. They are situations in which an activity takes place to achieve a desired change. They could be considered very similar to the idea of design situation. However, they should not be treated as synonymous with design tasks, as these imply a definite use of design ability, since they usually associate with designer labor. In this case, the "specific tasks" represent a probability of the existence of a common design ability, but

it is still uncertain, as they are practices performed by professionals from different disciplines.

Thanks to the principles of activity theory, the differences between a task, an operation, or an action are clear. Thus, traditional actions related to design such as making decisions, identifying problems or making a choice are studied in a broad perspective. Always from the point of view of the need to materialize a product. These conditions seem to make every human activity a potential design situation used in this study. This is normal and part of the context that supports this research. Supposedly design is a practice that everyone engages in, but the reason it goes unnoticed is that it is mixed with other skills and some of them take precedence.

For this reason, it is necessary to choose a practice that has a high compatibility with the design ability. If an arbitrary method is chosen, the analysis becomes more difficult because the variable could be buried under many layers of other capabilities. Therefore, decomposing the indicators into items helps to identify the task that is closest to the variable under study. This does not mean that the population under study must know the items under consideration, but even their unnoticed presence can influence the selection of the ideal task.

Thus, the "specific task" consists, first, of a materialized medium whose actions, with the help of a tool, result in a product. Second, it consists of a desired change that motivates the subject's goal. Finally, an original situation is placed in an environment where a problem occurs, surrounded by stakeholders. With all these elements, another operational chart is created for the specific task ([Table 7](#)).

Table 7. Specific task operational chart

INDICATOR	ITEMS	ITEM DEFINITION
Materialized medium	Actions	A group of operations organized to achieve the task.
	Product	The result of the application of a tool for a task.
	Tool	A physical element that is used in the task to perform an action.
	Objective	An aspiration that leads a task.

Desired change	Motivation	The absence or lack of something required for the task.
	Subject	The characteristics of the individual that performs the task.
Original situation	Environment	The components where the task happen.
	Problem	A catalyst of causes to effects from the task.
	Stakeholders	Individuals, groups, or institutions related to the task.

13 FIELDWORK

The aim of the fieldwork is to evaluate the functionality of the creative reasoning model to understand the behavior in the specific task selected. The model will be used to analyze and understand the design ability of different professions in a similar situation. The collected data will be used to achieve the sub-objectives necessary to answer the research question. Then, the hypotheses will be compared with the results and the conclusions will be made. Each [Sub-Objective](#) of the previous section, "[7. Objectives](#)," can be translated into a type of data that must be collected as part of the process and put together like a piece of a puzzle when evaluating the [hypothesis](#):

The first piece of the puzzle is to test the functionality of the selected model of design ability to identify its presence in non-designer professionals. This validates the results that construct the other two sub-objectives, especially for the population of non-design professionals. It is expected that there will be no inconvenience when the model is used to analyze the behavior of designers, since it is a model that originated in the field of design and has been used and evaluated in a variety of studies.

As the second piece, the model should be used to define how the design ability of the two groups, non-design professionals, and professional designers, are similar. It is important to highlight that there are also differences between designers in their design abilities, this could be based on their experience and education (especially if they come from different specialties), it is expected

that this case will be even more evident in non-designers. Nevertheless, in order to establish the future contrast of the population, homogeneity must first be achieved.

Ultimately, the third sub-objective is to understand the way that professional designers and non-design professionals perceive the creative reasoning model. To clarify the reason, if the ability is present, it is not treated in the same way for both groups. This final data will provide depth to the study's answer. Identifying commonalities in all fields lays the foundation to comprehend the design ability, but it is recognizing the differences which allows a better integration between disciplines.

13.1 Background

In the last decade, the number of studies on design ability has been steadily increasing. Most of them are related to the use of the theoretical foundations used for developing the proposal of creative reasoning. Although all the reviewed studies were evaluated as examples, the most important ones were selected based on their proximity to the research question, population, and method of the present study, which will be analyzed in this section. Based on these criteria, six studies were selected, two comparative studies on populations, two directly related to the model, and two related to the main population studied (non-designers).

The first study selected is called “Comparing designing across different domains: An exploratory case study” by Jeff Kan and John Gero from 2011. This document is a comparative study between engineers, architects, and software programmers. It is relevant to focus on three different disciplines, even if they are not professional designers, all of them have disciplines directly related to design, to the point of refer themselves as "designers". The method used on the other hand was based on a different task for each unit of analysis and a design protocol analysis to identify the common aspects.

The second study comes from Libby Osgood and Clifton Johnston “Assessing Design Ability through a Quantitative Analysis of the Design Process”. It is the most recent study on the list, published in 2022, and presents a comparison of undergraduate and graduate students at different levels using a common case with a real design task. The study has a duration of one semester and was implemented remotely, using an approach based on the analysis of their method. Due to the significant amount of the population, a statistical analysis was conducted to support the conclusions.

The third study, as mentioned in the paragraphs above, refers to the use of the model. It is one of the first works of the new century to use the visual reasoning approach, which is directly based on visual reasoning. Hsien-Hui Tang presented it in 2003 as “Visual Reasoning and Knowledge in the Design Process”. In it, he makes a comparison of a student and a professional designer establishing several improvements to the model (introducing clear types of knowledge) as well to the method of research using the coding scheme DCOCS (design content-oriented coding scheme) to a behavior observation method.

The fourth study is from 2009 and is titled “Visual reasoning model as an analysis tool for different tasks related to design abilities”. Their authors Yong Se Kim and Jung Ae Park translate their model in a diagram that helps a better understanding of the theoretical bases used and the protocol examination. Their population was composed of four engineering senior students, and the instruments used to sample were one specific for each category of the model, using the think aloud procedure in all cases. Since a fixed list of components of each category was considered, a statistical correlation analysis was performed and used to elaborate their conclusions.

For the fifth case, focused on non-designers, the study “The emergence of design ability: the early years” by Yvonne Outterside in 2019 was selected. A republication of a work presented in the conference IDATER of 1993, this study is particularly interesting because its units of analysis are preschool-aged children. Like the previous study, three specific tests were conducted to evaluate her model, which is based in the “visual thinking” and is very similar to the “visual reasoning”. However, their interpretation of the categories is more suited to the present studio as it is not fixed in visual skills (although the

instrument is based on them). This has already been mentioned in detail in the chapter "[10. Theoretical foundations](#)".

Finally, the sixth reference is the study of Peter Cheng and Herbert Simon. Part of the title of his work is used as inspiration for the name of the model "Scientific discovery and creative reasoning with diagrams". Although the older research of the group, published in 1993, is considered the closer to the conceptual work of this thesis. The study explores the practice of physics and the use of diagrams to represent their mathematical problems to achieve a different way of thinking. Their results show that this activity is widespread among them and is highly related to the use of design qualities.

As can be seen, there are numerous applications for the creative reasoning approach. Some studies, the most significant for the author and the present document, have been conducted for non-designers. However, there is no study comparing design ability of non-design professionals with professional designers; and studies on non-designers are limited and not related to professions. This study uses the experiences and suggestions of the previous documents to open a new area of work.

13.2 Procedure

The method of obtaining the necessary data was based on the background studies and refined with the help of the study's assessors during the meetings at the end of each section of the timeline. Thanks to their keen eye, significant improvements and key decisions were made to adjust the route of the fieldwork. The final plan, which can also be seen in the timeline, is divided into three exploratory stages and a fourth to share the results and seek the opinion of the participants. The synthesis of the procedure will be:

1. Identify the specific task to be performed and the ideal units of analysis.
2. Interpolate the creative reasoning model in the analysis of the behavior during the task.

3. Retrospective study of the task and use of an isolated basic operation where the design ability is clearly applied to introduce the perception of the model indirectly to the subjects.
4. Share the findings with the units of analysis to know their opinion and their point of view. That could be considered as an epilogue of the work.

As can be seen, the collected data will be used in the third phase to test the hypothesis and answer the research question. The [fourth phase](#) is considered as an addition to the study, which will give an outlook on the results of the conducted work. It is recommended to read it after the conclusions. The stages were more complex than expected and a specific instrument was developed based on the data previously obtained. Due to this close connection with the results of each stage and for pedagogical reasons, a detailed description of the process of each stage is given in the introduction of the chapters dedicated to the stages.

13.3 Analysis unit

There are two main groups that have a common pattern of design ability: Designers as individuals who focus on recognized design activities, and non-designers as professionals who never have formal contact with a design activity. The study focuses on the latter group but considers the origins of this population from tertiary education, as the context in which the problem occurs is directly related to this type of professional. This is not a coincidence, since most professional designers work in an administrative environment or where strategic or tactical work is carried out.

This relationship between professional designers and non-design professionals, as mentioned in the problem statement, was validated through the literature review, but also through the practice of the author and his colleagues. Therefore, the main sample of the study is the non-design professionals, since this type of non-design professionals is the population in which the problem usually occurs. Nevertheless, there is a wide variety of

possible participants in the situation under study, which is why the sample does not focus on a specific professional group but aims for a wide range.

In addition to these participants and considering that the research is a descriptive-comparative study, a "control group" or "ideal" sample is needed for the manifestation of design ability. For this reason, a group of professional designers is included during the fieldwork with the same instrument and task. This is the population that perceives the problem, and therefore they are used as a reference to understand the way design practice manifests design ability and to compare it with non-design professionals.

As mentioned at the beginning of this study, it is important to remember that not being a professional designer does not imply being a non-designer. A person who has no formal education in design, but who typically engages in an activity that is recognized by him or others as design, is a "designer." Similarly, there are some disciplines that do not come from a design faculty but are closely related to the practice of design, such as architecture, art, and some engineering.

Considering this and the fact that the research resources do not afford a considerable number of study units, the best representative data for the research problem was selected by conducting a study with extreme cases. This means that the ideal professional designers were selected and compared with the ideal non-designers. The following are the requirements that must be fulfilled in order to participate in the study:

Professional designers

- Graduated from different design programs.
- High experience in their fields (+5 years of experience).

Non-design professionals

- Without a previous formation in design, not courses or programs.
- From a program that is not close to design departments (art, architecture, or engineering).

- Representatives of bigger groups of disciplines that other professionals could relate to.
- Minimal or no contact with designers in their work.

14 FIRST STAGE

The aim of the first phase of fieldwork is to identify the "specific task" shared by non-design professionals and professional designers with the highest potential to demonstrate design ability. This task is derived by examining the responsibilities and roles of the samples, finding common actions and processes in their daily work. The method of data collection required quite consideration and the evaluation of three main alternatives. The first was the most direct, which consisted of collecting a regular day or work of the units of analysis. The second option was suggested by one of the assessors, which was a focus group to discuss the common tasks with the participants. The third option was an individual interview with the prospective samples.

Each of the options has its advantages and disadvantages. For example, the first option would be the most detailed register of their activities. However, this requires a special recording tool or a person to follow them, as well as the approval of the colleagues they are in contact with and the company where they work. Even more, probably one day would not be enough and several records are required over a longer period. So, the benefits are outweighed by the complications, making it an impractical alternative.

The second method, using a format more similar to a focus group, was proposed with the intention of using a real team of workers with a professional designer in their company. This has the distinct advantage of exploring the particular situation of the problem in their environment. However, the difficulty of obtaining such a group and the feasibility of reconciling the schedules of individual participants in the short period of time available for fieldwork make this an unviable option.

The interviews are the third option to consider. This method is not as precise as the other because it depends heavily on the quality of questions and effectiveness. Fortunately, the author has broad experience with this technique from his professional practice with study markets and his previous academic work. With an appropriate instrument, an interview can provide important data consistent with previous suggestions. The two main advantages are a general compilation of the multiple activities over a period that the subject remembers without interference from others, and a reflective register of the activities noted with more potential for task extraction.

This reflection on past activities can be a great advantage as it is considered part of the traditional method of behavior analysis. The so-called "introspective" study is usually combined with the concurrent and retrospective protocols used in the next stages. This information is provided by the subjects when they are asked how they proceed in performing the specific tasks. This is another way to "report after the completion of task" in addition to the most direct "retrospective" method. But instead of using the register created by the examiner, subjects turn to their long-term memory based on previous experience. Thus, it is not precise or solid data, but it is an excellent starting point.

After deciding on the technique to use, a pre-selection of the population was made. The group consisted of eleven non-design professionals (seven living in Germany) and thirteen professional designers (nine living in Germany). They correspond to Generation Y (born from 1982-1997) and from them the better two samples of each type were selected for the next phase based on their results. The names of the interviewees and the information they provided are subject to confidentiality, so the transcriptions of the raw data are not published in this document.

14.1 Instrument first stage

Among the different ways to conduct an interview, a semi-structured model was chosen as a specific technique. This has the advantage of being able to

manage the time well with the research unit and not get lost in the many different data to be collected. The interviews consist of two parts, the first with general inquiries about his profession and experiences that help to identify possible tasks. The second part uses two specific tasks identified in the previous section to explore how they are performed and how they perceive the relationship to design practices.

The sessions are approximately forty minutes in duration, but in some cases have been extended to one hour. The first part lasts about fifteen minutes and the second thirty. Zoom software was generally used to record the virtual appointments. In the few cases where it was not possible to use this platform or a physical interview was arranged, an audio recorder was used. After the interviews were completed, all data were transcribed and compiled into tables to facilitate comparison. The detailed instrument, which includes the operational table with the items, the guide, and the battery of questions with a marking guide, can be found in [Appendix I](#).

The questions used were open-ended and further exploration was occasionally conducted based on the responses. The reagents set were based on the items in the operational table from the “specific task” section. In the first part, three reagents were used per item, and in the second part, two were used. In the second part, the question round is repeated once, as each time a specific task was selected from the previous part. The author had experience in developing instruments of this type thanks to his Master’s in Education where conducted research for curriculum analysis (2018). An important aspect is that neither a “validation of expert ” nor a test of the instrument was required. However, the latter was done on personal initiative with a subject for each main population and some improvements were made rephrasing questions, merging, and adding others.

14.2 Non-design professionals’ answers

The diversity of this group's responses made it possible to identify some common aspects of their work and their perception of design. It is worth noting,

however, that a pair of professionals from a "craft" tradition were also included; a pastry chef and a musician were included at the suggestion of one of the assessors. They were not originally included because are not part of the typical tertiary programs, but it was a useful addition because they fit the requirements of the study and give another value perspective.

This inclusion was really valuable because the results were very different from the rest of the sample. The most surprising data was that both units responded with full confidence that their work involves design practice and that they possess and use design ability with naturalness. This means that they did not have to mentally strain to remember or analyze their actions in order to respond. Something that is at least difficult for the rest of the population to answer, if not with a clear negative.

Not only that, but they offer a variety of activities in which they use the ability to design and even try to identify the exact episodes in which this is evident with specific examples, like the chef with the plating, or the musician with the encryption. This simple recognition of the use and presence of design capability makes it unsuitable for the study of extreme cases envisioned in this document. Although it is a very interesting research topic, the response to this finding could be used as a topic for another research requiring a larger sample of other disciplines that originate from craftsmanship.

Nevertheless, to explain this event the author ventures a guess based on historical bases. It is worth considering that, as David Raizman asserts (2003), the history of modern design began with the division of design and craft. Before that, they had a common root, and it is only natural that other disciplines that emerged from craft activities preserve this part in their "genetic". Probably, the traces of common design ability have been strongly passed on and transformed in their professional practices, providing another alternative to understand the fundamentals of design.

After evaluating the data from all these units, it was found that some other professionals did not meet the requirements for design education. This result was unexpected, but some of them had taken some courses related on design thinking in their undergraduate programs. Even those who frequently collaborate with designers indicated that they would be interested in receiving

some supplemental training. This follows the theory that people who have ongoing close relationships with designers develop a better understanding of design practice and seek to complement their work.

Oddly enough, another common response from people in contact with designers was that they are some of the most difficult professionals to work with. The most common reason was that they work on the edge of deadlines and delays often occur. Similarly, engineers are among the easiest to work with. They indicated that communication with them is clear because they are straight to the point about what is needed, what is wanted, or what the problem is. They are also well organized and methodical in their approach.

A special case of the rest of the group was the nurse, as their activities were highly related to operational tasks. These are actions that do not aim to "produce" something to achieve a specific change, but to preserve and maintain an existing system. This is partly due to the use of highly automated tools such as the pressure gauge or the patient record (which is on a screen that receives only the characters typed). It was considered that the complexity of refining the activity, even if these systems required design ability, would overwhelm the present fieldwork resources and would also require at least a few similar cases to identify patterns. For this reason, it was removed from the final study list.

The final sample with ideal conditions for the extreme case study consisted of five people. Most of their answers were very similar to the main differences in the second part of the interview. However, even in the group of designers, there was one common task mentioned by almost all of them, which was digital presentations. When this was noted, the author turned again to the units that had not mentioned it to find out if they did. The answers were affirmative, but they did not mention it before because it is a very rare activity that happens at most once a month.

The majority of this select group clearly stated that they do not use design ability or knowledge in their work. In addition, when asked if they felt they had some level of design ability, they immediately declined. Although all of them create digital presentations (which was considered by the designer to be a type of design practice) and some of them do it very frequently, there was no

direct connection to this activity. The respondents did not try to reflect about this situation, as will be observed in the second phase of the study.

However, there were a couple who did take time to respond and reflect on their activities and mention that they use design ability in some ways for some tasks. When further asked how they view this manifestation, they directly referred to aesthetic aspects and subjective judgments. However, they also think that design ability is related to technical skills that they lack in order to develop complex tasks, such as "making products".

When asked about the process of task creation selected in the second part of the interview, only one of them related his work to design, the language teacher. Although most of the selected tasks can be classified in the area of strategic activities and require a strong use of projection skills. This, based on the model of the study, will be an indication of the use of design ability. Another common aspect with the designer group is that they recognize that a task is well done by receiving feedback from the people who receive the work. This also applies to their digital presentations, which do not appear to be completed in a fixed amount of time but are improved sporadically until the deadline.

Table 8. non-design professional sample

<i>NON-DESIGN PROFESIONALS</i>				
<i>Profession</i>	Design education	Work with designer	Task1	Task2
<i>Language teacher</i>	None?	None	Class planning	Digital presentations
<i>Project manager</i>	None	None	Schedule meetings	Digital presentations
<i>Project manager</i>	Partial	Some	3d modeling	Digital presentations
<i>Nurse</i>	None	None	Pressure control	Patient file filling
<i>Financial consultant</i>	None	Some	Data analysis	Digital presentations

<i>Mechanic engineer</i>	Partial	Some	3d modeling	Blueprints
<i>Communication coordinator</i>	None	None	Activity planning	Digital presentations
<i>Digital product manager</i>	Partial	None	Detail functions for apps	Digital presentations
<i>Industrial engineer</i>	None	None	Supply checking	Digital presentations
<i>Pastry Chef</i>	None?	None	Plating	Testing new flavors
<i>Musician</i>	None?	None	Song encryption	Equalize

The previous [table 8](#) shows the characteristics of the group studied. The green color highlights the professionals who create digital presentations in their work, even if this happens infrequently. Meanwhile, the red color marks the samples that have been dismissed for his design education or conscious relationship with design practice. Finally, the yellow color corresponds to the professionals who have contact with designers, but not as a condition of exclusion.

14.3 Professional designers' results

The answers of the professional designers served as a reference to identify the ideal "specific task" and were almost a natural result that came without effort. Almost all of them mentioned creating digital presentations with varying frequency. However, the most interesting data was provided by an advertising designer who said that the most often task in his job is to make digital presentations in PowerPoint. Moreover, with the time, it ended being considered equivalent to creating a poster or infographic. The only difference

is the canvas but was described as a design task that is just as complex and challenging as any other professional jobs.

This assertion was confirmed when it was asked about their process and considerations in the second part of the interview. Therefore, in the following session with the other units of analysis, the elaboration of the digital presentation was consulted and immediately selected to be studied in the second part of the interviews. The only exceptions were two textile designers and one industrial designer who mentioned that they did not work with presentations.

The probable reason is their position as juniors or operative roles, due to their modest professional experience. This could be related to the fact that the more experienced designers are involved in environments with a greater diversity of professionals and sometimes are the only designers in the area. In that situation, they consider a key responsibility to communicate the proposal in the clearest way possible and the presentations are a useful tool for that.

Therefore, all designers who create digital presentations consider them as a design product and use their design ability for this purpose. The tools they use to create them vary. Some use Figma, InDesign, Illustrator and PowerPoint as usual. Surprisingly, the designer who creates the presentations mentioned uses the latter more often. The reason was that other members of the company can easily and quickly change the original files.

After excluding those who did not meet the experience requirements, a total of five designers are left. Even though most of the responses were very similar across the samples, except for task and work location, where the new designer generally spent equal amounts of time in workshops and in offices. One response that particularly stood out to the author was that professional designers feel that most of their design tasks can be done by other professionals if they know how to use the tools, but with poorer results.

The main reason why they think that other professionals do not get the same "quality", even from other designers, is related to the knowledge they acquire in their work and not in their education as designers. This is a very controversial issue that could be related to the Dunning-Kruger effect, where they underestimate their own design ability and overestimate those of non-

designers. However, it could also be because they directly and fundamentally associate design ability with the ability to use "design" tools and experience.

When asked about those who are more difficult to work with, respondents indicated that they were professionals from sales departments because they generally do not take time into consideration. When asked who is easier to work with, they mentioned designers from other departments or blue-collar personnel because they are more open to their suggestions and are willing to mix their knowledge rather than confront them.

The following [table 9](#) shows the list of different designers consulted and marks in green who creates digital presentations. In red those who do not meet the experience requirements (discharged) and in yellow those who work in an environment where there are only designers, such as a design studio.

Table 9. Professional designer sample

<i>PROFESSIONAL DESIGNERS</i>				
<i>Profession</i>	Design experience	Environment with other professionals	Task1	Task2
<i>Industrial designer</i>	+10	Full	3d modeling	Digital presentations
<i>Visual designer</i>	+10	Full	Iconography	Digital presentations
<i>Fashion & product designer</i>	-5	Some	Technical Drawing	Clothes detailing
<i>Industrial designer</i>	+10	Full	3d modeling	Quotations
<i>Advertisement designer</i>	-5	Full	Infographic	Digital presentations
<i>Textile designer</i>	-5	None	Fabric proposal	Mood board

<i>Industrial designer</i>	-5	None	Briefs	Digital presentations
<i>Textile designer</i>	+10	Some	Silhouette proposals	Digital presentations
<i>Graphic designer</i>	+10	Some	Visuals to ads	Digital presentations

15 SECOND STAGE

The method selected to conduct the second stage of the study was evaluated from the review of the literature, as can be observed in the timeline. It was clear that, to understand how the design ability is present across professions, some kind of approximation should be necessary to the practice of professionals. In addition, in developing the framework, it was noted that most studies of design ability come from disciplines close related to design in special architecture and mechanical engineering and there is a recent increase in the last decade that use analysis of professional designers or student in formal design programs to reach the current understanding.

Thus, it was no coincidence that most prior studies mentioned above, use “protocol studies”, a term the author was familiar, though not directly, from educational research. There, the method is often used to understand the learning process, and it is usually applied in dissertations where control groups are used to test the effectiveness of new educational methods. At the end of the theoretical foundations, it was found that the technic has been transferred to the design field since the 1960s under the unofficial name of “design protocol analysis” which is the current name used in the community that study the design ability.

At the time when the variable operation was carried out, it was also concluded that this method is strongly connected with the procedure of thinking aloud. In psychology, it first appeared in the 1930s with Otto Selz, who coincidentally develop it to study “creative reasoning processes” (Someren et al., 1994).

Gradually, it has been used in the design field and it is important to observe that the work of Simon, Schön and Cross (main references of this thesis) rely heavily on this technique, which consists in a mixture of the protocol method and the aloud procedure.

Later, the use of design protocol analysis and thinking aloud was strongly promoted by the Delft University of Technology in the 1990s thanks to the Faculty of Industrial Design Engineering, which organized the workshop "Analyzing design activity" in September 1994. They were "regarded as the most likely method (perhaps the only method) to bring out into the open the somewhat mysterious cognitive abilities of designers" (Cross and Dorst, 1996).

"The adoption of protocol analysis as a research technique for design is an effort on the part of design methodologists to find a rigorous form for their empirical research. Protocol analysis is somewhere in the middle ground between the 'hard' experimental methods of the natural sciences and the 'weaker' purely observational methods of the social sciences ...The number of protocol studies in design has been growing steadily since the beginning of the 1980s" (Dorst, 1995)

The spark for a wide variety of new studies starts and a "review on design protocol studies identified that this method is not only accepted by one or few design disciplines; in fact, almost all major design disciplines adopted protocol analysis as a valid research tool." (Jiang et al., 2009) Although, more than one third of the work until 2009 comes from the industrial design. However, this does not mean that are used exclusively for the study of the design practice.

In special from the industrial design field, design protocol analysis "included non-designers, i.e., people without specific design training, as their research subjects. Most of these studies were user studies" (Jiang et al., 2009). This means that is also an effective method to examine the usability of the products, in a way very similar to ergonomic studies, like the minute per minute, where a session of an activity is recorded and then evaluated in fixed ranges. As a note, there is a high probability that ergonomic methods were inspired by the protocols as they were formalized at the end of the millennium, but there is no specific proof.

15.1 Concurrent protocol

The way the protocol method is implemented with the think aloud procedure is usually called a "concurrent protocol". This research technique consists of recording an activity while the performer speaks what he or she is essentially thinking in a clear voice. It is not a reflection or description of the thoughts, but a mirror of them, saying them as they come to mind. So, it tries to give direct information about the cognitive process and all this data is transcribed to analyze it. This can be done quantitatively or qualitatively, as has been done for both types of research.

Regardless of the case, this practice requires a significant amount of time, even for preliminary preparation. As seen in the present study, the first phase was designed to determine the best task for the test and the ideal participants. This is important to consider and has been included in the descriptive diagram below, which simplifies the workflow very well (Fig.12). It is a demanding way to research but is considered “among the more detailed techniques for studying short term processes” (Dorst, 1995).

Fig 12. A practical guideline to quantifying qualitative analyses of design cognition. (Rusmadiyah Anwar et al., 2015). Mod by Cesar Yachi (2023)

Fig 13. The think aloud method, *A practical guide to modelling cognitive processes* (Someren, Barnard and Sandberg, 1994). Mod by Cesar Yachi (2023)

The diverse literature reviewed for the development of the instrument generally recommends a task duration of no more than two hours, taking into account the average active concentration of the participants. In addition, multiple sessions may be scheduled, although given the subsequent work required to process the data, it is recommended that the total length of the

protocols (i.e., the total time including all study sessions) be limited to 10-1000 minutes.

After the session is recorded, which is referred to as the registered protocol, the conversion of the raw data into cooked data is usually referred to as the "coding" process. This starts with dividing the document into manageable sections to analyze them individually. These parts are called "segments" and sometimes grouped for a more complex study; in which case these groups are called "episodes". The segments are analyzed using the research framework, which creates a tool to identify the variables. This is referred to as the "coding scheme" and is the "Rosetta stone" to understanding the behaviors and thoughts recorded.

The described procedure ended with the "coding protocols" as the result, which are compared with the hypothesis of the study. Usually, the model made in the framework can be translated as the "coded protocol predicted". In this way, conclusions can be obtained, and the protocol method is completed. The information obtained will be then used to evaluate the hypothesis. This technique can be visually understood thanks to the diagram of Someren, Barnard and Sandberg ([Fig. 13](#)), where the reference images of the different components from this document have been placed.

15.2 Instrument second stage

The required task was chosen based on the results of the first phase, where it was found that most participants make a digital presentation. Although the frequency of this task is not equally common to all, the results are physically similar, so the cognitive process is more likely to differentiate the work. Even though the topic of this assignment was initially planned to be something similar to their usual work, there would be some inconveniences in asking them that:

1. The lack of material required for a novel presentation, as the content used could be the result of previous activities that required a lot of effort.
2. The topic of the different units of analysis could be very different as they all have roles and different disciplines, which may make it difficult to analyze their approach.
3. The time and availability for sharing information generated for their work or material for their work could affect their willingness to participate.

This problem could be solved thanks to an assessor who suggested to use as a topic; to explain their field or/and their work to others. This was the best alternative, as it allowed them to use all their knowledge and available materials, while considering the use of content that could be made available to the public. Moreover, since the topic is the same for all of them, it is possible to use a fixed time and a similar criterion of analysis for the different episodes that will appear during the coding.

After selecting the task, it was necessary to select the participants. Due to the complexity and resources required to carry out the second phase, the sample was narrowed down to four participants. Two units of analysis from each main group, each of whom was considered an ideal candidate for a specific reason, as can be seen in the table of final participants.

Table 10. Extreme cases chart

Type	Profession	Main reason to select them
Non-design professionals	Project management	There are multiple disciplines that specialize as project management and designer find them frequently in their collaborative teams.
	Financial consultant	Its part of the group of professionals that are classified to be harder to work with. Tentatively their manifestation of the design ability should be the more different.
Professional designers	Graphic designer	It recognize make presentation a design task equivalent to make infographics and it is part of its main labor.
	Industrial designer	The only designer in the company. So, the work is permanently in collaborative teams.

They also indicated in the first interview that they work more intensively or less frequently on the "specific task". Thus, the project manager and the industrial designer give their presentations with a low frequency, which could be less than monthly, and the financial consultant and the graphic designer with a high frequency, namely several times a week, especially the former.

It is important to remember that this research will not compare the quality of the presentations with the practical products obtained during the fieldwork. It does not even assess the degree of design in them. The goal is to identify the presence of design ability in their processes and how it is manifested. The files made are just a pretext to create a potential situation that triggers the use of the ability and registers it for study.

The tool used for this purpose is the Zoom software, which allows recording the camera and the screen on which the device is working. The learning group received a guide a few days before the session, informing them about the session procedure. However, the questions and topic of the document were withheld to prevent them from creating a preliminary file or response. The document provided can be found in [Appendix II](#). A presentation was also used to introduce the different parts of the meeting. The slices of this document can be found in [Appendix III](#).

The "interview" process lasted approximately forty-five minutes and consisted of five parts. Three questionnaires, each with two open-ended questions. A warm-up part in which the participants practiced the procedure of "think aloud" to communicate any inconvenience, and the main part with the task request. This part has a fixed time span of 20 - 30 minutes. During this time, the author turns off his camera and uses the microphone only to say to continue speaking if the participant is silent.

The warm-up part was a suggestion from the book used as the main reference for conducting the second phase: "The think aloud method, A practical guide to modelling cognitive processes" (Someren, Barnard and Sandberg, 1994). The idea is to introduce the sample to and familiarize them with expressing

their thoughts using simple thinking exercises. They were not scored, but at the end of this part they were asked if the participant experienced any inconvenience. This was a useful way to fine-tune the procedure before starting the main task.

The questionnaires besides the included at the back part of the warm-up were one at the beginning and another at the end, both with two main questions about their assessment of design practice and design ability. In this way, at the beginning they do not associate design with creating a digital presentation and their answers are more spontaneous. In contrast, the third survey is asked at the end of the main task with two questions that are very similar. It was expected that (in the case of the non-design professionals) reflection and available short-term memory would cause their answer to differ from or contradict the previous.

15.3 Data processing

When using design protocol analysis, there are two main approaches depending on what is used as the basis for the study, although sometimes they are even combined, similar to quantitative and qualitative studies. The two types are usually referred to as process-oriented and content-oriented analysis (Jiang et al., 2009). The former focuses on how the activity is performed and uses the structure of the process, which is translated into a method. The latter, on the other hand (to which the present study belongs), focuses on "what designers look for, see, do, and possibly think" (Dorst and Dijkhuis, 1995).

It is worth noting that process-oriented analysis was the more popular in the previous century and was heavily used by studies from the field that sought to understand design practice through the method. As you may recall from the "scope" chapter, this line of thinking was most prevalent using the methodology and much of its development is based on the insights gained through the use of design protocols, though not always in combination with

the procedure of the think aloud. The reason for this is that the process-oriented type uses the physical behaviors and their outcome manifestations as elements for understanding its study variables.

The content-oriented analysis, on the other hand, needs access to the thoughts that are part of the activity, and the procedure of thinking aloud is the best way to obtain them. The purpose of recording the activity and examining it from beginning to end is to find and examine cognitive processes, not to describe a method or understand the final product. It is necessary to record all events because there is a high probability that the variable under study will not be present all the time but will occur sporadically or not at all. Since there is no certainty, it is necessary to examine all registers in detail.

As described in the research technique, once the data were transcribed, they were divided into sections of approximately one minute to analyze duration, as in an ergodic minute per minute study. This was the initial tactic, based on the author's experience in ergonomic studies, with the goal of making the data more manageable and finding the real "units" inside them. As stated in the "theoretical foundation" chapter, the "creative reasoning" should be a "model placed in context", the minimal part in which the model goes through a cycle (the segments) and manifests the design ability is the operations. Meanwhile, the interaction of the model in the long run (the episodes) should be associated with actions.

Considering this aspect with the principles revised in the "[5. Research question](#)", it could be related to the classification of segments and episodes. Thus, while a segment corresponds to a complete cycle of the categories in the model and therefore use of the design ability in an operation. The episodes correspond to the mix of these operations to achieve a specific action that can be partially or fully performed with the constant flow of the creative reasoning model. The following ([table 11](#)) shows the equivalence of the elements, with the minimum presence of the design ability highlighted in green:

Table 11. Equivalence, activity theory with protocol analysis

Model flow	Activity theory hierarchy	Protocol analysis method
Multiple cycles	Action	Episode
One cycle	Operation	Segment

The initial division of the protocol into minutes helps to focus on identifying what is happening without getting lost in the volume of data. For this purpose, a coding scheme was used, which describes in detail which types of thoughts belong to each category of the model. It was initially based on possible verbalizations, as is the most common and easiest way to transfer the data into social science software. It was not planned to rely on statistical data, but it would have been easier to use the software to draw conclusions through correlation analysis. Unexpectedly, while proceeding with these verbal codes, discrepancies arose in some segments.

It turned out that trying to use word codes was not the appropriate way to proceed, as the generated verbal thoughts have a very relative meaning to be placed in specific categories, as the verbs can be used in more than one sense. For example, "want" should obviously only be associated with the category "perceive". For to "want something" would connote a desire stemming from a need, and this from a perception. However, it could also be associated with a need that comes from the other two categories. The following are examples of verbalized thoughts in which "want" is used in each category:

- **Perceive:** *"I want to use more of this orange color"* / this state a desire from a perceived need, the participant visualize something and acquire a contextual knowledge.
- **Project:** *"I want to make a presentation about..."* / here the subject is defining a goal based in what was perceived (Previously he heard the requirements) and probably associate some implicit conditions with it creating the mental image or at least an idea of the presentation.
- **Represent:** *"I want to delete this slice too"* / in this case the thought is about an action that the participant is currently doing as part of the representation of his mental image.

As one can see, the use of "want" can contextually fit into any of the three categories of the model. For this reason, using a verbalization based on vocabulary would not be effective. Instead, it was decided to use the ["operational definitions"](#) from the ["12. Variable operation"](#) chapter. This is a tactic that is as recognized in the literature as the previous one but is more

complex due to the manual analysis of each segment of the raw data, as was done in the previous example.

Originally it was thought that the operations would be composed by a group of sentences, and although it happens occasionally, due to the velocity of the thoughts, it was common to find that all the cycle is mixed in just one sentence. This means that much of the protocol was studied as a grammar of structured sentences but using the principles of the operational chart of the “[creative reasoning](#)” subchapter. It was a welcome surprise that, except for the graphic designer, during almost all the protocol fragments of the participants were found to have segments that satisfactorily conformed to the model ([Table 12](#)).

However, two types of particular segments motivate to make a contrast of the write protocols with the video registers. The first one is called in studies of protocols as deviations and implies the abrupt change of the participant behavior. The second one initially was considered to record losses incomplete segments as they did not present the complete flow of all the categories in the segments that compose iterations. Thus, it was assumed to be an error in transcription, so a detailed examination of the recordings corresponding to the segments was conducted.

It was necessary to combine behavioral observation based on the register action protocols. This is another method that is often used in protocol analysis, but it does not include the procedure of thinking aloud in its study. It is usually used to create a flowchart to provide a reference method for process-oriented analysis. Since they consist in studying the physical movements to relate them to the model, then it could also be useful to validate the correspondence between the thoughts and the behavior.

Thanks to this procedure, the deviations were verified as thoughts that in the middle of the model flow start to focus on other aspects not related to the specific operation to the point that eventually the flow stops, and the specific operation is lost. It could be associated with an event where the person is distracted, but not from their overall task or even action, instead is a “micro” distraction placed in the current segment ([Table 14](#)).

In reviewing the records, it was found that not only was the original thought trace lost, but also the performance was interrupted, and the participant usually

ended up with another, new activity related to the thought that had entered the original flow. Since the cycle was not complete and had to be restarted, this is considered an unsuccessful use of the design ability. These cases are not used to contrast the presence of the study variables in the samples. However, they are useful for understanding the difference in incidence and fluency of the model.

The deviation cases could be related to the level of concentration on the task, but also to the development of the design ability. The unit of analysis where most of the segments deviated were identified from a high margin was the project manager, the participant who mentioned that performed the task with lowest frequency. It was clear that many of the situations were triggered or could be considered distractions, as thoughts went to issues that had almost nothing to do with what was going on. However, this disruption is usually immediately followed by a new ideal segment.

Almost no deviations were found in the rest of participants, especially in the graphic designer with zero cases. On the contrary, in this unit the second type of segment mentioned above was very frequent. This type of situation, which consists of the absence of an element corresponding to a category of the model, is like the deviation, but at the same time it is very different from it. They also consist in the arise of thoughts that have not direct relation with the operation performed and usually occupy the place that should correspond to one category, but the difference is that the rest of the model is complete, as if were not a disruption ([Table 15](#)).

The major difference resides there, after revising the video registers, was verified that the operation was not interrupted. On the contrary, the appearance of these foreign thoughts did not affect the behavior that was expected based on the original thoughts corresponding to the model. Moreover, the most obvious missing element of the model was usually the last one, from the “represent” category. For this reason, it was easy to notice that the cognitive process was not stopped and continued under the layer of the unrelated thought.

This evidence of cognitive layers resembles the ability of a device to multitask and was therefore so named. For the project manager, there was no observation

of this type of segment and for the financial advisor, it was very low. In contrast, both designers present a reasonable amount, but in the case of the graphic designer, there is a significant high proportion as in the deviation frequency of the project manager. It is worth mentioning that it is very unlikely the difference in the two types of segments in the participants was caused by the complexity or span of intrusive thoughts. This is because the multitasking thoughts were of longer duration and more detailed.

The most likely reason explaining the difference between the different outcomes could be a different type of design ability “use” in the task. If it were only the level of design ability, the big difference between the designers could not be justified (as both have a similar development). Thus, is highly probable related to the implementation of the ability in the specific task, since the graphic designer is used to work with two-dimensional projects and, as the advertising designer stated, a presentation is equivalent to other types of products from its expertise such as posters, brochures, or advertisements.

In relation to this, the graphic designer also works as a specialist in digital advertising, and the last point that supports this proposal is based on the results of the participants. Although the author does not pretend to compare the quality of the work done by the participants, the performance of the graphic designer and the final result was clearly superior. Thus, although he worked with different cognitive “sublayers of cognition”, the quality of his work did not decrease, indicating some superior control of his ability.

In addition to these two situations, an unexpected situation was also found during the behavioral observation. This consisted of an incongruence between what one participant announced during his procedure of think aloud and what was done in the real world. More specifically, this means that while their thoughts correspond to a category, at the same moment the events in the video correspond to what should be associated with the following category. Consequently, it seems to be a delay of thoughts or a forward behavior ([Table 13](#)).

These shifts always occur between the "project" thoughts and the "represent" behavior and may influence all subsequent iterations. Evidence of these segments was present in a large number of the project managers' episodes and

was initially associated with the suggestion that the thoughts were so brief as to allow for an overlap that could look almost simultaneous. However, after examining the participant's behavior in other episodes with similar actions but with ideal segments, it was found that this was not the case. Moreover, the presence of this situation "misalignment" is often accompanied by errors or multiple corrections over the same aspects.

Finally, after evaluating this evidence and some similar cases in all other samples, it was concluded that this situation corresponds to a kind of improvisation in the task. The application of trial and error without having an idea of the outcome but based on prior knowledge and expecting the best. Later, this assumption was confirmed in the third phase through the indirect questioning of specific episodes about their thoughts. These misalignments cases were also not included in the contrasting of the presence of the design ability, because although they represent a successful "oral" flow of the model, the incongruence with the behavior detracts from their presence in the "specific task".

This is a good reminder that the presence of the model is not synonymous with the existence of the design ability. If this were the case, the model of creative reasoning would have to be called the model of design ability. However, this is not the case, because in addition to the model, another condition must be fulfilled, namely the application in a "specific task". If misalignment occurs, the cognitive process is out of sync with reality and therefore will not be applied to the task. Probably there are other process levels working simultaneously and the model could be applied in one of them as "imagination".

So, it is good to remember that the model of creative reasoning may also be present in other types of abilities, some of which may also fall within the cognitive domain. This is certainly a complex topic that cannot be reviewed in this document and will be closed here. Nonetheless, the discharge of the protocol with the deviations and misalignments will not significantly affect the samples, with the exception of the project manager, which will be taken into account in the comparison of the units and would not affect the overall conclusion for non-design professionals.

The following tables decompose a reference set into the categories of the model and present the behavior concurrently as the thought takes place. Although the model is achieved by with the first three columns of color, two more were added because it was found that the last segments of an action or operation isolated from an episode are usually composed in this way. This will be analyzed in detail in the following section on the cases of the non-design professionals, since the most obvious situations are presented there.

The first diagram shows an ideal segment ([Table 12](#)) where the register of think aloud corresponds to what was observed in the video. It is worth mentioning that the participant who came closest to this situation in all his operations was the financial consultant. On the other hand, the cases of misalignment ([Table 13](#)) and deviation ([Table 14](#)) were almost exclusively related to the project manager. The last chart ([Table 15](#)), related to the multitasking situations, was exceptionally frequently observed in the graphic designer.

Coded protocol situations

Table 12. Ideal segment / operation

CATEGORY	Perceive	Project	Represent	Perceive	Project
THOUGHT	I don't like this gray	I could use other color	I am changing it to green	Let's see	Yeah, now is ok
BEHAVIOR	Observe a detail	Small pause	Proceed to change it	Observe the change	Move cursor away

Table 13. Misalignment / improvisation

CATEGORY	Perceive	Project	Represent	Perceive	Project
THOUGHT	I don't like this gray	I could use other color	I am changing it to green	Let's see	No, It doesn't fit
BEHAVIOR	Observe a detail	Proceed to change it	Observe the change	PAUSE OF ERROR	Proceed to change it

Table 14. Deviation / distraction

CATEGORY	Perceive	Project	Perceive	Project	Represent
THOUGHT	I don't like this gray	I could use other color and maybe I will used it in other presentation	I don't like the font	I could use Arial	I am changing it to it.
BEHAVIOR	Observe a detail	Pause of distraction	Identify a need	Imagine the change	Proceed to change it

Table 15. Multitasking / expertise

CATEGORY	Perceive	Project	Represent	Perceive	Project
THOUGHT	I don't like this gray	I could use other color	and maybe I will used it in other presentation	Let's see	Yeah, now is ok
BEHAVIOR	Observe a detail	Small pause	Proceed to change it	Observe the change	Move cursor away

After identifying all the segments in the fragments of the protocols created by the temporal division, the segments that are directly related to a particular action are grouped as episodes. As expected, most of the operations were directly associated to each other. These data clusters were put into a special table format ([Table 17](#), [Table 18](#)) that allows for more effective comparison and analysis. Real examples of these charts can be found in the following subsections. The components of the protocols ([Table 16](#)) used by them can be seen below with a description.

Table 16. Protocol chart layout

Tempo	The range of time from the original record.
Reference	Selected from the start of the tempo.
Cycles	The quantity of cycles that complete the model in all the episode.
Protocol	The transcription of the thoughts with the internal classification of the segments based in colors that correspond to the category of the model.
Action	A verb that summarizes/describes the episode that takes place.
Operations	A list of words that summarizes/describes each segment grouped.
Thoughts	A reference of the thought types presented in the episode, verbal for that type, (non-verbal) they will be included in parenthesis in the protocol aloud, and mixed means a segment that has both previous types and can be noticed because have some part of color in parentheses.

15.4 Professional designers' cases

The results from this group were intended to serve as a reference for a nurtured design ability and to facilitate the identification of the creative reasoning model in the other group. As might be expected, the model emerged naturally from the units. While each participant has relevant characteristics that will be explored in the "Result contrasting" chapter, instead there was a common aspect that will be consolidated in this section.

For this analysis, the aforementioned episode charts were prepared ([Table 17](#)). They were used to identify commonalities between the two participants in each group. As mentioned earlier, the graphic designer protocol, which was originally fragmented in time, does not show the presence of the model in all parts. However, after compiling the segments into episodes based on the actions, all sections of the protocol contain at least one ideal segment. This was also the case for all other protocols, but in their case the result was predicted due to the large number of ideal cases.

The total length of the task protocol in this group for both participants was forty-nine minutes, and the graphic designers took six minutes longer. The number of slices was similar, but the tools used were different; the industrial designer used PowerPoint software, while the graphic designer used Illustrator software. They employed images of their previous files and the industrial designer had to use Google to consult a client's information to use as a reference. They show no discomfort during the think aloud process, although the industrial designer fell silent at three moments, in one of which it was necessary to ask him twice to "keep talking."

The differences in the tools used lead to a contrast in the order of the episodes, their duration, and the common presence of some actions. However, they have a consistency on the presence of the creative reasoning in all episodes. This means that the design ability is present in all the tasks, with the model usually being condensed into segments of a unique thought (sentence) corresponding to all the categories. The operations are usually completed in more than one cycle, but usually only one of them is an ideal segment. Their actions are

composed for a large number of operations, so iteration of the model in the episodes was common without exceptions.

These iterations were intense and fast, even though there were almost no cases of misalignment. On the contrary, especially in the case of the graphic designer, the presence of multitasking was high and constant in all episodes. This participant always displayed infiltrator thoughts that appear in the superior layer of cognition are related to the use of the presentation, especially the way it will be explained to the audience. These thoughts were very complex and created an overall context that sometimes included the participants' dialogue. Furthermore, this was used to orient the structure of the presentation and the type of elements included in the slices.

The author believes that these constant thoughts about the goal to be achieved by the presentation represent an “intentionality” of design that is made explicit in connection with the use of the design ability. This makes sense in the context of the general theory of competencies that define the use of abilities and willingness. Unfortunately, this cannot be confirmed with certainty and further research is required. Intentionality in design is an area of research that is gaining new momentum in this new century, but it is clear that it is not synonymous with design ability and is not the aim of the present research. The analysis of this aspect requires the development of a different framework that focuses on it.

However, when analyzing the segments, it was found that this thought, which is associated with potential intentionality, usually occurs in the place corresponding to the category "represent". As explained in the case of multitasking, they do not interfere with the behavior of operations, so it can be assumed that the original thought corresponding to the model exists in a subordinate layer of consciousness. Moreover, due to the nature of the data that should be used (the commands of the tool to materialize the mental image), the author suspects that the thoughts on this sublayer are nonverbal.

For this reason, in many episodes where the model is evident, there are some cycles or segments with a mixture of nonverbal and verbal thoughts, making it difficult to identify some categories without following the behavior with the video confirming that the category "project" was translated to the next category

“represent”. This was not the case for all episodes, in particular for the industrial designer, but some of the most common ones where this multitasking appeared were during editing, operations related to images such as inserting, scaling, moving, or aligning.

It was also noted that when looking at a section, the participant would pause a little between thoughts and the cursor would slowly move around the elements, but without a specific destination. On the contrary, when they announce something about the category "project", the movement of the cursor is still slack, but they take on more coherence and velocity and start to aim at the tools they are going to use. It is possible that when they begin to send the command to display, they remember previous experiences and their memory acts as the thought of the command.

This could be the main reason why there is a notorious absence of verbal thoughts related to certain aesthetic operations. As a result of what was identified, the extent and detail are much less than those of the non-design professionals. Probably because of their experience, as in the case of the multitasking segments, they are more economical with their verbal thoughts and even the instructions could be visual. This was explored in the third phase by examining the thoughts that the participants have in the specific moments, but also with an isolated exercise inspired by the operation in which these situations take place.

In general, the work of the designers was very fluid, some aspects that the author did not expect were the amount and variety of textual content, moreover, the speed and spontaneity to write paragraphs was almost immediate without an obvious reflection, but without errors to be changed later. This was also the case for the non-design professionals. In the discussion with the assessors, mastery and experience with the subject was suggested as an explanation for this situation. Since it was about what they do in their fields, it was natural that the knowledge of the participants was very high and allowed this level of performance.

Table 17. Chart composed with two equivalent episodes of the designer's protocol. The colors in the protocol aloud correspond to the categories of the creative reasoning model. (Cesar Yachi, 2023)

* Some actions end their cycle with a clear verbal affirmation, which implies that they contrasted what has been done with their ideal expectations. These thoughts are placed in the projection category and were confirmed by the non-design professionals.

Unit of analysis	Tempo range	Reference image	Model cycles	Protocol aloud	Action protocol	Operations Observed	Thoughts V/NV
Graphic designer	22:30 – 23:25		X4	... Why 3c because they come in groups of 3 in 13 rows This from here (comparing) (copy paste) aligned, just that*, this one the Tablet, (comparing) (copy paste) scaled, aligned, there almost aligned*, that way the web is filled, easy. After that...	Exemplify	Examine Define Copy Paste Scale Align	Verbal (non-verbal) Mixed
Industrial designer	24:20 – 24:50		X4	Metal, in metal we can put this 3M Backside and some big element (open his file) like this bag hanger, we will put this 3M (copy paste, scaled, aligned), (observe) we will put the Plax ice here (copy paste, scaled, aligned) (observe) and will put this bag hanger (copy paste, scaled, aligned), (observe) I don't remember the brand, I think is called Binnies...	Exemplify	Examine Define Copy Paste Scale Align	Verbal (non-verbal)

To conclude this section, it should be mentioned that the answers to the questions related to design and its ability were as expected. In the first question, the industrial designer explained design as a solution process and the graphic designer as the transformation of ideas into reality. When defining the term "ability", the former mentioned the use of resources such as tools and personnel, while the latter meant the combination of aesthetic and technical knowledge.

In the third question, both participants fully affirm that they perform a design task based on their interpretation of design. Similarly, they feel that they have used design ability, but surprisingly, they feel that their use was limited to a specific part of their work and not in a high "quantity" in the case of the graphic designer when using "design" knowledge of composition, and the industrial designer in the operations strongly related to the appearance of the presentation.

Thus, the samples show a broader understanding of design when they think about it without a practical example, probably because their thoughts are more

abstract. After solving the task, they relate design directly to their product and limit their understanding to the more tangible, in this case aesthetic aspects. These data are contrasted in the third phase with their opinion about the existence of design ability in non-design professionals and the use of an isolated case of operations, where the "represent" category of the model is less significant than the other two.

15.5 Non-design professionals' cases

In the case of this group, their results are the main reason for the fieldwork, and it was assumed that it would be difficult to detect the presence of the creative reasoning model. However, this was not the case, because the manifestation of the cycles was as frequent as in the protocols of the designers. Moreover, the study unit with the most ideal segments belongs to this section. The financial consultant can be considered an ideal example because his protocol has the least number of special segments (deviations, multitasking, or misalignments) and the think aloud process has the most continuous cycles, with some of these iterations making up the totality of the different episodes.

It is true that the project manager also has a high presence of ideal segments, and a simple observation will be more than that of the financial consultant, but a large part of them was overridden after comparison with the recording video and classified as misalignment. Even taking this into account, this population has the highest rate of ideal segments in terms of number of episodes. Thus, their cognitive processes were more explicit and verbal, which allows testing the presence of the model. The results show a high presence and functionality, indicating a clear presence of the design ability in their task.

When looking for similarities between these samples, the same structure chart was used as in the previous case ([Table 18](#)). The difference in both protocols was significant in the extension, as the financial consultant took almost half the time than the project manager. The project manager needed five minutes more than the set time for the rest of analysis units because the interviewer felt that the participant needed this time to complete his presentation with a

satisfactory perception. As mentioned earlier, this research does not purport to compare the performance of the work performed by the units of analysis, so this additional time does not significantly affect the variable of the study.

The total length of the task protocol for this group was fifty-four minutes, five minutes more than for the designers. This finding is not to establish a difference, but to note that both groups registered a very similar amount of time of data to analyze. Both participants used PowerPoint and the scope of their presentations was similar. They open previous files to support their work, the financial consultant to use a template and the project manager to use an image. Finally, their browser was also used with different objectives, the financial consultant to extract images and the project manager to look for a translator. The latter also used Excel to extract a table and insert a chart into a section.

Unit of analysis	Tempo range	Reference image	Model cycles	Protocol aloud	Action protocol	Operations Observed	Thoughts V/NV
Financial consultant	12:45 – 13:50		x6	So first I take a look to my template and think the best one for this maybe this one (comparing) as a starting page (passed slice) Ta ta ta delete. I don't need the other slice and agenda; I only need content slice (he deleted it). For example, just a normal slice (passed slice) I don need this and Maybe this as well (he deleted it) I don't like the color grading. Yeah, maybe I can delete this (he deleted it) and also delete this and keep this (passed slice) I don't need this, I don like the star design I'll delete it, keep deleting.	Diagraming	Examine Define Select Delete	Verbal (non-verbal) Mixed
Project management	21:40 – 22:35		x3	The background so this is white again, here white and maybe I should put it on the color of our logo (change color) its better and for having it is more modern, I would put like one little line but yellow (she do it and scale it) so should look more officially like something I will do every day, but I am not doing, maybe here is better (move the line)	Diagraming	Examine Define Change color Insert Scale Move	Verbal (non-verbal)

Table 18. Chart composed with two equivalent episodes of the non-design professionals' protocol. The colors in the protocol aloud correspond to the categories of the creative reasoning model. (Cesar Yachi, 2023)

Participants did not show any discomfort during the think aloud procedure, although the intervention to ask to "keep talking" was significantly higher for this group. They did so immediately after the signal. A notable exception is the difficulty the project manager has in trying to put a clustered column into a

slice. The first attempt failed, and it suddenly went silent. After several unsuccessful corrections and sporadic silences, it was noted that the participant's humor deteriorated until the participant was able to fix the problem using Excel. This event was particularly useful as it helped to understand how a mental image that did not match what was expected caused a momentary but obvious pause in their overall process.

This helps to notice something that was suspected in the analysis of the designers' protocols. The entire flow of the model could go through the entire cycle and revisit the "perceive" and "project" category. This means that after using the representation of the idea, the ability is still working to validate what has been created by comparing what is perceived as the result of the materialization with what was expected in the mental image. This comparison is part of the "project" category, as the mental idea is used to overlay both data and decide if the result is okay or if further work should be done on it.

During the protocols, the two cases were common and easy to identify. The first case, which consisted of accepting the result either because what is perceived match or because the original idea was transformed with the input, ended with an exclamation of affirmation. This could be a "good", "yes" or something more elaborate, such as "that way is okay" or "this is fine". In the second case, when the idea and the perception do not match, the cycle of the model is usually continued with less verbal thought but fixed in the same operation. It was curious that when this mismatch is too unexpected, another kind of exclamation with negative connotation may appear, as in the case of the clustered column, where the participant probably involuntarily exclaimed "oh shit".

Another curious comment that emerged during the protocols from both participants was their "disregard" for "design matters." While conducting the activity, they occasionally mentioned that they did not focus on aesthetic aspects such as composition, shapes, colors, etc. They referred to these elements as the "design" of the presentation and focused on the "content." It was very interesting to hear these comments because when asked at the beginning of the task about design and its ability, one participant replied, "*design is to be creative to present normal things in a creative way thinking*"

about the experience" while another participant said that the ability had to do with "creativity" but was not limited to aesthetics.

Although their direct answer was beyond aesthetic aspects, in practice and perhaps unconsciously, they cannot disassociate design with aesthetics, or the action related to the "represent" category of proposals. But even in this case, they did not consider their own practice related to "aesthetics" as design, because after mention the comments of the previous paragraph, they perform operations related to it and the model was explicitly presented in their think aloud procedure. Therefore, when they finished the task, the following questionnaire yielded interesting results.

When asked if what they did implied design ability, both agreed that they used them to some extent. One mentioned that this was the case while adjusting the appearance of the presentation; and the other surprisingly answered: "*when I think in how place information or make it more illustrated, or the more logical way to put the information.*". So, they could also think about their own use of the design ability after reflecting on their practice, but apparently not while they were using them. Moreover, this reflection is limited to the physical results, in this case aspects of aesthetics, which manifest themselves thanks to the category "represent".

In answering the question of whether what they are doing is a design task, they feel that it is in part, but not because it is related to their original definition of design or the broad understanding of the ability from the paragraph above. Instead, they believe that there are aesthetic aspects to presentation that cannot be omitted. They emphasize that the aesthetic aspects of presentation can be done better by designers and paid no attention to them. Ironically, from an aesthetic point of view, their results were better than those of the industrial designer, who incidentally uses the same tool, and not so inferior to the look of the graphic designer.

Both participants used PowerPoint, although the method was very different, as one started from scratch and the other with a template. Although there are many similarities, one of them was that they both initially decided on a series of slices that had to be deleted at the end due to time constraints. This suggests that they have an original idea that needs to be adjusted due to conditions. A

likely explanation for this mental image is the behavior of the designers and the financial consultant who went through the presentation linearly without returning to the previous slices, while the project manager kept returning to the previous slices to modify them frequently.

The consistency of the mental image proposed in this group was not clearly expressed in the procedure of the think aloud, except in certain episodes related to the “aesthetics” of the slices, such as edition and exemplification (placing an element that works as an example). In other cases, the effects seem to be particularly marked when the utterances are linked to subjective evaluations, such as catchy, cool, or modern. It is possible that, like nonverbal thoughts, it operates at an inferior cognitive layer, much as in the multitasking cases.

Returning to the cases, the behavior observed based on the studies of the deviations helps to notice the same patterns as in the designer group. When the segments present the ideal models, the register of the participant's screen cursor shows different rates of speed and precision depending on the category associated with it. The difference with the previous group is that most of the thoughts associated with the “perceive” category are subjective with judgments of their perceptions, while the “represent” category are more detailed or descriptive of what is being performed.

A tentative answer to this could be the need for confirmation of their actions due to a lack of confidence in their "aesthetic" decisions. One thing in favor of this is that the parts that correspond to the category "project" are often formulated as a question instead of a future explanation. This means that instead of saying "I will make this of color blue", they say "*maybe I could make this of color blue?*" These could also be related to their capacity to form the mental image, assumptions that will be explored in the third phase with questionnaires and some sections of their retrospective analysis.

16 THIRD STAGE

This part of the study was initially intended as an opportunity to share the model with the participants to get their views. However, after identifying the variety of situations for the segments and the assumptions for the model, it was decided to extend it as an introspective analysis with three groups of objectives: the presence of inconsistencies in the questionnaires, the use of nonverbal thoughts in the segments and exploring their indirect opinion about the model without showing it.

This first group refers to the response to the inconsistencies between the first and second interviews of the non-design professionals. As revised, they initially stated that they had no design ability or knowledge, but later, immediately after the task was performed, they mentioned using the ability. So, in the end it was not clear whether they felt they had the ability or not.

Another contradiction was that they fixated on design practice as an aesthetic matter, while interpreting design ability more broadly. It will be valuable to deepen their understanding and the relationship between the two terms. This will help to place an indirect perception of the model and adding the results of the professional designers can help to evaluate the hypothesis.

The second group tests the inferences made about the different situations of the model presented in the segments. Not about deviance, as these cases are supported by evidence of their behavior and the think aloud; instead about multitasking and misalignment, as both are highly associated with the presence or absence of a mental image respectively.

Fortunately, almost all cases in the four study units were presented in different types of episodes, so variable and heterogeneous data dealing with the same derivations could be valuable evidence for the validity of the statements. It is also assumed that this is part of the straightforward workflow of all participants except the project manager, and although in very few instances, it could also be associated with some repetitive processes among the others.

This is valuable data to evaluate the proposal. To achieve this, the assumption about the layer of cognition, including one of nonverbal thought is considered from two fronts. On the one hand, retrospective studies of the episodes are conducted with the participants. On the other hand, an operation is carried out on the segments, in which the mental image plays a key role, to investigate how the model works.

Finally, the last group is asked for their indirect opinion about the model, which can also be done by practicing the isolate operation. In addition to the condition of high use of the mental image from the previous paragraph, it is considered that the category "represent" must reduce its weight to prevent the inherence of "aesthetics".

The best match was selected from the operations observed in the tasks. They were presented in the action of exemplify. Based on this reference, some quick tests are elaborated to be used in the instrument with different degrees of variation of the categories to see which ones are recognized by the participants as valid models of design practice ergo with design ability presence.

16.1 Retrospective protocol

In this stage, the data obtained through the register of the "concurrent protocol" analysis are combined with a "retrospective protocol." This is a "report after the completion of task" (Someren et al., 1994). With this method it is possible to re-examine certain aspects of the task with the participants; and usually these studies are divided into two subcategories: "retrospective" and "introspective". Both are based on the long-term memory of the performer and refer to the previously completed task.

The first category, the retrospective, is usually the detailed description of what the participant did. It is created with the aim of obtaining the most accurate perspective possible, which allows the smallest details of an activity to be identified. It is good to know that this description is usually based on the perceptions of the performer and, therefore, it is strongly related to the physical

world and psychomotor areas. Therefore, it was usually used to study the method and its components.

In contrast, the second type, the introspective, seeks explanations for the behavior of the actors and explores the rationality behind it. This investigation is particularly useful for the present study, in which several conclusions and some conjectures have been made through the analysis of the four cases. To support them, the behavior of the most representative events is traced with the protagonist. Immediately after, indirect questions are asked that can be related to the conclusions without telling the participants what is aimed to be confirmed.

As can be seen, both types are basically explorations of the protocol from the practitioner's perspective, although they are not considered with the same rigor as the other data types. For this reason, they are not used alone in a study. It is always assumed that " humans are just inclined to reconstruct events as more structured than they were originally. Their memory is guided by their knowledge of the result" (Someren et al., 1994). However, if the expected responses and inferences are not obvious to the unit of analysis, it might be useful to explore the conjecture with them.

16.2 Instrument third stage

The next week after the second phase, a new interview was conducted. Similar to the previous one, a guide was created, but only for the interviewer ([Appendix IV](#)). A presentation was also created and shared with the participants on the same day to guide the different sections ([Appendix V](#)). This consisted of the exercises (called simulated situation [I](#), [II](#), [III](#)), their respective questionnaires, and then the introspective analysis, which was concluded with a personalized and general questionnaire.

The session lasts about forty-five minutes, the simulation with the questionnaires about ten minutes, the introspection thirty minutes, and the last questionnaires about five minutes. Only the questionnaires after / and the

retrospective protocol were different for each participant and contained five questions based on the data from the second interview. The instrument used was Zoom as in the previous phases and the interviews were also recorded so that all information was reviewed in detail after the interview was completed.

The simulation situation was so called because it was based on an assumed context that was part of an exemplify action, which, as previously described, consisted of "place an element that works as an example." This means that a person chooses something that corresponds to what they have in mind. It is good to know that there is no implication of how the selected element came to exist. It could be a product of their own authorship or another being, which is not even necessarily made for other people, consider that even a rock or a cloud could be used to exemplify.

Exemplifying can be done in different types of tasks with different skills and abilities, but in the case of presentation, it shows up when images are chosen as examples of content. It is important to remember that the exemplifying episode might be close but does not involve creating what is selected. For example, if someone wants to explain something with a sketch, drawing is done first and corresponds to other episode/action, then it is evaluated if what was done is useful to the explanation. This evaluation is part of exemplify.

Looking at this example, one might think that exemplify can be an action that is done very quickly, so that it seems intuitive and consists of only one operation, and there might be episodes where this is the case. However, when analyzing the protocol of the previous phase, it was found that it is a continual action, usually consisting of iterations of ideal segments in which the creative reasoning model comes into play. Thus, to study this situation, it is broken down into a test that can be performed in a single operation. Basically, a simulated situation in which the cognitive process consists of only one cycle of the model.

In this case, the particular advantage of choosing the exemplify action takes relevance, the category "represent" usually is very limited in terms of physical manifestations. As can be seen in the results of the second phase, design practice and ability, even among designers, are usually directly and exclusively associated with activities related to aesthetics in the transformation of matter.

In this sense, exemplify lacks leadership in this category, to the point that in a shallow examination some cases seem to present the model incomplete in that area.

Nevertheless, it is important to remember that not all elements of the "represent" group are necessarily associated with reality migration. It is true that design ability has a context in which there is a requirement that reality needs to be changed, and the natural response is to manifest some kind of representation in the external world. However, this does not mean that the process of "make a fair copy," the vulgar definition of "represent," must be identical to the creation of the proposal in the external world.

For example: *“Imagine a person that due to an accident in his major adulthood cannot move any part of his body. He cannot speak but at least can hear and see. Also, suppose that our technology has gone as far as allows us to create some kind of peripheral between the brain of that person to a printer. Thus, he can print exactly what he is thinking, could be text or images and when he decides to do it. This printer is a little far from him, close to the doctors and that is how they know that he is fully rational, and conversations can be made. The person cannot see what is being printed until finished but at least could hear the machine working.”*

Let us pause the narrative for a moment to analyze how the process might work. If the person is going to send something to print, he must have a clear "mental image" of it. This means that he should not continue to work on what is to be printed when he sends it off. He must decide that what he has done is finished and hold the final idea before he sends it to the printer. This fixed thought of what has been decided falls into the category of "represent" and as can be "observed", does not require a physical manifestation or a tool to be completed, but uses the capabilities of memory and the knowledge acquired through the previous processing of the idea.

Now, *“imagine that this person was a designer with decades of experience, a colleague from their work comes and tells him that they have a big problem as they could not find any with his competence to fill his position, but they need to develop a work (maybe a poster, some furniture, a dress, etc.). So, they go to visit them and ask them for some advice, some ideas to help the teamwork*

(a draft layout, dihedral views, a clothe sketch, etc.). The visitant explains that knows the designer cannot do his best, but he will be very helpful to give them some reference for the new worker in his place. The designer accepted and decided to do it and the printer produced one page.”

Let us analyze this again using the model of creative reasoning: First, the person hears the request, which belongs to the category "perceive". When he decides to make something and develop an idea, the cognitive process is assigned to the category "project". It is important to remember that even if it is not a new idea, but basically a complete repetition of a previous one, it is still part of the projection because it requires an evaluation of its relevance to the context, which at least requires some adaptation, and it is this activity that is the basis of projection. Finally, when all thoughts come to rest again and the decisions are made, the final "mental image" of the category "represent" takes place.

So, ideally, the model takes place in the presented situation, which, by the way, can be classified as a kind of "specific task", previously described as an activity to materialize a medium to achieve a desired change in a situation. The change is the satisfaction of the colleague and the medium used to achieve it is the printed page. Given these two aspects (task and model), there is no question that the design ability is being used in a context that could be classified as design practice.

It is interesting to note that the case of this “quadriplegic designer” with limited senses and feedback is the same as that of a machine executing a design ability or a more explicit AI image generator. This is the point the author finds most interesting in this paper, the most controversial, and perhaps the most debatable. If an AI were capable of a creative reasoning model that considered the basic elements as a prompt, the search and modification, and the end result as each part of the categories, then it would be like the person described in the example.

This document does not want to interfere with this discussion, but only to share an unexpected observation and will not go further. So, to return to the topic at hand: The idea of the simulation was to construct a case where the design ability is present in a very basic and to some degree obvious way. This was

inspired by the process of exemplifying and the limited number of factors that can be used to explore the opinion about the model and their conclusions in the hypothesis. Therefore, it was decided to use them as part of the third instrument.

It was assumed that this simulated situation would be useful to introduce the units of analysis of the model without directly explaining what they consist of. However, before we used it with them, it was tested with other designers of the first phase to evaluate its functionality. Of course, we cannot repeat the experiment because we do not have the necessary technology yet. But in the meantime, it could at least be simulated. So, this narrative was created for a graphic, industrial and textile designer, with the necessary modifications in the kind of reference needed (*a draft layout, dihedral views, a clothe sketch*).

The results were very interesting. All participants stated that they were able to solve the design task, but with many limitations that were directly related to the quality of their work. In addition, they did not feel that they had done any design practice initially. When asked why, they responded that what they were doing was part of the design process, but not a design practice per se, and that they would have had to do other things to get the proposal finished instead of doing a draft.

When it was pointed out to them that what was required was a draft, they thought about it for a moment and then acknowledged that what had been done is design. Nevertheless, they all felt that it would be better if they could see and compare multiple drafts at the same time. This makes evident they consider the design task as a performance strongly related to the development through comparison of proposals. Another important conclusion from this exercise was that professional designers seem to consider design practice as the presence of a complete method rather than the use of ability.

With this information, the first section of the instrument was developed, but with significant changes. First, the "context" was changed to be more familiar to non-designers. The colleague was replaced by a daughter and the task was changed to a simpler idea of an illustration. Second, the simulation is translated into three case types, each with a greater frequency in each category of the

model, and for each there is a questionnaire with similar questions related to if is considering design practices and the use of design ability.

The first case focuses on the perceiving category (Fig. 14) and sets the stage for the example activity, which involves selecting an alternative for a mental image. The exercise begins by giving the participant a description of a dragon. The typology is intentionally set to facilitate the quick construction of a reference, but not constrained by a fixed fact of reality. It is also an ideal starting point where they need to modify their thoughts with the incoming data that needs to be translated to fit that original idea.

The reason the description is verbal and said only once is to force the participant to focus on the mental without being distracted by lower levels or thoughts such as reflection on the exercise or the data provided. It also boosts the listening skill and makes the meaning of what is being heard. After completing this description and receiving confirmation that they have a clear mental image, they are asked to describe their idea and select the closest image from a group. With this "physical product," they are asked about the connection between the process and the design ability and practice.

Fig 14. Representation of the model for the simulation case 1 of the third stage instrument. The incidence on interpretation of the description makes the priority over the creation of the mental image and the selection of an image. (Cesar Yachi, 2023)

It is important to note that when participants hear the description, they interpret the data in the "perceived" category. They must match what they hear with what they imagine and for this reason translate the sound into an in-depth vision. The result is what can be called "contextual knowledge," a blend of what they hear and the prior data they have from experience. For example, if they hear "big fangs," they might remember an animal with those characteristics and retain that aspect to work with.

However, due to the limitation of short-term memory, there is a possibility that these elements will be immediately incorporated into the construction of the idea that corresponds to the category of "project," which could be similar to a process of fitting, matching, and even composing, as in "collage" and "rasterization." When these elements are fixed to create a clearer image, as in a "rendering," this corresponds to the category of "represent." If this happens, it is a continuous process on a micro scale, and it is important to be slow and make short pauses in the description until it is completed.

Another important detail to consider is the images used for the selection pool. Each of them is a valid option based on the description, but each has a special feature that is relevant and stands out from the others. Thus, none of the images has all the characteristics described, but the selection is expected to be based on the most important ones that were considered when building the mental image with the information provided. At the same time, these parts are used as support when explaining why they selected a particular image.

To avoid using the memorization of features as a list, some features that are easier to "memorize" are included in the three images to omit their use in the comparison of the mental image, such as the color, the type of limbs, or the presence of claws and wings. And some special features not mentioned are added to mislead the attention and explore how far their imagination can go in the projection.

The second case ([Fig. 15](#)) is most similar to the case of the tetraplegic designer. In this case, the narrative is about the context and the daughter's request is to design a unicorn with a background. There is no more input than that, so the category of "perceive" is very limited, and likewise the print work is not significant and serves as an excuse to consider the materialization of the idea.

Although the latter carries a bit more weight due to the requirement to fix the final proposal. Instead, the "project" category is the most significant because it emphasizes the construction of a clear mental image, which is required to be very detailed as some questions are asked in relation to it.

Fig 15. Representation of the model for the simulation case 2 of the third stage instrument. The incidence on the creation of the idea takes the priority over the almost null perception and the fixation of an image to be printed.
(Cesar Yachi, 2023)

The third case (Fig. 16) was significantly modified after being used in some units of analysis. Originally, it was considered part of the second case, with additional conditions added after the second survey was completed. However, it was determined that the significant differences in the results warranted treatment as a third case. Therefore, the survey was refined, and although it is still based on the second case, the weight in the categories has changed in all cases, so it is much higher in the "represent" category.

With this changes, the participant were asked to "print" a new image. But it changes from being asked to make a variation of the original illustration to replace the unicorn with a specific image provided and placed in the background previously imagined, which was added as a requirement in the second case. In this way, the "perceive" aspect is even more important than the "project", because the mental image is already made, and the minimal work required in this category is to replace it with another image that is also ready. They give the highest priority to the "rendering" of the final product, which corresponds to the representation.

Fig 16. Representation of the model for the simulation case 3 of the third stage instrument. The incidence on “represent” of the mental image is higher than the perception of the reference image and the “swap” made to construct the final idea. (Cesar Yachi, 2023)

Finally, the retrospective protocol (classified as introspective) reviewed five episodes per participant. The procedure consisted of observing a section of the video in which an action is performed, usually lasting about a minute or two, and then answering the related questions. However, after experience with some examples, it was decided not to let the video play completely, but to pause it at the moment when the case being studied was more significant in the event. And after their answer the video continue in case is need it for another question related to the same episode.

This change proved to be a good practice, as the participants were more focused and better able to remember the information. The main question usually related to whether they had some kind of mental picture of what they were doing or what they wanted to achieve. Subsequent questions attempted to confirm and explore their answers. Some of these related to describing what they envisioned, and others related to whether what they expected was consistent with their results. Since they were not shown the video of the full episodes, these answers could be partially validated based in the congruence with their next actions or operations.

In general, there was no discomfort at this stage and the respondents showed their interest in learning more about the research. Therefore, a next meeting was arranged in the next few weeks, which will be part of the fourth phase.

16.3 Designers' cases

Thanks to the data collected in the third stage the inferences were tested with positive results, the existence of nonverbal thoughts supposed in the cases of multitasking are validated for the performers and their condition to guide the process of work in a continuous flow was also explained. Their answer about the case of exemplification from the second stage corresponded with the proposal transposition of the model. Meanwhile, the results of the simulation cases of the third stage were enlightening to the hypothesis evaluation.

The first common result among designers was the use of nonverbal thought as a frequent part of the multitasking that allowed them to omit some verbal sections in the segments with the ideal manifestation of the model. These types of thoughts are also present as a clear mental image of the layouts before working on them. However, in some operations of selection or choice that compose part of the “exemplify” actions, they did not have a clear mental image, only a rough idea or intuitive requirements.

This has been associated with the use of images from their warehouses where they know that they will find something useful without effort to define what they were looking for. On the contrary, the operations next to them and part of exemplify, like placing or editing, had a clear mental image. Additionally, when they work on new elements or images that are from other sources, their search starts with a clear mental reference, that keeps transforming it with the inputs that they receive.

In the case of the task from the second stage, there were very limited situations when they had to use images from other sources like the internet or the pre-shaped forms of their software, but when presented they made use of detailed ideas that were described as a clear mental image. On the same note, that condition was affirmed when they were diagramming or using the elements in the background, supported by their behaviors. Based on this, and thanks to the questionnaires we can affirm that they were aware of the use of design ability in the aesthetic episodes of the protocol.

Thus, the task and the simulated cases demonstrate that a selection of an image (exemplify) makes use of the model, therefore involves design ability. For case one, which is closer to “exemplify”, The results correspond as was immediately recognized as the use of design ability and practice. It was recognized the creation of an elaborate mental images in a short time based on the limited inputs provided. They choose and describe the dragon with elements that were not mentioned, being part of their own initiative into their models. It was the same situation when asked to describe their unicorn in the second case, although, they were more fixed on the idea of a horse with “supporting elements” like the horn.

Probably for that reason, the second simulated situation was not immediately recognized by the designers until thoughtful reflection. The use of the memory as base for the construction of the unicorn as a mental image started with a horse as was expected, but the professional designers did not perceive that even this data has been transformed to adjust to the context of use, until a brief pause to answer. Therefore, is clear that identify the “project” category impacts drastically in their perception of the design ability.

In the third case, the results were mixed as one of the participants was questioned using the previous cases, in that way was indirectly induced to associate the two previous situations to recognize the use of design ability. Meanwhile, the other designer makes the association positively and without much reflection but was mentioned that if the reference image provided was not from their authorship it would not be considered a design practice.

Returning to the retrospective protocol, they do not associate the complete use of the model in the task but have a high incidence in the “represent” aspects like skills or knowledge describing the thoughts that correspond to that category. Even though they consider that was not the only type of manifestation of design, they intuitively affirm that there are other aspects of the design ability but couldn’t identify them. In the same way, they consider that other types of abilities can be used to make a presentation, and not everyone that makes a presentation is a designer or uses the design ability.

These contrast with the last general questionnaire, when asked if the creation, nurture, or transformation of ideas (of any type) could be considered design

practice and imply the use of design ability they agree. One designer illustrates this with a case when someone wants to buy something for the car like a rim and before doing it imagines how will look, in his opinion that is design and the person use design ability to image the match. For the other, it is when an idea is ready to be shared that could be considered a design, while the process in the mind is the design practice that uses the ability.

Finally, when asked how they believe the non-designer professionals would make their presentations designers considered that maybe the other group could not achieve what they wanted, or at least would be more difficult for them to mix aesthetical aspects and the content, designers affirm that they would be faster because would take decisions more quickly and will work in a more organized way. However, the real inference will not depend on the design formation, instead the experience doing presentations and the knowledge of the topic that are doing will make the difference in a presentation. One of them even affirmed that one designer without experience will be overcome by a “non-designer” if have enough experience.

16.4 Non-designers' cases

Similar to the designers' section, thanks to the retrospective protocol and the simulation cases, the presence of the model was positively tested, and this also includes the presence of nonverbal thoughts in the episodes. They had an idea of the layouts before creating the slices, but there was a particular and interesting difference in the case of the project manager, who instead of the financial consultant and the designers that possess a clear image, was more like a non-verbal list of requirements that work more as an intuition.

This highly supports the supposition to explain why only that participant returned frequently to previous sections to modify, improve, or correct them. As well as the constant presence of misalignment and deviation segments. The presence of a clear mental image orients the workflow and the use of the resources available. It has been identified that while clearer the mental image the higher will be the performance of sample. However, usually this is not

verbalized, and was required an observation and introspective analysis to complement the data from the concurrent protocol.

Also, usually when a mental image was placed, on-design professionals regarded it as “knowledge” based on their memory and experience, an aspect that works as the model, but they do not recognize it as part of the design ability. Instead, they are more angled to consider it as a type of imagination or “know-how.” That was the case in special for the first simulated situation, which even count with a very detailed mental image in both participants, to the point that when they choose the image of reference, they select them based on traits that were not mentioned in the description and even some of them were altered.

That was highly different from the designers that choose their image based on a specific characteristic described by the examiner. So, although both groups use a good amount of creativity is possible that the designers have this one tamed to serve their objectives more precisely while the non-design professionals give them freedom without control. This could explain why the project and specially the “represent” category is substantially more present in verbalization of non-designers.

In the second case of the simulated situations, it was also recognized that the participants have as much creativity as designers. However, the results to the identification of the model were mixed because although the work in both cases was described in high detail, one participant consider that he used design ability at a certain degree, while the other negate the idea because his mental image was purely a previous knowledge with any alteration. It was considered that the image is a memory of a movie or a tv show, so even with the paper printed, it was considered as a performance of imagination, not design ability.

This answer was explored more in detail, asking how can be considered design. The answer was that it requires giving it “more work” and being “out of the head”, this means materialization, thinking in the details, in the background and to who is going to be (the daughter). All these things were explicitly asked for in the instruction and were affirmed to have been done by the participant. It seems this was noticed when answering and finished saying that it should be done not as a referential idea but as trying to make it the best “prettier” possible

and unique. There is a possibility that this perception is due a total lack of design intentionality, but it was not further explored.

So, in the end, although one of them was more extreme, both participants consider design ability related to the “Represent” category with two basic conditions. The first one is the novelty of the ideas, as they are fixed with the use of “creativity” in the activity that implies design ability, moreover it should be evident and have evidence of this “effort or talent”. This is a curious situation that reminds the claim of total authorship of one designer to be considered as the use of design ability. Although that case corresponds to the third simulation of the previous group. Where in the present is part of the second simulation.

So, for non-design participants more or less share the idea that the use of a mental image is only part of the design ability if it is related to somewhat new. If there is something that one knows is memory and knowledge, not design practice. For that reason, exemplify is not evident as an action with design ability, instead is imagining. This notion changes when requiring more “work”, as the second situation, and was especially evident in the project manager whose results based on the task and simulations show that must apply more effort to create a mental image. On the contrary, the financial consultant does it more subconsciously, which would explain the contradiction between the usual answers regarding the mental effort and a usual refusal to recognize design practice in the different stages.

Passing to the third simulation situation, both participants agree to be a design practice, as one affirms that because it is a “better” situation for the use of design ability as the images serve as bases to create the final image; and the other participant considers that it can be a practice of design because there is an extra “work” that is not based in “only memory.” Supported by how evident was for them to recognize the third simulation case as a practice of design while the first one was impossible and the second one was debatable. The second condition is the “tangible effort of materialization” on the idea.

This could be deducted thanks to the simulated situations that were developed with different weights of categories. With them it can be detected which ones are more related to design for each population, and in this case has been very

clear that while more reduced the “represent” category becomes, the more difficult is for them to recognize the existence of design ability. In general, the two conditions; novelty and effort, make that design ability is instinctively related to the aesthetic and although everyone can be a designer when making a presentation.

Finally, although both “accepted” that have some kind of design ability, they consider that are not any close to what proper designers possess. Moreover, they consider that they use it at least partially differently. The reason is that they use it to manage their data, explain things or make some elements more attractive. But not to develop the overall aesthetic of the presentation, which is what they consider the main use of the design ability, that a designer would give it. From this point of view “they become one when their focus is on make it the “prettiest” possible” (paraphrasing one answer). Certainly, this corresponds with their opinion of the differences with a designer making a presentation, as they state that will focus on the aesthetic first and maybe later on present the data to finalize the content.

17 FOURTH STAGE

The last stage is like an epilogue as has been mentioned at the start of the fieldwork. It was conducted to introduce the participants in the model formally and explicitly. The instrument used was the draft presentation made for the sustentation of this thesis. The presentation ([Appendix VI](#)) takes around forty minutes with almost fifty slides and the discussion took around twenty minutes. One meeting was held for each group, using the same tool, and recorded.

This section was made after finishing the document and has indirect references to the following chapters, so it is recommended to read previously the other parts if the interest is a sequential comprehension of the hypothesis and results. However, in case of being more interested in the overall process of the fieldwork and how it ended, it would be better to continue in this section.

It can be noticed that in contrast with the rest of the stages the results will start with the non-designers. The reason for this is that at the end of this study, they cease to be the protagonists. Although they have been the main source of data to construct the research, in the case of this stage, the most important aspect is to know the opinions of the professional designers; the public to whom the present document is addressed. That is why their feedback is placed at the end of the section. However, as was explained after finishing this stage. The results and hypothesis will return to place their focus on the non-designers' professionals.

17.1 Non-design professional opinion

In the case of the non-design professionals, the meeting presented mixed results, as the participants agreed with all the theoretical bases and the results of the study. They were particularly surprised to find that the data demonstrated they use the design ability in a consistent manner and frequency as the designers. It was even more when they see that most of the ideal segments in the protocols belong to them. This was happily recognized, even after hearing the finding of deviations and misalignments of the project manager. Who did not object to the findings on the protocols.

A minor observation while presenting the results and the significant differences between participants, was made by one of them who consulted if there was a consideration of the gender of the participants. This is an interesting observation that can be considered as a minor limitation of the study as one of the members was from a different sex of the other three. However, when this was mentioned to the designers, they curiously disregard this aspect.

The data was absorbed clearly and there was no question related to the process, but they mentioned that now understand plainly why the stages were conducted in certain ways. The simulated situation was of particular interest as they could see what the reasoning was to develop the exercises in based on the model. One major observation, however, was that one of the participants mentioned

that even agreeing on the model and its presence called as design ability, for himself will still be called plain “imagination”.

An apparent reason for that is that does not want to be called a designer but also states that does not have a problem if is called design ability by the rest. This was still considered after reviewing the hypothesis evaluations, which were also agreed to by both participants. Again, they were really surprised to find that their supposition about how designers will work was wrong and one considered that could be a coincidence, this hardly could be the case as the author saw the same patron in his colleagues. Another aspect that caught their attention was that they were more focused on the aesthetic than the designers.

In their final thoughts, a really curious expression was that “maybe non-designers are better designers”, and frankly the author considers that could be true for conducting studies of design ability. As the design ability is more evident and superficial than the other group. It must be noticed that the presentation conducted with this group was the first one and the presentation did not include the sub-objective specific slices. It was considered through this experience was necessary to present them independently with the designers to make the findings more comprehensible and reaffirm the results that derive from the main answer.

17.2 Professional designer’s opinion

The duration of the meeting with the professional designers’ group was substantially longer, they are the main group to whom this research is aimed, and their answer was positive. They mentioned that the information was easily understood and expected some more complex and confusing theories. They agree the validity of the model and consider that is the minimum expression of design ability.

They arrive at a similar conclusion of the author without influence, the design ability that is manifested in the minimum cycle is a base unit, and an atom that when merged in a bigger cluster allows and manifests different ways of design

ability even among designers, influenced by aspects like experience and education. After showing them the proposal, in their opinion they can recognize the presence of the model in his work easily.

About the results of the contrasting results, there was a bigger attraction to the quantitative data, in part because is more digestible as the chart is short and simplified. On the contrary, in the qualitative observations, although it was established that designers present a greater frequency of cycles of operation, they wish to have more explicit percentual data about it. Nevertheless, the results of the coded protocols were supported by them, and they find the process pertinent.

The hypothesis evaluations were also shared as this meeting was made after concluding the document. It was a surprise they had high acceptance of the proposals even when the data show aspects that they initially disagree on the previous stages, especially, the presence of design ability in all the participants. the similarity in the design ability, and the major difference in the orientation. They also consider adequate the modification made to the original diagram of the hypothesis ([Fig. 10](#)) that will be revised in that section of the present document.

Concerning the sub-objectives, there were no objections to them. The proposal of the design ability model (that will be revised in the first sub-hypothesis section) was considered easily understood and valid. The second sub-result, about how can be presented the design ability, was also interesting for them. Although initially they consider the greater factor of difference, the experience and knowledge. The proposal is based on the orientation of the ability. Caught their attention specially the use of context (the potential intentionality), but it was explained that in the case of the non-designers was no evidence of it.

This opened an interesting proposal, maybe the context is present but as a cognitive sublayer. This does not significantly influence the results but is an interesting aspect that studies of design intentionality could take into account. Finally, the third result was also agreed and was a surprise that the participants did not refute or object, at least partially that their basic understanding of design starts with aesthetic aspects. The diagrams presented help them to clearly understand the proposals and they even make an interesting inference.

They consider that the way the non-designer sees design as something far and not directly related with the aspects related to reflection could explain that sometimes design is considered more as an operative labor.

On the other hand, it was a surprise that they consider that this could be a valid base to explore the idea of design intelligence usually regarded as part of the spatial intelligence but based on visual skills. This was also an appreciation to consider while making the framework and was interesting to see it appearing again at the end of the study. The author agreed with both affirmations.

18 RESULTS CONTRASTING

As has been mentioned, there is an ostensive difference in the occurrence of the model between the different units of analysis, even inside the groups. It has been identified that a major cause of this situation is the use of a clearer mental image and orientation in a contextual use that has been addressed as potential intentionality. The variation in these aspects could be associated with the high difference in the frequency to do the task.

All of them have a consistency in the presence of the design ability but the small particularities are worth sharing before going to the similarities and differences between the two groups. It is notable that the units that have a similar frequency to work in the type of task assigned, also share similarities in their behavior and proportional use of the design ability. This can be noticed better by analyzing a chart of model frequency.

That chart is constructed based on the rate of the category's manifestation into the segment over the number of fragments of the concurrent protocol using the initial method of time-based on the minute-per-minute analysis. So, the unit of ratio is the number of sections valid by the overall quantity of sections in each sample. It was preferred that way because the posterior analysis made based on action/episodes is more disparate in their segregations and does not take significant consideration to events where the model is not present.

For example, one unit could take two minutes without an ideal segment inside and in the last minute of the episode have one, so it was three minutes related to an action. Meanwhile, another participant took two minutes and presented a multiple of ideal segments (two cases per episode). This could be a typical result of the analysis based in activity hierarchy, maybe none of them did the action better but the model has significant differences in both cases. Now, imagine that the task was made for the first unit in two episodes identical, and the second unit takes three also identical. Then, the [table 19](#) will be made as an example.

Table 19. E.g. Activity hierarchy chart

DIVISION BY ACTIVITY HIERARCHY	
Participant one	Participant two
EPISODE I 1 ideal segment	EPISODE I 2 ideal segments
EPISODE II 1 ideal segment	EPISODE II 2 ideal segments
	EPISODE III 2 ideal segments

Most of the results and inferences obtained and revised in the different stages have been done through analysis using data equivalent to the chart above. But there is also valuable information that has been obtained from the initial division based on the minute per minute studies. An equivalent using the present example will be if the chart takes six minutes in total (each participant could have different times but to simplify the math, they will have the same time), a chart based in the division based on a typical fragmentation per time will be observed as the [table 20](#).

Table 20. E.g. Minute per minute chart

DIVISION BY TIME	
Participant one	Participant two
MINUTE 1 / 0 ideal segment	MINUTE 1 / 1 ideal segment

MINUTE 2 / 0 ideal segment	MINUTE 2 / 1 ideal segment
MINUTE 3 / 1 ideal segment	MINUTE 3 / 2 ideal segment
MINUTE 4 / 0 ideal segment	MINUTE 4 / 0 ideal segment
MINUTE 5 / 0 ideal segment	MINUTE 5 / 1 ideal segment
MINUTE 6 / 1 ideal segment	MINUTE 6 / 1 ideal segment

Now if we consider the ratio of ideal segments for each participant, in the first case will be 100% for both participants. On the other hand, in the second chart, the ratio for the first participant is 33% and for the second is 83%. The results with the charts are very different, so which one is right? The answer is both, what is important to know is that each one has different meanings and uses.

The first ratio ([table 19](#)), for example, which base is divided by actions and operations, allows us to know if the model is present in all the activity, not the amount of it used, but determine its presence across the different aspects of the activity. However, their results in macro and quantitative data are very limited. Instead, a valuable amount of information can be acquired through the individual analysis of the levels of the activity and their comparison with their peers.

The second ratio ([table 20](#)) instead allows us to know how intense the use of the model is, independently of how is used or when. It allows a study of the task from a macro perspective and a more quantitative result. In the case of the present study, their result would have been very limited if used alone, but complementary data of the analysis based on the activity theory is a great asset. Its best use could be when observing the frequency of each element that corresponds to a category.

That means considering the presence of segments where the model was incomplete like the deviations or even the misalignments to have a general overview of what was intended. This shows a general approximation of the practice of design in the task and the frequency of the design ability, reflected in the following chart ([Table 21](#)) which the ratio is based on the number of segments (or parts) with the total division of its protocol.

Table 21. *Explicit frequency*

Model component	Industrial designer	Graphic designer	Financial consultant	Project manager
Perceive category / Contextual knowledge	85%	71%	86%	100%
Project category / Develop knowledge	100%	82%	90%	100%
Represent category / Contrasted knowledge	66%	39%	91%	90%
Ideal segments occurrence in time	40%	15%	86%	63%

In this chart is notable the big occurrence of the category's components in the case of the project manager. This evident presence of thoughts related to each category was a great help to validate the operational chart used as a coding scheme. On the other hand, it was a surprise that their component results were not correlated with the value of "ideal segments". This was later understood by the high deviation and misalignments during their process. But even with these results, there is still a clear difference in the presence of ideal segments in non-design professionals.

This is associated with another difference in the "represent" category on designers, which can be explained by the high presence of multitasking situations during that point of the model flow. The two cases will be explored in detail in the "differences section" on the following pages. On the other hand,

a significant similarity between all the participants is the consistency of the “project” category. All of them mentioned that work with some kind of idea in the mind, although probably ones more detailed and clearer than others.

One can notice the presence of these ideas, with descriptions or intentions to make in the future. When all these thoughts are consolidated there is a development of knowledge and a mental image. They can be identified with statements regarding the modifications that are planned, as there is a high possibility that are linked to contrasting the mental image with what they are perceiving; “I will move this to ...”, “I am going to use ...”, “I would like to put that in...”, etc. At the same time, some of these manifestations usually non-designers denote doubt or unclear visions by using; maybe, would, perhaps, etc.

Finally, it has been a welcome surprise to find a good number of cases with thoughts related to perception. Even if it is true that the perception skills are the more used and probably the information more abundant, it was expected that they will be less verbalized or even nonverbal at all. However, they are present, usually as an overture of the operation like; “Let’s see...”, “I am checking...”, “I will look...”, etc. Or as the crystallization of the process that takes place in a type of contextual knowledge that presents a judgment or appreciation of what is being perceived; “I like this”, “this is ugly”, “I don’t like that”, etc.

However, it is well to consider that one never stops to create thought in the categories, at least for “perceive”, it is a continual process that is part of the cognitive layers that have been mentioned. That will also explain how usually all the models can be found in one sentence. The reason to talk of the model as a flow is that is a reality that the presence of a main cognitive layer takes precedence over the rest and is not fixed in a type of thoughts while it manifests the verbalization. When the order of the priorities of the elements is comparable to the model category, then based on the framework of the study is a clear manifestation of design ability.

The existence of the layers takes relevance as a result of the research, it shows the difference between “observe and see” in all the categories, validated by the analysis of the mental image in the different protocols, interviews, and simulated situations. It is an explication of the lower finding in studies of

concurrent protocol analysis of designers that are based just on the transcriptions. The present study demonstrates the importance of conducting the think aloud procedure in combination with a retrospective protocol, behavior observation and especially with the activity theory foundations.

To conclude the observations in the chart, a curious aspect is that except for the financial consultant, the rest of the participants have the category of “represent” as the lowest one, this has been unexpected, actually before starting the second stage it was expected that category will be the most populous. As are the “simpler” descriptions. However, fortunately, the think-aloud method is not a description of what one does, it is the reflex of the mental process, and it seems that the actions related to the psychomotor domain are placed in cognitive layers inferior to the reflexive thoughts.

To summarize the particular differences in the four units using the data for the two types of charts revised at the start of the section and made with all the information gather in the stages of the fieldwork, the following chart is presented based on the presence of the model:

Table 22. Protocol particularities

Graphic designer	Industrial designer	Financial consultant	Project manager
Place his work in a constant situational context and in that way build and identify all the aspects that are needed.	From time to time place the work in a context to identify the requirements that could be missed.	This protocol has been the most ideal for the study as the model is present in the best way, with consistency and verbal evidence.	There were frequent deviations and misalignments, which gave an unexpected perspective of the model.
Does not manifest elements constantly in the represent category but has a clear mental image	There are short verbal communications of the represent category and	The thoughts of the “represent” category are detailed and the	The behavior was the most different with frequent returns to previous slices to make changes or add

that guide his work being multitasking.	is significant less than the perceive category.	most verbally expressed.	aspects that were unconcluded.
Make a clear structure draft before starting the work and is highly focus on the content and the narrative.	The “aesthetic” of the presentation is done by the diagraming of the content and improving after finishing the last slice.	The “aesthetic” of the presentation is done by the diagraming of the content.	Although these situations the model place perfectly in all the protocol what implies a use of the design ability.

18.1 Similarities between both groups

It is worth noting that all this information has been achieved thanks to the analysis of the activity using analysis of frequency (based on a minute per minute) and behavior (based on activity hierarchy). So, the results are a combination of both types of information. This allowed us to identify similarities and differences between the two groups of the study. The most important result is that at the end, both groups present the model across all the tasks and in the same episodes (actions) with equivalent segments (operations).

So, the presence of design ability is highly similar between professional designers and non-design professionals. Is like a tool that is on the desk of each participant and used at the same moments, however, what is different is how is used. This “use” is based on the significant differences in each category of the model. This transforms the design ability about the context and is present in each one of the participants in a different way but with common traits.

The first one was the assumption that all possess a mental image that affects their performance in the second stage. This has been tested with positive results in the third stage of the fieldwork. It was curious however that the person with the “better” performance has not had the highest presence in the “project” category; and this was the same with the second one, the financial consultant. This could be the result of their experience in the task and the use of that

knowledge more as an input from a “perceive” category (a memory) than an adapted mental image.

As mentioned in the section of designers of the third stage, the most usual presence of this situation is during the operation of select in the exemplify action related to files that they are confident to find. This can be supported by the unusually high presence of the “perceive” category in all the participants, and in the designers, it is even higher than the “represent” category. This will also explain the refusal of the financial consultant to consider their activity as design, in the same way as he does with the second simulated situation of the third stage.

Because what he retains in his main is the bigger influence of the input of “perceive” received it by a memory and ignores that he made minor adjustments in the “project” category, disregarding the flow and the model; ignoring that he uses design ability. This is not the case for the designer group and the project manager, the first because after they recall their memory, probably make a more complex process of adaptation to the circumstances where they want to use the data.

On the other hand, the project manager shows evidence of difficulty in creating mental images that directly influence their process of remembering. Probably the information is in a less detailed way than the other participants and for that reason must make an extra effort to complete the missing elements with new elements based on imagination which is a clear part of the “project” category. This in particular has been corroborated in the questionnaire of the second simulated situation of the third stage when asked, why was considered a design practice.

Finally, besides editing and diagraming being highly related to “aesthetic”, the actions of searching for a reference (exemplify) and summarizing are highly associated with the model in both groups. For “exemplify” the study has been extensive since the third stage, however, to make it more manageable and validate part of the assumptions it was conducted with is an association to visual operations. Nevertheless, exemplify goes further than that, e.g., making an analogy will be an excellent nonvisual case of study.

Based on what has been researched design ability can easily be present in fully verbal activities, a case to explore that could be based on operations based on verbal exemplification or summarize of documents. During the concurrent protocol analysis, was found multiple episodes on different participants related to these activities present ideal segments. Especially for the case of summarizing their text, if was not for the necessity of testing the presence of mental images, that would have been the action selected for the simulated cases of the third stage.

18.2 Differences between both groups

The most striking difference and certainly unexpected, was the lower presence of ideal segments in the professional designers, the reason for this is their extensive use of the multitasking case, which is not considered an ideal situation but a particularity. In the case of the non-design professionals, the missing percentage is based on deviations, misalignment or in very few cases actions without segments. Even with these inconveniences, it was surprising the high amount of design ability used. Especially for the financial consultant, which as mentioned previously, is considered the perfect sample for the study.

A curiosity with him and the other member in that group was observed on the concurrent protocols when compared to the manifestation of the “perceive” category. The designers are less subjective in their appreciation, it was common to find expressions in the non-designers like; “I see an “ugly” square”, “Look that “modern” color”, and “Watch this “catchy” image”. On the contrary, designers almost do not give “aesthetic” judgments. This could be due that their education tried to delimit the relation of aesthetics with design.

It was also interesting that the graphic designer, which was the better performer of the task, present the lowest percentage of ideal segments, which also is associated with the highest presence of multitasking situations. It is a particularly notable contrast to the values of ideal segments between the better performers in each group. Having the greater ratio of the ideal segments the financial consultant seems to be verbally conscious of their creative reasoning

process, and after the multiple interviews demonstrate that is combined with a clear mental image of what is doing.

This also includes the “represent” category, so the use of the tool takes relevance in “its” cognitive process, a case that repeats with the other participant from the non-designers, the presence of ideal segments is the second highest and could be even higher than the financial consultant, if we're not by the problems of misalignments or deviations. It is really curious they even associate his actions with the skills and knowledge that are part of the model, but they refuse to consider those elements as part of design ability.

On the contrary, designers and particularly graphic designers work with the mental image as a second plane, but not unconsciously, instead is a nonverbal thought. There would not be strange to affirm that as one achieves a greater domain of the design ability, their verbalization is reduced, especially in the represent “category” and its use goes to a secondary layer to give space to the other cognitive process that was found and orient their work, “the potential intentionality.”

This has been already postulated in previous research on the field, to the point of affirming that design is a nonverbal process. However, it is important to notice that the majority of works mention the idea of nonverbal because refers to “mental images”, this is not appropriate, the study on the protocols and the simulated cases demonstrated that some mental images can be and are normally verbalized. The reason why they are not frequent is usually that a superior layer of cognition will take preference to be verbalized. And in the case of the designers, this will be the “potential intentionality.”

The manifestation of this is that professional designers talk frequently with themselves as imagine a context with the public, they imagine this experience vividly and even give “live” to different participants with specific dialogues. The complexity and extension of this situation are high and could be almost the duration of an episode that could take minutes. There was a case of the graphic designer of over four minutes with minimal and short pauses due to thoughts that corresponded to one category of the model. This sometimes makes identifying the model difficult but gives valuable data.

There was also a common space between segments, of all types of ideals, multitasking, or even a few deviations where this “contextualization” appears and can last one minute. These “interruptions” are more evident in the omission of a big part of the thought that corresponds to the “represent” category, that in contrast is more verbal and detailed in the non-designer group. As has been mentioned when was inferred in the second stage and tested in the third stage, this could be in part due to lower confidence in their “aesthetical qualities” but also for a mental image less adapted to their canvas and used more like a memory or reference formed like as if were a interpret data from the “perceived” category.

The industrial designer showed a lower use of this orientation and for that reason, his multitasking segments were significantly less but even exceptionally higher than the non-design professionals. As has been mentioned although the expertise on design, the difference between designers could be due to the lack of frequency to work on the task. This could be supported by seeing the other group where the cases of the financial consultant contrast the zero occurrences of the multitasking in the project manager protocol.

Finally, the last difference to take into consideration is the number of cycles required to close operations. Although both groups frequently present sentences where the model could be transposed entirely, non-design professionals seem to use fewer cycles in the operations. However, most of the differences in cycles between populations are based on major use of multitasking operations from designers. In that way, their process is faster than the non-designers even when there is more intensive use of the ability. This implies a high degree of effectiveness in the task.

19 HYPOTHESIS EVALUATION

To evaluate the hypothesis first a specific analysis has been made of each element of the model in the groups of study. The most significant aspects have been placed in the following chart ([Table. 23](#)), to make a quick examination of

the original proposal in the general evaluation after that the sub-objectives will be revised concerning the original sub-hypothesis.

Table 23. Model contrasted on samples.

Model component	Professional designers	Non-design professionals
Perceive category	They use visual skills without physical evidence of being used differently except by small differences in episodes and verbal affirmations.	
Contextual knowledge	The information manifested are basically ostensive descriptions.	They descriptions includes many subjective appreciations.
Project category	They build their ideas based on their experience, knowledge and contextual use. But the main axis, and the ratio of each one was different in non and professional designers.	
Develop knowledge	Their final ideas are verbally more detailed, they affirm to have clear mental images.	Their final ideas are usually nonverbal, but noted because are used to validate actions.
Represent category	All the units of analysis present significant different ways to materialize the presentation even using the same software (power point).	
Contrasted knowledge	They frequently do not communicate thoughts related to their representation.	Their thoughts are verbal and correspond with their action using the tools.

19.1 General evaluation

The hypothesis proposed indicates that “The design ability is common between professional designers and non-design professionals as projection skills and partial contextual knowledge used to materialize a medium that achieves a desired change in a situation.” This means as the diagram presented in the

previous chapter that the category of “perceive”, their product the “contextual knowledge” and “project” are shared.

It was proposed, the first one “perceive” would have some differences, that will affect the knowledge, “contextual” while the second one “project” would be identical in both groups. It was considered that the use of skill will be similar, and actions will be oriented by at least: the raw data (knowledge that wants to be communicated), context (situation or public where wants to be used) and experience (previous work on other presentations).

On the contrary, the “represent” category will possess significant differences in each group and these differences will significantly affect the “development and contrasted knowledge”. The diagram below (Fig. 17) includes the simplified decomposition of the “project” category orientations, and it is also illustrated in one color. On the contrary, the “perceived” category shows a transition of two types of green to notice the presence of some differences depending on the population.

Fig. 17 Orientation detail of the thoughts of the 'project' category (Cesar Yachi, 2023).

After examining the data from all the protocols, a small difference was detected, and a new diagram based on the result identified was made (Fig.18).

Fig. 18 Diagram result from the fieldwork (Cesar Yachi, 2023).

What has been noticed is that the components of the “Project” category fundamentally the skill and knowledge are not the same (Fig.19). While non-design professionals orient their work in raw data and experience to define and structure their presentations and their mental image of them, professional designers, used as their main guide the context and create a high detail image of it to develop their presentation.

Fig. 19 Differences in orientation of the Project category (Cesar Yachi, 2023).

In that way the new diagram considers a division in both categories being partially shared, and the variation of the original hypothesis as the final answer:

“The design ability is common between professional designers and non-design professionals as partial contextual knowledge and projection skills used to materialize a medium that achieves a desired change in a situation.”

The general hypothesis is followed with the results of the sub-objectives, that support the final answer to the research question. The three conclusions obtained from them give an appreciation of the more evident effects from the original problem statement, “the unclear distinction of the practice of design from non-designers”. Each one of the results conforms to a facet that helps to understand better “how design ability is present across professional fields.”

19.2 First sub-objective evaluation

The first sub-objective is identifying a model of design ability ideal to establish a common understanding between professional designers and non-design professionals. The reason for this is the difficulty in understanding design roles in non-design teams. A clear model will help to overcome the semantics barriers using explicit and structured elements that conform to the design phenomenon. So, what definition of design ability could be used to bridge a common understanding between professionals?

The answer to this is “Design ability as a creative reasoning way to materialize a medium to achieve a desired change in a situation”. This construct has as the keystone the idea of creative reasoning as a cognitive process that is refined as a model of design ability ([Fig.20](#)) developed for this study based on a solid design theory as visual thinking, but also the educational theory of the KSA. Thanks to them and the inclusion of the hierarchy of design knowledge by Stolterman et al. and the interdisciplinary activity theory from Vygostky et al. with some improvements made by the author.

This proposal has been tested with excellent results in the different stages of the fieldwork and is presented as a tool for further studies in the field of design

practice and especially design ability. Complementary, the different instruments used for its sampling are provided in the annexes as part of the outcome of this research.

*Fig. 20 Design ability model
(Cesar Yachi, 2023).*

19.3 Second sub-objective evaluation

The second sub-objective describes the differences and similarities of design ability in the participants; to explain the unexpected results on design teams working with non-design professional members. Considering the variations in the design ability helps to expect and delegate different outcomes based on the way each one performs when a design practice is required. This matter is addressed with the question of; how design ability can be present in design and non-design professionals?

As a hypothesis, it was proposed that the “project” skills used by professional designers and non-designers are similar (there is not a fixed list, it would depend on the task) the only difference could be the way how they are used, and the type of results that they obtain as a developed knowledge. On the other hand, is expected that most of the “perceive” as well as, to some degree, the contextual knowledge obtained. There was no prediction about the magnitude or frequency of the design ability used as there was no support to make an inference.

The results of the protocols and simulated situations show that the suppositions work as expected. The represent category is presented very differently even among designers using the same tools, and for that reason affecting the contrasting knowledge. The other categories present a partial similarity, especially in the skill used to construct the mental image, mention apart is the common use of imagination for its construction.

Meanwhile, contextual knowledge presents a variation due to the different backgrounds of the participants as it is a crystallization of their interpretations. Those differences are accumulated in a snowball effect that is derived from a significant difference in the development of knowledge. About the use of a more intensive frequency of cycles of the model, it has been validated in the result contrasting but even considering that the performance of the designers was overall faster but effective.

Besides these particularities, the similar occurrence and degree of the design ability used between the two populations were unexpected but welcome. It is the way how is used that creates the differences mentioned in the paragraph above and there have been significant findings about it thanks to the research. The main one has been identifying the aspect that generates all the variations, which is the way they orient their activity. Each participant has provided particular data that allows them to propose some levels of design ability “use” based on its orientation. This proposal is presented in the diagram called “design ability ladder” ([Fig. 21](#)).

Fundamentally, a non-designer without experience in the task will base their work on intuitive requirements that maybe not even achieve to be a mental image due to the continuous fuel or orientation to canalize its imagination, this

will conduct an intensive process of trial and error that could border with the improvisation or spontaneity. This has been the case for the project manager.

Another case will be a non-designer that works frequently in the activity to perform. In that case, their process will be based on the experience which provides a mental image that guides the flow of the design ability model. This does not mean that not consider the requirements, they are also integrated with the idea created with the experience accumulated. That has been the case for the financial consultant.

Similarly, even a professional designer that is not used to certain activities will base the use of his ability in their principles on his education. Its formation will help to place and use the requirements and experience in a certain and methodical way. This will structure their practice and allow them to save resources to create a clear mental image. This will influence the way his design ability is manifested. Like in the case of the industrial designer.

However, when the professional designer whose frequency in the activity is high, can explore all the previous elements and the resources available to place the idea in a detailed context that guides and defines the use of the creation. These cognitive processes are not part of the design ability model. They work in parallel, usually taking priority in the cognitive layers. The author has decided to call this mental state a design intentionality, but independently of the name its presence is a fact and works in synchrony with the design ability, this special condition guides the professional design practice.

Fig. 21 Design ability ladder (Cesar Yachi, 2023).

As has been mentioned, these four levels do not necessarily mean a different degree of design ability development but logically they are related to the degree of formation and practice in design. However, what is considered the main divisor between the levels is how the design ability is used because those influence drastically how the cognitive process is manifested. And while higher the level, it is easier to have a big perspective of the situation and it is easier to recognize the design practices and the use of design ability in them.

A curious aspect about the design ability ladder is the unexpected similarity with the Danish design ladder (Fig. 22). This proposal made by the Danish design council in 2001 focuses on the way design is implemented in companies. This proposal has been frequently used in business studies as a tool to evaluate the current and potential integration of design in their activities and as a reference point to orient their action to capitalize the use of it.

Fig. 22 Danish design ladder (DDC, 2001, <https://ddc.dk/>).

The similarity with the ladder proposed in this study starts with the four steps, which pertain to the degrees of individual use of the design ability ladder can be associated with a correlational effect. This means that populations with certain levels of design ability will manifest a relationship with design, equivalent to the DDC ladder. But this cannot only be translated to companies

the author proposes that any organic system of people, translated as a society, will integrate the design practice in the way of the majority of its members using its ability.

These could seem obvious, but, curiously, there have not been studies related to it and the design ladder has not been further developed to this degree, in a simple way both proposals describe the same phenomenon. But it could be said that the DCC presents the presence of the design practice in a macro vision while the present study proposes its study on a micro level. If these proposals are matched, interesting inferences could be raised:

In the first level, there is a limited identification of the design ability, and in that way, a systematic design practice is absent. As a description done by the DDC (cited by Blomqvist and Toukokuu, 2006), “Solutions are based on the perception of functionality and aesthetics shared by the people involved. The points of view of end-users play very little or no part at all.” This can be an excellent description of the use of the “Natural” level of the design ability and is because is orientated solely to the requirements of the task, the project manager could be placed in this area.

Then, in the second level, the design ability is based on their experience, inspired by the requirements and memories proceed to construct a mental image. This is the main orientation and for that reason, their design practice seems to a “form-giving” (then in other revisions of the DDC has been called Styling), it starts to be a clearer recognition of design but is perceived as aesthetic matters and that’s the way how is address in the companies from this level and are equivalent to the results obtained with the participant considered part of this “empiric” level, the financial consultant.

After that, in the third level, the individual attempts to apply their formation in design on the activity, as the industrial designer in the task of the stage two. This education orients its design ability and result in being more effective which allows to present a proposal more integral where “the design solution is adapted to the task and focused on the end-user” (DDC cited by Blomqvist and Toukokuu, 2006). This does not mean that the previous levels can achieve satisfactory results, but thanks to recognizing the practice of design more than

aesthetical factors, other elements appear that could be expressed as thinking outside the box.

Finally, for the four-level, the design ability is extremely driven by intentionality, this could be usually related to a specific context, a user, or usability, which means that the design ability takes a secondary role in the cognitive process. The thoughts are still focused on the activity, but the vision goes beyond the proposal that is being built. At a corporate level this will be as “The design process combined with the company vision and future role in the value chain” (DDC cited by Blomqvist and Toukokuu, 2006). The graphic designer will be placed in this step.

In this way, the two ladders can be observed as sides of the same coin, as individual and group. But, a really important consideration, is that the design ladder considers the absence of design and its gradual inclusion, however, the author strongly disagrees with this visualization. He postulates and supports this statement with the present study, that the design practice is present in the four levels. In reality what happens is that the use of the design ability varies significantly in each case, causing the variation in the identification of models and the design practice in them.

19.4 Third sub-objective evaluation

The third sub-objective is oriented to compare the understanding of design ability between professional designers and non-design professionals using the model. The reason was found the root of the drawbacks in implementing design ways in transdisciplinary activities. The different comprehension of the practice between non-design professional and professional designers could explain how the common goal is associated with the different members. The question to work this aspect was; why is design ability understood differently by design and non-design professionals?

The sub-hypothesis to explain this semantic barrier considered the differences in the model observed in the results ([Fig. 18](#)). Contrasting the way of the design

ability present in the simulation cases, protocols and multiple interviews conducted in the different stages, it was noted a marked trend to associate design with the segments and episodes where the “represent” category takes high relevance.

This validates the supposition that non-designers will rely heavily upon their experience with physical means to establish an ostensive definition of design, Nevertheless, it was a surprise that it was not a direct association with their practice, instead, they use as a reference their idea of the work of professional designers. After evaluating this situation, a little, it started to make more sense as when one tries to define music will think of what a musician does, or in a more ambiguous sense if one thinks of what nursing is, one will think of what a nurse does.

This translates to the current model used in the general hypothesis as the sector related to the “represent” category of the designers, the section more distanced from the non-designers, which until certain points explains how some people see design as a mysterious or spontaneous phenomenon. This is especially true when they think of design ability as a matter of creativity and disruption.

It was after reflecting on the use of the model in the different situations and protocols from the second and third stages, that the non-design professionals recognize partially the use of the ability and practice of design. But they limit this comprehension to their own “represent” category. However, the fixation with the materialization process also leads to the reduction of the practice of design to be treated as an aesthetical or decorative activity.

Which could be related to the major explicit reference to components of the presentation like background, cover, colors, etc. For that reason, it was also understood that they expected that designers that make a digital presentation would focus first on the aesthetic of the presentation and maybe even neglect or struggle with the content. And the work that they do will have better “content” and lower “attractiveness”. The following diagram ([Fig. 23](#)) represents in red squares the parts of the model that non-designers can detect from the model. The more intense the red color is, the more evident for the participants.

inconveniences, but the performance of the designers in what they mentioned was indeed superior except in the aesthetical factor, that although subjective if evaluated from a simple perspective it could be said that they were equivalent.

The following diagram (Fig. 24) presents the designer's understanding of the design ability, covering all the models but with more incidence in the “represent” category and overlooking the presence of the model in the non-designers.

Fig. 24 Understanding of design ability by designers (Cesar Yachi, 2023).

20 IMPLICATIONS

The problem of an unclear distinction of design practice by non-design specialists is verified and present in a variety of professional environments. However, it is not as popular as other design matters, probably due to the high dissociation between the academy and the practice. It is an aspect that is hardly

noticed by a researcher that spent his time in the education of design, and usually detected in the Laboral world when a designer cross way with multiple disciplines not related to design but with common goals.

On the other hand, it has been a surprise for the author, that even professional designers, from pure specializations in departments of design and with more than a decade of experience, still associate design immediately with aesthetic aspects, and naturally this happens with many other groups. This is certainly a result of the shallow, if present, reflection on their practice. It is also a perception that is highlighted in special by Schön in his book “The reflexive practitioner”, where he claims that professional practitioners do not participate actively in the exploration and expansion of their disciplines, although possess a “hidden” practical knowledge.

It has been noted, thanks to this research in the different stages, that this reflection enriches the understanding of the design practice substantially. As a result, the use of the design ability is more evident through the immediate post-reflection than in the practice itself or what they can recall, even by the non-designers. However, the more reduced the “represent” category of the model becomes, the more difficult is to recognize the existence of design ability. This can be translated in a very simple way as less thought about the use of tools.

On the contrary when the effort of the materialization is higher, and the thoughts related to the “represent” category; there is a more evident relationship with the “aesthetic” elements of what has been done, that usually in the case of non-designers is mistaken as the core of design and treated as an equivalent of decoration. The omission of the other two categories also makes the impression in non-designers that creativity is a fortuity event of an operative process.

But this is also a complicated matter to explain for the designers before being presented with the model; they initially consider the main trait of their activity “the authorship” and “the use of tools” as the characteristic of the design. This is not as different as most of the literature revised that place drawing as the most fundamental aspect (skill) of design. However, this study is aligned with the current that proposes that design is over the material world, although is

linked to it by an unbreakable bond, its main trait is the creation of mental images, and its tool is the imagination skill.

The design practice indeed goes beyond the cognitive process to many psychomotor domains because the design has become complex. But at the same time if we do not recognize the mental image as its most elemental form, then we cannot establish an explicit development of the design ability. This has not been a problem in the current formation of designers as the traditional workshop education module as the axis of design program has solved this necessity indirectly and in aboriginal way.

However, recognizing the base element is a way to improve the quality of education and a way to be transmitted to non-designers as a part of regular education. The design ability, as has been studied in this document, is the atom of the design practice, is the way how design performance takes form in the reality and the clusters of the different actions that involve design ability could take different forms even if they are composed only of the same element because it is a “polymorph material” that can be combined with other abilities or work by itself in different ways.

The use of the design ability is a dynamic flow that at the same time is developing constantly, as any ability improves with practice and that includes not only formal manifestations of design. Moreover, the acquisition of new skills and knowledge of a person allows new types of manifestations and methods where this ability is applied. Consequently, the variation degree in the distribution of the ability in the population is very significant, and the contrast between professional designers and non-designers is evident in plain sight.

This does not mean that non-designers do not possess design ability, or it is not developed. Wide numbers of authors support that they can design. Arguing “that design capability not only resided in professional designers, but it is a specific form of general problem-solving capabilities (i.e., every ordinary people can design though their levels are varied). However, it still lacks empirical evidence to support these arguments. It requests a further investigation on how ordinary people design and compare it with designers’ design processes” (Jiang and Yen, 2009).

A big problem for this validation is related to considering design with the problems. This indeed comes from the tradition of the industrial design field. Sadly, that consideration has distorted the topic. As has been stated by some of the same authors the way how the designer works with problems can be very particular and even chaotic, although it is true that from the studies of the branch of methodology have been certain approximations to a consensus, they are still debatable and instead of being a way to relate ordinary people, has been a way to differentiate designers from them.

Moreover, that is the excuse to propose bringing the design perspective to the common society and initiatives like the design thinking branding have been so successful. The idea is to bring design knowledge to non-designers, and it is true that could be helpful, being the line of the studies in design methodology at the moment. However, this does not help find the design aspects common with non-designers and this is a big loss as is a way to understand the basic nature of the design.

Recognize that ordinary people's design opens the opportunity to understand our practice from their basis, as has been done using the present model. The study shows the presence of design ability in a highly similar frequency between professional designers and non-design professionals. Like a tool that is on the desk of each participant and used at the same moments, and the main difference is how it is used fundamentally in the construction of the mental image.

This cognitive process is the capacity to link three types of categories of thoughts from different skills and knowledge. The connection between them has a specific orientation and the flow completes at least a cycle to manifest the process. Different actions in a task would require disparate amounts of interactions and usually an operation is composed of one textual cycle. This verbalization could present the model in one sentence or a group of them, usually, designers compress them significantly more than non-designers, so even if they use more cycles, they take less time.

It is important to consider that a cycle requires reflection that evolves so it cannot instantaneously or overlap all the categories in the same moment. The time required will be dependent on the person, the task, and the situation. Also,

it is a type of cognitive process that could take place simultaneously or intermittently with others, especially if they are related to the same goal. The existence of cognitive layers allows this “multitasking” capacity, and it is the most superficial where verbal thought takes place.

This could happen in the three categories of the model. As has been observed in the protocols, a simulated situation, where there are different mental images, one directly related to a memory and works as an input in the “perceive” category. Others and the most usual that works as the ideal presentation expected and could use the previous one and adapted to a requirement of the situation. So, all the thoughts that come from perceptions will suffer some kind of modification that orientate the behaviors in reality, some kind of mental image related to the tool use, such as “tutorial videos”, that could replace the verbal thought of the commands that are used.

That explains why designers do not have frequent register thoughts related to the “represent” category and if it is also account that the “project” category which possesses the higher use of the “mental images” also possesses very simplified descriptions. It is comprehensible that some researchers have interpreted that design is only linked to nonverbal thinking. Nevertheless, when there is evident nonverbal thought of the model. Designers use the superior layer of their cognition to create another image related to the context of use, which has been addressed in the study as a potential “intentionality”.

The present study has reached that point, and it is hoped that will go further, the suggestions for further research will come in the next chapter based on the evidence that supports the existence of design ability in all the participants in a very similar way. It does not mean that there have not been differences, even between the designers. But the variations in the intensity of cycles, and the different orientations on the design ability have been associated with education, formal programs or based on experience.

21 FURTHER RESEARCH

Departing from the valid assertion of design ability as the “creative reasoning used in the specific task”, or in its extension version: “A cognitive process that uses a sequence of disparate skills through a body of knowledge to materialize a medium to achieve a desired change in a situation.” It can be affirmed with confidence that the design ability is used in a variety of disciplines that could be related to non-graphical activities.

There are indeed some few but significant research related to nonvisual activities and design, the most relevant for the present work are the research of Simon with mathematical problems or Outterside with children, but the use of a model proposed, and method of this research could give them a perspective through the field of design and a more solid structure of the cognitive process studied.

A wide variety of opportunities for study cases are open, based on the results of the first stage. From them, the author is attracted to explore the manifestation of design ability in professionals with disciplines that have a tradition from craftsmanship like design. Professions from music, pastry, or literature for example. So, the design phenomenon is not limited to visual matters, and probably the study of these activities would bring unexpected details of the ability.

Another interesting topic that was born from the third stage is studies based on the simulated situation of “The tetraplegic designer”. It is a case with undoubtedly design practice and presents the design ability in an explicit way that can be directly associated with the model. It could even be simulated as an iterative cycle as he made multiple proposals. It would be ideal the application of the “Oz wizard” method or use an image generator to study the extend the comprehension of the design intelligence.

As has been revised at the start of the framework, nowadays the research on the field of design is robust and solid to propose to establish an addition to the Gardner proposal. The different aspects that were well observed by cross can be supported with new evidence and the model of design ability works with

them. It can be considered as the core operation, which means an identifiable, specific, and essential process to perform a particular rational behavior that is required as a condition for a type of intelligence.

On the other hand, the study presented a qualitative analysis as the sample is not statistically significant, however if applied to classrooms it could provide additional valuable data. Considering that the approach will change from breath study to a depth study. In the same way, it could be used in students on different levels of a design program to identify turning points in the design ability ladder based on specific tasks.

Some particular aspects that have not been explored in deep are the relation of mental image and memory and its exploration would be a valuable asset to complement and go further to this study. In the same way, the relationship between the level of clarity on the mental image, verbalization and the layers of cognition could be studied in a more particular and detailed way.

Finally, the main point that is expected to be explored considering the results of this research is the relation between design ability and intentionality. The author considers this work as a starting point to study design intentionality from an educational but also a labor approach; why, how, and when is formed? These are some of the main questions that could be addressed in their study.

There has been a clear “intentionality” presented by the designers but is possible that would be different between specialties and depending on the task, as has been seen in the present research. Strong intentionality improves performance notably and is an aspect to be considered in any professional that aims to improve design performance. The author encourages this as the main route that should be followed in the studies of design science to improve the professional practice.

These studies of intentionality could also be mixed and integrated with the theory of competencies, widely studied in the educational and human resources fields. The European model considers the mix of ability and willingness to define an educational competency. From that perspective, the intentionality will be the base of the willingness and the potential existence of a general design competency is evident. However, a study of that kind would be better conducted by a designer with a strong relationship or being educated in an

educational department, as the complexity of that kind of study require strong support from that field and will bring a big impact on the academical field.

22 CONCLUSIONS

This thesis opens in the context of the professional field, where designers work in collaboration with other professionals but encounter multiple challenges. From placing their role in the company, passing by unexpected results in collaborative work with non-designers, to integrating a design practice with multiple disciplines. All of them with the common root of “the unclear distinction of the practice of design from non-designers.” This will be the spark that conduces to the train of thought that structure the research question.

Is perceived that non-designers have an unclear distinction of the practice of design, maybe because they cannot design; However, it is established that everyone can design, then does everyone have design ability? Being that all of us have design ability, do we develop our design ability differently? If is the case, then probably each profession understands design ability differently, so how is design ability present across professions?

The way to achieve the answer has been based on a thorough analysis of the performance of two different groups of people over a specific task with a high potential to use the design ability. The objectives of the descriptive comparative thesis were to identify the ideal model of design ability for designers/non-designers. Identify the similarities and differences of the ability; and compare the understanding of design ability in both groups.

The variable of study has been the main aspect of study from the research question, the design ability. It was not planned to alter the condition of the ability of the participant, so is considered non-experimental research. The quantity of participants has been very small and the data very deep and particular so, it has been considered a qualitative study.

Meanwhile, the fieldwork has been divided into four stages; the first using interview, the second a technique based on a concurrent protocol and the think-aloud procedure, the third one with a retrospective protocol and a test based on exemplification operations, and the final fourth a presentation of the findings. After processing the raw data, the results tested the hypothesis and helped to achieve the objectives.

This ambition and statement were proposed by the author almost ten years ago in an intuitive way: “Design is defined as a process, conception, plan, or disposition to something. But if reduced to its minimum expression, it can be classified as a “projectual activity”. However: although all people can design and many times it is done intuitively, it is the design professions that specialize in designing” (Yachi, 2014).

Finally, the model of design ability proposed has been accepted by the participants and used in the hypothesis evaluation showing that everyone possesses the design ability in a very similar way, but due to what is the element that orients their use the identification of the design practice changes significantly. Designers can recognize the total extension of their design ability, in contrast, non-designers only recognize part of it, which is equivalent to what they recognize ostensibly in the designers.

23 RECOMMENDATIONS

Through the experience of the present work, the author can provide three suggestions. One related to doing the research, another related to the practice, and one last to the education of design. In detail, the first one is about exploring design ability and concerns the fieldwork. The use of concurrent and retrospective protocols mixed with the think-aloud method is an excellent way to understand the manifestation of the design practice. But the management of the data could be a big challenge as it's a heavy workload in the different parts of its development.

The original idea of the author was to work with eight samples and in the end, to be reduced to half of them. It is true that the development of the framework also takes a lot of time, but even using the current specific design ability model. It must be considered a preliminary work to identify and prepare the task successfully as “the experimental set-up heavily influences the protocol data, and the amount of interpretation needed to wrench conclusions from the protocol data is also comparatively large.” (Dorst, 1995)

As an idea, the document presents the set of tools used for this study consisting of guides, charts, diagrams, presentations, and questionnaires in the different sections and annexes. That last part could be useful as a reference for any study interested in exploring the practice of design and identifying the design ability in them. However, it has to be considered that the instruments always have to be adapted to the specific conditions of the research.

The second suggestion is about the solution to the problem statement, as can be remembered; “the unclear distinction of the practice of design from non-designers.” This is translated as the capacity to identify what is design ability and when is present. As has been stated, thanks to studies based on extreme cases, everyone possesses design ability. Being able to know that what one is doing; is design based on the use of the ability would change dramatically the different effects that have been mentioned in the context.

However, it could seem that knowing the name of something would not make a great difference, but it does, a name implies recognizing and differentiating what is talked about. In that way, a designer with a clear understanding of the design ability and its presence in non-designers can capitalize on the potential of their organizations, even more, If they are the only designer in a group, because is “responsible for liaison and communication between design and other disciplines, which has proven to be an excellent means of dealing with the problem of linkages across departmental and disciplinary boundaries” (Heskett, 1989).

So, it is important to consider that a use design ability is not “make things”, is “think when you do a thing”. A “designer is essential: as more than a gear, is a magnetic compass. The designer is proposed as a project promoter, the axis through which the contributions of the different areas are integrated, boosted,

and innovated to define the unity of the product. It must be present at all stages of development through constant dialogue” (Yachi, 2014), but the most important aspect is that they must be able to communicate their role and performance.

If the practice is not addressed as design even if is done with mastery could be even ignored as an instinctive act and could not be associated, enricher, and perfectionate with precedents experiences. Moreover, as long as this unawareness remains there will not be an effective integration of the resources from the design discipline to improve their practice and even receive some backlash.

One typical case for example is non-designers that receive capacitation in the popular branding of “design thinking”. A good number of them rarely applies its contents in activities outside of the specific task that are used in their training workshops. This big fail has reached the point to question the use of the term “design thinking” and authors like Cross proposes the idea of establishing two meanings for it (the original and the popular) or using a new terminology as “designerly thinking” to address the cognitive aspects of design, in his document “Design thinking: What just happened?” (2023).

This obstacle is not solved by the current design education, as even experienced professional designers have struggled to define clearly what their core ability about, and it is worse if one tries to find a consistent understanding between them. The reason is that a big part of modern programs did not consider establishing a clear conception of the design ability. Moreover, their development is ignored as a solved part of the informal or “hidden curriculum” (Posner, 2004) of design programs but cannot be achieved in a small course or workshop for a non-designer.

The variations of design ability described in the ladder ([Fig. 22](#)) cause or allows a better understanding of the design ability. For that reason, could be inferred that the orientation applied on the design ability determines the type of connection between the professionals, being the cornerstone of their integration in teams that integrate multiple disciplines. If the objective is a real integration of the design practice in the society. The most elemental and

important part of the initiative should be making the use of design ability explicit.

This does not mean transferring a culture, proposing methods, creating approaches, or teaching ways of knowing, acting, or thinking. Non-designers do not need to be “professional designers” yet. At this moment people do not need “design thinking,” because they already have something more important disregarded, their “design ability.” Non-designers are “beggars sitting on golden benches” (a common Peruvian expression, unfounded attributed to Antonio Raimondi).

Non-designers can take many workshops and hire the best professional designers. But as long as they have “The unclear distinction of the practice of design” their efforts to obtain the “so popular” benefits of design, would be in the best case inefficient if not a big failure due to their ratios of investment. As “design cannot make an effective contribution in any company unless there is strong understanding and support for it at the highest level of management... of equal importance is the need to integrate the design function into the activities of a company at all levels” (Heskett, 1989).

Then, how do you achieve a real integration, that ends in transdisciplinary practices? Some promote to establish a new approach to the practice with “a fluid, evolving body of knowledge and ideas, often from outside design, whose objective is to provide designers with new tools and methodologies to initiate and catalyze transitions...” (Irwin et al., 2014). So basically, the inverse of the current design thinking. It’s a very interesting proposal.

But it is possible achieve this understanding of the exterior ,if designers do not have a clear comprehension of themselves? As was mentioned in the paragraphs above there is a lack of theoretical support to help the professionals to communicate the nature of their practice. This led to the third suggestion, that goes around the design education of professional designers but also non-designers, expressed as a trend to “impart design-led creative thinking skills to students across more disciplines” (DERC, 2020).

Design ability needs to be understood for the practitioners to make a manifestation of design able to establish a fruitful dialogue whit the other disciplines. To do it, any curriculum from a design program should be

improved considering as one of its main, formal, specific, and explicit axes to the design ability. Moreover, it must be part of the educational objectives if we consider the use of a healthy systemic curriculum.

As an expert in curriculum development, the author knows that this is a challenge front the traditional curriculums of design programs and maybe it will be a change really difficult to achieve for departments that do not count on professionals from the field of educational management or instructional design. However, is well to notice that “A curriculum that works satisfactorily for a certain time and under defined conditions may gradually become obsolete” (Lewis cited by Yachi, 2018).

It is a fact that design institutions invest their resources in other initiatives, that seem have results in a short span and attractive as part of the publicity of the trends and address directly to the society imposing or offering the practice of design as the answer for the new century. It is understandable if what the author proposes is not attractive as is a change in the long term, and a subtle solution that will not attract the exposure or patronage of investors.

Maybe a more reasonable option will be to aim for basic education, where the “Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development” (OECD) has a complete plan for the next decade to foster “creative thinking” as one of its goals in as one the main future skills. Their main promotor and president Andreas Schleicher emphasizes the “creative reasoning” as “the key for find solutions, working across disciplines, resolving problems and seeing that other people think differently” (2018).

The similarities between what has been studied, develop, and aimed in the study with what the OECD has developed are striking and are a big coincidence as the author did not get in contact with them until write these lines as a recommendation from one of his assessors. Thus, design ability must be an indispensable component of this “creative thinking”, described as “the competence to engage productively in the generation, evaluation and improvement of ideas, that can result in original and effective solutions, advances in knowledge and impactful expressions of imagination” (OECD, 2019).

24 FINAL THOUGHTS

This research has been a great opportunity to address many ideas that have been seeded during the professional and educational career of the author. Now after these pages, he has a clear route of how to conduct his adventure in research, and how relates to his practice. We were always eternal students in this life, but you can't always be self-taught. Sometimes we need teachers to “teach the route”, the time in the MAID program gives the orientation needed and is crystalized in this document.

Thus, this thesis ended up presenting the most valuable knowledge acquired by the author until today, the result of its reflection on practice and its education; “Design is a natural phenomenon that shapes our world unintentionally but driven by a strong causality” translated to the human performance would be; “design practice as the use of the design ability in a design situation” and design ability is defined as “creative reasoning applied to a specific task.”

The present work aligns with these precepts, but recognizes that “all human knowledge is uncertain, inexact, and partial” (Bertrand Russell, 1948) so this thesis is a stance to present a paradigm of the design cognition, but at the same time it recognizes the author best lesson from his years in his art faculty, “everything is perfectible” ... always.

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27 APPENDIXES

27.1 APPENDIX I

INTERVIEW GUIDE

Objective:

Identify specific tasks with the potential to use the design ability.

Type of task required:

To materialize a medium to achieve a desired change in a situation.

Operationalization chart:

Dimension	Dimension definition	Indicator	Indicator definition	Items	Item definition	
Specific task	Activity to materialize a medium to achieve a desired change in a situation.	materialized medium	It is a perceived result of the task (usually physical but could be digital).	Actions	A group of operations organized to achieve the task.	
				Product	The result of the application of a tool for a task.	
				Tool	A physical element that is used in the task to perform an action.	
		Desired change		It's the ideal state of the reality aspired as result	Objective	An aspiration that leads a task.
		Motivation			The absence or lack of something required for the task.	

			of the task	Subject	The characteristics of the individual that performs the task.
		Original situation	It's the state of the situation prior to the start of the task.	Environment	The components where the task happen.
				Problem	A catalyst of causes to effects from the task.
				Stakeholders	Individuals, groups, or institutions related to the task.

Sampling Process:

In the first session an interview with two sections will be conducted and recorded, after analyzing the data a second session will be arranged where the sample would perform the task selected through a design analysis protocol.

Interview Method:

The interview will take around 30min in the first section and around 20min for each itinerancy of the second section. Before starting the second part, a pause of 10 minutes will be taken to select the most adequate tasks to examine. The interview will be recorded, and data will be processed after the sampling.

Section 1

ITEMS	Nº	REACTIVE
General information	1.	<input type="checkbox"/> What is your name and age?
	2.	<input type="checkbox"/> What is your profession?
	3.	<input type="checkbox"/> Have you participated in a course or program after finishing your bachelor, what type?
Action	4.	<input type="checkbox"/> What do you do at work?
	5.	<input type="checkbox"/> Which tasks take more time, which less?
	6.	<input type="checkbox"/> Which are your more frequent tasks in work?
Product	7.	<input type="checkbox"/> What are the results of your work, products of your effort?
	8.	
	9.	<input type="checkbox"/> What are the best products for your work, why? <input type="checkbox"/> Are you the only person that can give those results?
Tool	10.	<input type="checkbox"/> What is the tool that you use the most in your work, why?
	11.	
	12.	<input type="checkbox"/> What is the tool that you enjoy most to use, why? <input type="checkbox"/> What is the tool that you don't like to use, but must do it?
Objective	13.	<input type="checkbox"/> Why did the company hire you?
	14.	<input type="checkbox"/> Why is the objective of the area where you work?
	15.	<input type="checkbox"/> What is your work role?
Motivation	16.	<input type="checkbox"/> What do you enjoy most in your work, what disgusts you?
	17.	
	18.	<input type="checkbox"/> What do you enjoy doing at work, what don't, why? <input type="checkbox"/> Who else can do your work, why?
Subject	19.	<input type="checkbox"/> Do you consider that have design ability?
	20.	<input type="checkbox"/> Do you have any kind of knowledge of design?
	21.	<input type="checkbox"/> How would/do you use design knowledge/ability in your work?
Environment	22.	<input type="checkbox"/> Do you work in more than one space, how are your work area?
	23.	
	24.	<input type="checkbox"/> Where do you work the most, why? <input type="checkbox"/> What differences are between your main work area and others?
Problem	25.	<input type="checkbox"/> What would happen if you were not in the company?
	26.	<input type="checkbox"/> What is the harder task to do in your work, why?
	27.	<input type="checkbox"/> What are the most usual difficulties in your work?
Stakeholders	28.	<input type="checkbox"/> What are the professions of your members team?
	29.	<input type="checkbox"/> Which professional is easier to work with?
	30.	<input type="checkbox"/> Which professional is harder to work with?

5' Pause to identify the tasks to use in the second section of the interview (at least two selections).

Tasks selected:

Section 2

TASK SELECTED		
ITEM	Nº	REACTIVE
Action	1.	<input type="checkbox"/> Can you describe how do you do the task?
	2.	<input type="checkbox"/> What is the most important action to do the task?
Product	3.	<input type="checkbox"/> How do you know that you finished the task?
	4.	<input type="checkbox"/> How do you know that the task is well done?
Tool	5.	<input type="checkbox"/> Make a list of the tools that you need to do the task.
	6.	<input type="checkbox"/> What is required to use the tools correctly?
Objective	7.	<input type="checkbox"/> Why do you have to do the task?
	8.	<input type="checkbox"/> Describe how is done the ideal task?
Motivation	9.	<input type="checkbox"/> Can you delegate the task to another person?
	10.	<input type="checkbox"/> Why the task must be made by you?
Subject	11.	<input type="checkbox"/> What knowledge do you need to do the task?
	12.	<input type="checkbox"/> What are the benefits to do the task?
Environment	13.	<input type="checkbox"/> Where do you do the task, can you describe the place?
	14.	<input type="checkbox"/> Can you do the task in another place, what is indispensable?
Problem	15.	<input type="checkbox"/> What are the causes to require doing the task?
	16.	<input type="checkbox"/> What are the effects to not do the task?
Stakeholders	17.	<input type="checkbox"/> Who are the essential people to do the task?
	18.	<input type="checkbox"/> Who benefits from the task?

TASK SELECTED		
ITEM	Nº	REACTIVE
Action	1.	<input type="checkbox"/> Can you describe how do you do the task?
	2.	<input type="checkbox"/> What is the most important action to do the task?
Product	3.	<input type="checkbox"/> How do you know that you finished the task?
	4.	<input type="checkbox"/> How do you know that the task is well done?
Tool	5.	<input type="checkbox"/> Make a list of the tools that you need to do the task.
	6.	<input type="checkbox"/> What is required to use the tools correctly?
Objective	7.	<input type="checkbox"/> Why do you have to do the task?
	8.	<input type="checkbox"/> Describe how is done the ideal task?
Motivation	9.	<input type="checkbox"/> Can you delegate the task to another person?
	10.	<input type="checkbox"/> Why the task must be made by you?
Subject	11.	<input type="checkbox"/> What knowledge do you need to do the task?
	12.	<input type="checkbox"/> What are the benefits to do the task?
Environment	13.	<input type="checkbox"/> Where do you do the task, can you describe the place?
	14.	<input type="checkbox"/> Can you do the task in another place, what is indispensable?
Problem	15.	<input type="checkbox"/> What are the causes to require doing the task?
	16.	<input type="checkbox"/> What are the effects to not do the task?
Stakeholders	17.	<input type="checkbox"/> Who are the essential people to do the task?
	18.	<input type="checkbox"/> Who benefits from the task?

27.2 APPENDIX II

STAGE 2 GUIDE

DESIGN PROTOCOL ANALYSIS

Procedure: Warm up - Questionary - Think aloud - Questionary

Space: The room should be quiet, a glass of water should be at hand, the chair should be comfortable. The computer should be connected, and the camera and audio tested.

QUESTIONARY 1

Question before starting the warmup.

- ~~What do you understand about design practice?~~
- ~~What do you consider is a design ability?~~

WARM UP EXERCISES

Instructions: Solve the problem while you say out loud what comes to your mind. You can take a piece of paper or use any kind of tool.

Exercise 1: ~~I have 5 chocolates more than Otto and he has 2 chocolates less than Mika, Mika has 3 chocolates, how many do I have?~~

Exercise 2: ~~My brother is older than my cousin, my cousin and my sister are born at the same time. If my cousin can drink a year before me and we are 3 siblings, who is the youngest of us?~~

QUESTIONARY 2

Question before starting the final task 4 questions (2 hides):

- Have you felt comfortable doing the warmup exercises?
- Have you felt some inconveniences doing the warmup exercises?

MAIN TASK

Task: make a digital presentation

Theme: ~~a type of presentation about your work~~

Material and tools: open selection, you can use all kinds of tools or data.

Time: between 20-30 min

Objective: start from scratch and finish it at a bare minimum acceptable to present a colleague, client or public.

Instructions: You are asked to perform this task in the way you are used to going about a commission in your daily practice. It is important that you say aloud everything that you think or do while making it.

QUESTIONARY 3

Questionary at finish the next task:

- ~~Do you consider that you have done a design task?~~
- ~~Do you consider that you have used design ability in the task?~~

27.3 APPENDIX III

27.4 APPENDIX IV

Guide interview

Stage 3

This guide is used by the interviewer to contain the narration that are not register in the ppt because should be oral.

Simulation case 1:

-Please listen carefully to the description while imaging a dragon described, remember that at the end you will have to possess a clear image of it to answer some questions, you will only hear the description once:

“This cartoonish dragon has 4 limbs with claws in all of them with big and strong legs and shorts arms. A long neck, strong and thick tail. Its big head had a long nose with big holes like a crocodile and big eyes. His head has horns, and two wings like from a bat growth from its back, without fur in his body and scales of red color.”

Questionary:

The question will appear sequentially to do not influence the answer with other data:

1. Do you have a clear image of the animal in your head?
2. Did you imagine different shapes of the animal before having the final one?
3. What are the main characteristics of the animal that you imagined?
4. Now choose one of the following images that better correspond with the mental image that you have of the animal. (Three options are presented)
5. Is this animal identical to what you imagined, why?
6. Why did you choose that animal?
7. Do you consider that what have you done is design, why?
8. Do you hear about design thinking, what it is?

Simulation case 2:

-Please listen carefully to the description and if you have any doubt please ask:

“Imagine you are in your major adulthood, already having a child son. Sadly, you have an accident that does not allow you to move any part of your body, you can’t talk but can hear and see. Also, suppose that our technology has gone as far as allows us to create some kind of peripheral artifact between your brain and a printer. So, you can

print exactly what are thinking when you decide to do it (that's how we know that you are fully rational like now). One day your young daughter visits you and ask you to make her a unicorn in a nice background."

Questionary:

1. Do you have a clear image of the animal in your head?
2. Describe your mental image?
3. If the technology existed, do you think that you could send to print that image, why?
4. You had printed that image. do you consider that what have you done is design, why?
5. Please choose one of the following images that better match your idea and explain why. (Three options are presented)

Simulation case 3:

-Please retain the original image in your head of your unicorn and the background while I keep the history:

"Your daughter receives your image she like the background and how the unicorn is in there, the size the position, even the color., but she didn't like the unicorn appearance as it wasn't as what she had in his book, she shows you the book and ask you to put that shape of the unicorn in the image that you made."

Questionary:

1. Can you have a clear image of the new image?
2. How do you swap the unicorn? Do you have to make some changes to the unicorn in the image?
3. Do you think now what you have done is design?
4. Is there any difference with the previous case?

Simulation case 3:

-Please listen carefully to the description while imaging a dragon described, remember that at the end you will have to possess a clear image of it to answer some questions, you will only hear the description once:

"This cartoonish dragon has 4 limbs with claws in all of them with big and strong legs and shorts arms. A long neck, strong and thick tail. Its big head had a long nose with big holes like a crocodile and big eyes. His head has horns, and two wings like from a bat growth from its back, without fur in his body and scales of red color."

Questionary:

1. Do you have a clear image of the animal in your head?
2. Did you imagine different shapes of the animal before having the final one?
3. What are the main characteristics of the animal that you imagined?
4. Now choose one of the following images that better correspond with the mental image that you have of the animal.
5. Is this animal identical to what you imagined, why?
6. Why did you choose that animal?
7. Do you consider that what have you done is design, why?

Behavior analysis:

Please answer the question related to the interview 2. A video of the episode is shown before starting the question in each slice. Although they all have different inquiries, they have in common the following:

1. Why do you ----- in this moment-----?
2. Do you have a mental image, an idea, or a set of conditions when you do ----
-----?

Specific questionary professional designers:

List of questions based on the interviews 1-2.

Specific questionary non-design professionals:

List of questions based on the interviews 1-2.

General questionary:

1. Do you consider that you have a mental image or idea of the presentation that you wanted to make before using the tools in power point?
2. Do you think that this mental image or idea was created by design ability, why?
3. Do you consider that the mental image or idea of the presentation is design, why?
4. In your opinion design ability could be the creation and nurture of ideas? Why?
5. How do you think a non/designer works differently his presentation in ppt?

27.5 APPENDIX V

27.6 APPENDIX VI

